

Influencing Factors of Social Commerce Adoption on SMEs in Pakistan: Implications for SMEs in Hospitality & Tourism Industry based on case studies

A thesis submitted for the degree of Doctorate of Business Administration

By

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Declaration

I certify that this work was not submitted for any other degree or professional qualification. I declare that my individual efforts resulted in this thesis.

09 June 2021

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ABSTRACT

Small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) contribute to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in several economies. After developing the latest information and communication technology (ICT) tools, many SMEs have contributed to enhancing their social commerce (SC) potential in developed countries. This development is relatively low in developing countries as compared to the developed nations. Therefore, the main aim of this study is to identify the influencing factors on the adoption of SC on SMEs in Pakistan. Recommendations were made to SMEs to adopt SC more effectively by integrating the TOE (Technological, Organisational and Environmental) model developed by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990).

Many previous studies solely focused on developed economies, and research on SC adoption in underdeveloped nations is limited. As a result, the primary goal of this study is to add to the body of information about the development and adoption of social commerce in SMEs in emerging economies after identifying key SC adoption determinants.

This research is being conducted in the context of SMEs in Pakistan's emerging economy. Twelve participants took part in this study from seven case studies. During the data collection process, all participants were either owner, social media managers/ executives or general managers from the same department.

The methodology adopted in undertaking this study is the qualitative research approach. This research has empirically identified the influencing factors affecting SMEs to adopt SC and the benefits of ICT use in their organizational performance. Semi-structured interview method were used to collect the data. In the next phase, Thematic Analysis (TA) method were used to identify the main themes, sub-themes and the codes.

Based on the results of the interviews, the conclusions suggest that SMEs in the Hospitality and Tourism sector are adopting SC mainly for marketing purposes to promote and enhance brand image. Furthermore, to attract and reach more prospective consumers, improve sales, enter new markets, and use SC as a customer care communication channel. According to the research, government support for SMEs and ICT infrastructure preparedness in Pakistan, internet affordability and availability, the benefits of SC platforms, and the functional diversity and simplicity of use are some of the primary motivations for using SC. Furthermore, the findings revealed that SC cost-effectiveness, low entry cost, and consumer popularity on Social Media (SM) are the primary motivators for SC adoption in SMEs. Moreover, assistance for small and medium-sized businesses and internal SM and business management were essential variables that motivated and enabled SMs to improve their performance in the implementation of SC.

However, to achieve successful SC implementation, SMEs are faced with several challenges. The fundamental problems were the lack of skills, trust, and SC rules and legislation in Pakistan. Furthermore, the unwillingness, if any and attitudes of management to pay SM charges has a particular influence to restrict SC adoption improvements. Furthermore, preliminary SC adoption plans, personal effort dependency and poor understanding of SC's broader functioning among small and medium-sized businesses were unwanted for SC adopts success in small and medium-sized enterprises. Lack of entrepreneurship, lack of IT skills, lack of IT understanding within society, lower literacy rate, and owner-manager positions were also significant factors influencing the adoption of SC within Pakistan's SMEs as a growing economy. The findings have ramifications for Pakistani government officials, IT providers, and small business owners. The low rate of SC adoption by SMEs in Pakistan has clear implications for the Pakistani government (GoP). The findings of this study may aid them in increasing the number of competent programmers and better targeting them to encourage SMEs in Pakistan to embrace SC.

This situation would provide an opportunity for IT suppliers to promote their goods and services. They should also evaluate the decisive variables of SC adoption to improve their chances of success. Many small business owners desire to increase their level of adoption to compete more effectively. Furthermore, various recommendations have been made for Pakistani SMEs, including best practices to adopt and bad practices to avoid. Successful SC implementation and better operational improvement outcomes are strongly connected with the effective adoption of best practice.

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List of Abbreviations

B2B	Business to Business
Ecommerce	Electronic Commerce
eWOM	Electronic Word of Mouth
GoP	Government of Pakistan
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HR	Human Resource
ICTs	Information and Communication Technology
IS	Information System
ISPs	Internet Service Providers
IT	Information Technology
PKR	Pakistani Rupees
PTA	Pakistan Telecommunication Authority
PTCL	Pakistan Telecommunication Limited
RQ	Research Question
SMEs	Small-Medium-Enterprises
SMEDA	Small-Medium-Enterprises Development Authority
SC	Social Commerce
SCCs	Social Commerce Components
SM	Social Media
SNSs	Social Network Sites
SP	Social Presence
sWOM	Social Word of Mouth
SBP	State Bank of Pakistan

SDNPK	Sustainable Development Networking Program
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TOE	Technology Environment Organization
TA	Thematic Analysis
(UNDP)	United Nations Development Program
USA	United States of America
UK	United Kingdom
WWW	World Wide Web

1. Introduction

This chapter is dedicated to giving the reader the relevant background information for this study. The backdrop of research is initially discussed, followed by the context of research. This involves informing the reader about the country in which this research has been conducted, the companies' size, the business phenomena under investigation, and the usage of the social media platform. The study objective and questions will then be discussed. This is followed by a brief examination of the methods of research, including the investigation process. The research contributions will, after that, be emphasised. In conclusion, the thesis framework is shown.

1.1. Research Background

Small-Medium-Size Enterprises (SMEs) play a distinctive starring role in an emerging market economy. Ayandibu (2017) illustrates that most developed countries acknowledge the importance of the SME sector in assisting their economies. Also, SMEs are the primary source of job creation and income generation in developing countries. These contributions of SMEs help developing nations to maintain and increase living standards. The rise of personal income assists people to contribute to the development and competitiveness of the economy.

Businesses are continually in technological transition in the age of globalisation (Acciaro et al., 2020). To achieve sustainable and competitive advantages, organisations must implement information and communication technology capabilities into their strategic initiative. New innovative sales and communication channels and new technologies have led several organisations to formulate the business strategy (Alonso-Dos-Santos & Liébana-Cabanillas, 2017). Since information and communication technologies (ICTs) are cost-effective and considered a tool to enhance economies, large organisations adopt these technologies to get competitive benefit in the market (Diaz-Chao et al., 2015). The performance of ICTs integration within the organisation depends on a variety of factors, including information technology (Liu et al., 2013), human resources capability (Poisat, 2017) and absorption capacity (Liu et al., 2013).

Numerous empirical studies illustrate that the significance of ICT adoption positively affects an organisation's growth, competitiveness, and performance (Haseeb et al., 2019; Yunis et al., 2017; Yunis et al., 2018). Unfortunately, the focus of these studies was mostly on large corporations. There is limited research to investigate the contributions of ICTs adoption amongst SMEs and their impact on SMEs capabilities, such as business performance, growth, marketing capacity, and competitiveness.

One factor contributing to the low rate of ICST adoption among SMEs is a lack of empirical research in SMEs. Other issues contributing to the low rate of SME adoption include a lack of financial resources, infrastructure, and organisational culture (Yunis et al., 2017; Rahayu and Day, 2017). Overall, penetration of ICTs in SMEs remains low in most countries compared with large organisations (Al Busaidi et al., 2019). Due to the number of challenges that SMEs face, such as lack of technical expertise, human resource, and limited financial resources in developing countries, they do not encourage them to adopt ICTs (Okundaye et al., 2019).

According to Okundaye (2016), ICTs tools are described as hardware, software, and services used to process information to meet the organisation's goals and objectives. There are several ICTs resources available for the companies to use, including SC. Three essential pillars enabled the emergence of social commerce: electronic commerce, social media apps, and Web 2.0 constructions. In this regard, social media plays a critical role in economic growth since it provides new opportunities for businesses and customers to communicate with one another (Rutovic, 2016). Therefore, Companies have started to use social media platforms to increase information sharing, communication, and cooperation (Kot et al., 2017). The majority of electronic commerce (e-commerce) organisations have begun to include Web 2.0 resources into their websites to assist their consumers in connecting with other consumers, promoting their purchase intention (Lu et al., 2016). Therefore, companies have recognised the significance of adopting SC, regardless of their scale and activities.

Since the introduction of advanced technology, SM dispersion has changed the way people exchange information and build relationships between vendors and consumers (Han et al., 2016). On every edge of the earth, a developing number of residents extensively depend on social media for information and discussion. SM is described as computer-generated communication that enables users to produce and share content, knowledge, images, and ideas or participate and contribute on social networking sites (Peck, 2014). Internet apps that build on web 2.0's ideological and technological features are referred to as social media. Virtual communities, microblogs, video/photo sharing platforms, social bookmarking, and other social applications, including weblogs and wikis, are social media forms; the purpose is to provide more diverse communication functions and meaningful platforms (Fuchs, 2017). Users share information and knowledge, opinion, and experience about the products they get and services of brands with other users with the same need and interest on social networking sites through provided online forums and communities (Han, Min, & Lee, 2016).

Globalisation has brought transformation in today's business environment that has created challenges in business conduct and generated numerous opportunities (Dijkmans, Kerkhof, & Beukeboom, 2015).

Managers can use these significant opportunities to engage stakeholders and also for speedy communication. Small businesses, which can support new developing trends, can benefit significantly from social media. The advent of social commerce is probably one of the most notable developments nowadays (Wamba & Carter, 2016). Zafar and Mustafa (2017) commented that SMEs are essential to every country's economic success and growth. In general, limited resources restrict the usage of SMEs in information technology systems and applications (Dwivedi & Sahu, 2014). Despite the favourable impact and growing number of adopters, the literature indicates that a small proportion of SMEs is convinced of social commerce adoption's perceived advantages and value (Adam et al., 2016). Section 1.2 provides an initial overview of the social commerce adoption.

1.2. Research Motivation

The adoption of social commerce has two directions of studies. The first direction covers the usage of SC and its effects on customer purchasing intention and behaviour (Alalwan, 2018; Liu et al., 2019; Zhang and Benyoucef, 2016). The second aspect is the impact and adoption of social commerce in the organisational context. From a corporate perspective, most of the literature pays attention to non-profit organisations and emphasises the public relation department. As mentioned in section 1.1 regarding its adoption in business contexts, most of the research focuses on large enterprises, with little research on SMEs' usage and adoption of social commerce.

Despite the growing importance, perceived value of social commerce for SMEs (Zamrudi and Wicaksono, 2018), there are limited studies about how SMEs use or adoption on social commerce technology. So far, only a few studies have investigated the use of SM to enhance business management and its effect on organisation performance, particularly in developing countries (Ahmad et al., 2019). Several studies have been carried out on the level of use, challenges, and metric system for social media in SMEs. There have been various research on social media usage levels, impediments, and metrics in SME environments (Adam et al., 2016; Puklavec et al., 2018). However, little is known about how social media use by SMEs in Pakistan affects their performance.

Since social media tools are economical and have little technological skill requirement, there are growing pieces of evidence that SMEs become early adopters of social media to enhance their customer support capabilities (Ahmad et al., 2018; Barnes et al., 2012). Low cost and minimal technical requirement make it easier for SMEs to deploy social media (Ferrer et al., 2013). Social media provide SMEs with an opportunity to implement or promote e-commerce based applications in a low-cost way. As a result of these shifting environments, SMEs must consider the impact on their

future business strategy (Idris et al., 2017). Internet-connected businesses can adopt social commerce without any additional resources. Small companies are increasingly adopting social media as their sole platform for conducting business, known as social commerce. Therefore, SM grows exponentially among enterprises and becomes a vital business management phenomenon (Trainor et al., 2014). As a result, organisations are adopting online platforms (Larsson, 2018). Social media is getting more popular among businesses because it makes the communication process quicker and confidential (Siamagka et al., 2015). Setting up an account on one or more social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter is the first step to start the process. Business owners provide their name, phone number, and other relevant information on their business account page. They then start advertising for products by uploading a post that includes a product photo and a product description. Interested customers in purchasing a product then contact the company owner via direct messages, embedded in the social media platform or mobile instant messaging services like Whatsapp (a popular instant messaging app in Pakistan).

Many scholars (Nisar et al., 2019; Odoom et al., 2017; McCann and Barlow, 2015) have explored the use of social media in business and specified that it could generate many advantages for businesses. Many researchers (Agnihotri et al., 2016; McCann and Barlow, 2015) revealed that SM could help enterprises get closer to their customers more efficiently and become more competitive. According to Icha and Agwu (2015), modern organisations view SM as a strategic tool for increasing firm value, sales, profits, and competitive advantage.

Braojos-Gomes et al. (2015) illustrate that despite the popularity and optimism towards SM in the business setting, the adoption rate of SC in SMEs has remained low. It's due to a lack of understanding of leveraging and reap the benefits of technology (Braojos-Gomes et., 2015). Modern organisations develop SM presence as a tool for marketing campaigns, advertisements, building relationships, information sharing, and interaction with the networked/mediated public. Therefore more research is needed on the adoption and impact of social commerce technologies in SMEs in developing countries.

As stated earlier, there is evidence that organisations that use social commerce technology can be benefited from market value and competitive advantage. Technological growth continues to occur in developing countries. There is much greater access to mobile phones in these countries than electricity, water supply or sewerage (Mitullah et al., 2016). These technological developments continue to lead to changes in traditional business practices. Even now, if we live in the 21st century, the digital gap between developed and developing countries persists. Many companies and customer are connected via new platforms or social network. This development to be the result of a new stream of e-commerce

called social commerce(Liang et al., 2011; Zhang and Benyoucef, 2016), but it's not happening in developing countries, as they need to use the designed social shopping sites system and models for SC (Saba et al., 2017). SC is generally embraced by SMEs worldwide after e-commerce. Millions of people access social media platforms that provide information about individuals and their network that can benefit organisations, especially SMEs.

There are numerous factors to the adoption and non-adoption of different technologies, so the E-commerce adoption by SMEs, in particular, has been studied to reveal the key drivers of adopting e-commerce. Existing literature directs that geographically diverse factors affecting e-commerce adoption vary. Due to cost, lack of knowledge and risk of change, Australian SMEs are less engaged towards digital business implementation (Molinillo and Japutra, 2017). In the Malaysian SMEs sector, adoption of web continuance will rely on CEO creativity, CEO IT attitude and the cost (Ramayah et al., 2016). Research on variables influencing e-business adoption and non-adoption has gained in many ways, as high-income economies have changed successfully by developing and creating e-commerce. Influencing factors and challenges of E-commerce adoption in developed and developing countries have been studying for a long time (Sharma, 2014, Lim et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2016). Existing literature indicates that cost is the most common factor in all countries amongst the adoption and non-adoption of E-business in SMEs. Furthermore, to the high cost of barriers, SMEs often have low access to infrastructure, lack of skilled labour, knowledge of e-commerce, high cost to computer equipment, which discourage SMEs to adopt the new technologies (Ahmed and Sinha, 2016).

Due to the limited resource of the inadequate information infrastructure (Cerchino ad Esposito, 2017), crucial electricity shortfall and lousy governance in developing countries like Pakistan are the most common barriers for SMEs to adopt the technology. Apart from those common barriers like electricity shortfall, cost, and lack of technical skills (Casidy et al., 2017), poor telecommunication infrastructure, lack of knowledge (Cerchino ad Esposito, 2017), and limited financial resources (Cerchino ad Esposito, 2017) seriously affects adoption of e-commerce in Pakistan. As a result, numerous SMEs diverting their focus towards the emerging trend of SC.

Social media is an appropriate approach for Pakistani SMEs as it offers several opportunities, including low cost, low IT skills and low barriers to adoption (Abed et al., 2017). In addition, SMEs can grow and develop brand communities and enter various market niches and promote their goods and services through social media (Guha et al., 2018). Social media offers a practical and straightforward strategy for SMEs to access future customers and build a comprehensive business network (Ghezzi et al., 2016),

build customer trust and loyalty, manage credibility and gain marketing knowledge (Han et al., 2016). Many SMEs feel that they must be engaged in SM (Abed, 2018).

At the centre of this research, the Pakistani SME sector is of interest for several causes. Firstly, Pakistan's average economic growth rate is rising at 4.7percent per year, with a population of 216.6 million and the fifth largest population in the South Asia region (Pakistan Economic Survey, 2019). This economic development has got the attention of the government. As a result, SMEs are making a significant contribution towards employment and GDP. Secondly, this sector has not been examined in Pakistan regarding social commerce adoption and information and communication technology (ICTs).

In short, this research is inspired by the lack of study on SC adoption and its use in Pakistan by SMEs. This study will develop the latest literature on the implementation of SC in emerging countries and specifically in Pakistan. In addition, this study will provide recommendations to managers regarding the different steps to adopt and implement SC in SMEs in Pakistan. Table 1.2 provide the full insight on the existent work on this topic.

Adam et al., 2016	Internal factors within entrepreneurs that influence the acceptance and use of Social commerce among SMEs in Malaysia
Ahmad et al., 2018	Reflections of entrepreneurs of small and medium-sized enterprises concerning the adoption of social media and its impact on performance outcomes
Alalwan, 2018	Investigating the impact of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention
Wamba and Cater, 2016	Social media tools adoption and use by SMEs
Puklavec et al., 2018	Understanding the determinants of business intelligence system adoption stages
Zamrudi, Z. and Wicaksono, 2018	Social Commerce Adoption in SME's

Table No. 1.2: Existing Work on Social Commerce Adoption in SMEs

1.3. Research Problem

As the technology evolves and matures, it brought new information and communication technology to allow users to send and receive messages virtually and quickly. It also created pools of knowledge sharing and trading online. "Social Commerce" is defined as "one form of commerce that is mediated by social networking sites and other social media that make use of both online and offline environments for business purposes" (Busalim et al., 2019).

PricewaterhouseCoopers (2017) reported in a survey that the shopping behaviour of 47% of 25000 digital buyers globally influenced by reading reviews, feedback and comment on SM, which shows the growing use of SM in community interactions and social commerce activities (Zafar et al., 2019). Another survey reported by Statista (2019) shows that more than 85% of Taiwanese digital users use social media, and Facebook was the most popular social network with a 95.8% penetration rate.

Social Networking Sites (SNSs) are advancing and fast, introducing technological trends into Pakistan's conventional industry and other developing countries (Zafar et al., 2019). Nowadays, SMEs in numerous sectors, including transportation, retail, telecommunication, and hospitality and tourism operators, have fan pages on social media to attract customers and attain a competitive advantage in Pakistan (Solangi et al., 2019).

Many scholars (Agwu and Murry, 2015; Ali et al., 2019; Abed, 2016; Abed, 2020; Saba et al., 2017) have shed light upon adopting social or e-commerce from different dimensions countries such as Nigeria, Malaysia and Saudi Arabia. For example, Agwu and Murray (2015) illustrates the barriers of e-commerce adoption, Akam and Mishra (2017) discussed the factors influencing consumer intention in social commerce adoption, Abed (2016) importance of social commerce in Saudi Arabian SMEs, an empirical study upon social commerce adoption using Technology-organisation-environment.

Furthermore, the researcher has explored and carried the deep research on online data bases such as emerald, google scholar, British library Ethos Website, Elton Bryson Stephens Company (EBSCO). Not a single article has addressed this issue (influencing factors of social commerce adoption on SMEs in Pakistan). In fact, only a few publications on Pakistani IS/ICT have been published. Only one article on ICTs in the context of SME was published, which was perhaps unanticipated. Most studies on ICTs in Pakistan have so far focused on their impact on customer behaviour and purchasing intent (Talat et al., 2013; Sair and Danish, 2018; Solangi et al., 2019; Hassan et al., 2018). There was not a single

paper published that addressed the adoption of ICTs or social commerce technologies from an organisational standpoint.

None of the studies was carried out to investigate the different steps that SMEs have to go through to adopt social commerce, critical influencing factors, challenges of SC adoption, the impact of SC adoption on the organisation. Therefore, this study will address the social commerce adoption from an organisational perspective.

1.4 Research Context

This study focuses on small enterprises in Pakistan that have used social media platforms for trading reasons. As a result, it is critical to offer the context of this research in terms of the nation in which it was conducted, the size of the enterprises engaged, the business phenomena under investigation, and the social media platform employed.

1.4.1. SMEs (Small Medium Enterprises)

Entrepreneurs must determine how their small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) will connect with clients and value them as part of the strategic decisions in 'business model' creation and evolution (Björkdahl, 2020). The role of the strategic decision means examining that digitisation stages can be used for SMEs within the allocated time and resources (Li, 2020). With the help of the World Wide Web, these choices can increasingly eliminate the barriers for the organisation setup, leading the many new entries to the marketplace and, specifically, the SMEs (Warner and Wäger, 2019; Dahnil et al., 2014).

This previous development is significant because (1) entrepreneurs' SMEs are a vital aspect of many economies—for example, SME's employ over 70% of the entire workforce in the UK economy—and (2) eCommerce provides the most feasible approach of building efficient retail channels and therefore overcoming their inherent resource limits (Kirchhoff, 1994; Kirchhoff et al., 2013; Storey, 1994). Apart from cutting their investment and transaction costs in building both marketing and distribution channels, E-commerce also reduces transportation barriers and eliminates physical limits of time and place, allowing SMEs to expand their client bases (Santarelli and D'Altri, 2003). Especially, internet-based E-commerce technology will enable SMEs to better engage and connect with prospective new and existing consumers, perform less expensive market research, and provide more effective and efficient customer care and support (Auger and Gallagher, 1997; Hoffman and Novak, 1995).

Early research on e-commerce adoption revealed that businesses evolve through phases in adopting ICT and e-commerce technologies, moving from one stage to the next in a well-planned, sequential process (Daniel, 2003; Taylor and Murphy, 2004). An interest in the technological components of the e-commerce adoption process was a recurring theme in this early research. Some scholars divided the stages of e-commerce development into two categories: early acceptance and later institutionalisation (Grandon et al., 2011; Kapurubandara, 2009; Molla and Licker, 2005; Tan et al., 2007). Lefebvre et al. (2005) researched the manufacturing sector of Canadian SMEs to capture the progressive unfolding of Business to business (B2B) e-commerce in SMEs. In the penetration of e-commerce, they discovered a reasonable evolutionary route. Their findings suggest that there are more benefits to e-commerce than previously thought. SMEs have also explored new and entrepreneurial approaches and were ready to enhance their company operations through the use of websites, according to the report (Lefebvre et al., 2005). E-mail and the internet were the most common e-commerce activity in early surveys, and websites' usage is limited.

An organisation named "Packages Ltd" began its work in 1957 on computers and began the computerisation process in Pakistan. Since then, the use of IT is rising gradually. Although Pakistan's government initially was slow in implementing and disseminating IT, IT is now one of its top priorities. In both public and private sectors, IT is commonly used for numerous activities. Ministry of IT is fully responsible for monitoring all IT related issues along with other departments/institutes like E-Government Directorate, Pakistan Computer Bureau, Pakistan Software Export Board, Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, Computer Society of Pakistan, Pakistan Software Houses Association (PASHA) etc. in other words, the speedy usage of IT in variety of sectors is rising day by day with all support of the Government of Pakistan. Reduction in the cost of both hardware and software is another factor behind the extension of information technology.

SMEs in the Pakistani private sector are the most common form of organisation. SMEs constitute approximately 90% of all enterprises in Pakistan (Iqbal and Ahmad, 2020). SMEs are creating 80percent of jobs in the non-agriculture sector (Iqbal and Ahmad, 2020). Also, the contribution of Pakistani SMEs is 40% of the country's annual GDP (Iqbal and Ahmad, 2020). Thus the government stresses the role of SMEs by promoting and help young Pakistani entrepreneurs. For instance, the government of Pakistan has launched a program called Ignite to support and encourage entrepreneurship in youth (Pakistan Today, 2020). Despite the government's steps to promote SMEs to embrace the ICTs, only a limited number of SMEs are fully aware of the advantages of emerging technology.

Next, section 1.5 represents a summary of the theoretical framework supporting the research effort described in this thesis.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

Research on emerging technology and implementation has established several theories and models to cope with the adoption at the consumer and organisational levels in the research literature regarding theoretical models used in technology adoption. Oliveira and Martins (2011) identified that the Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) Framework is the essential theoretical lens used to examine the adoption and implementation of new technology in the organisation. This research takes advantage of the TOE framework by (Tornatzky, Fleischer and Chakrabarti, 1990) for two reasons. Firstly, it was commonly used to comprehend the integration of innovative technology in an organisation (Oliveira and Martins, 2011) and provide a clear theoretical and methodological foundation (Anamuah-Mensah and Marfo, 2009). Secondly, this theory has been widely used to explore the adoption of prior technologies in the SMEs context; social commerce adoption using TOE framework: An empirical investigation of Saudi Arabian SMEs by Abed (2018) and the factor affecting S-commerce adoption among micro and small-medium enterprises in a sub-urban and Rural Economic area by (Zulkiffli et al., 2020) are comparatively recent examples.

1.6. Research Aim and Objectives:

Based on the discussed rationale so far in the introduction chapter: this research aims to investigate the social commerce adoption from the organisational perspective with the emergence of social media platforms. It also aims to develop a recommended strategies for SMEs to adopt social commerce in Pakistan. The aim of this research can help SMEs in Pakistan for more social commerce adoption. Due to the increasing use of SC in Pakistan's public sector, this study explores opportunities, barriers, and key influencing and critical success factors for s-commerce adoption. Furthermore, this study will investigate the technological, organisational and environmental factors to make recommendations to the SMEs managers to adopt social commerce more effectively.

Identifying the influencing or inhibiting factor of social commerce adoption would assist in understanding the potential that social commerce offers to SMEs. Understanding these factors would

also help provide insight for policymakers, stakeholders, and business practitioners to stimulate the adoption of social commerce technology.

The following objectives were defined to address the above-stated aim of this research:

- To understand different steps Pakistani SMEs have to go through during the Social Commerce adoption process.
- To understand the critical success factors influencing the SC adoption among SMEs in Pakistan.
- To investigate the drivers and challenges that SMEs face in Pakistan during the SC adoption.
- To understand the impact of SC on SMEs and make recommendations to SMEs in Pakistan for a successful SC adoption to their business.

1.7. Research Question and Sub-Question

The research question of this study aims to explore the adoption of social commerce in SMEs present in Pakistan and underline key factors making an impact of social commerce adoption on the organisation. From the central research question, four more additional sub-questions were explored.

- i. What are the different steps to adopt SC in Pakistan?
- ii. What are the drivers and challenges of SC adoption amongst SMEs in Pakistan?
- iii. What are the critical success factors influencing SC adoption?
- iv. What is the impact of SC adoption on SMEs, and what recommendations can be made to adopt SC more effectively?

1.8. Research Methodology

In this research study, the author chose to use the qualitative research method. The prevailing method is the qualitative method, represented by interview questions filled by the owner/manager. The questionnaire was the most effective way to collect data from a large sample of the population. The thesis is exploratory and descriptive and takes a qualitative method to research. As the aim of this study is exploratory nature in section 1.4, the research follows an epistemological approach consists of the qualitative research mode chosen.

Data collection was taken in two phases. In the first phase, a survey was undertaken to determine SMEs to be interviewed and used as a case study. Boodhoo and Purmessur (2009) illustrated that case studies

had been used to collect descriptive data through extensive analysis of an event, organisation or circumstances. In the second phase of research, Semi-structured interviews have been carried out with SMEs Owners, Directors, Head of department and Marketing manager for data collection purposes. This research also aims to investigate the level of ICTs adoption in Islamabad and Rawalpindi, Pakistan. Islamabad was selected as a context of study for two purposes. Firstly, Islamabad is the capital and economic centre of Pakistan, with many Pakistani SMEs in both cities too. Secondly, it has the maximum technologically built infrastructure in the county (Javed, 2020).

1.9. Significance of the Research

Information Technology is becoming a more and more extremely influential force in every aspect of the world's growth. Many SMEs in developed countries have recently adopted and implemented ICTs for development, compared to Pakistan, where the adoption and implementation of ICTs are shallow in SMEs.

Thus, this research is of significant importance for the Pakistani economy as it aims to highlight the influential factor to adopt new technology, especially social commerce in SMEs. Examining these factors may lead to encourage further entrepreneurship ventures and to generate more start-ups. In addition, this research will contribute to the limited literature on social commerce in Pakistan since this research is aimed to investigate the adoption of social commerce within the organisational context. Its findings are aimed to provide a deeper understanding of challenges associated with the adoption of social commerce surrounding Pakistani SMEs. They can help to improve ICTs adoption in developing countries such as Pakistan. Furthermore, the research recommendations would lead to the effective use of emerging technology.

On the practical hand, this research will significantly impact practitioners, especially in social commerce in developing countries. In addition, this research will make suitable recommendations to the management about the significance of SC adoption and its successful implementation in the organisation, particularly Pakistani SMEs.

Also, senior administration, IT executives, strategy makers, business managers, social media marketing managers and government department will be benefiting from this research as it will enable them to understand advantages associated with the adoption of SC along with critical success and

failure factors of SC adoption. Finding this study will also assist stakeholders, practitioners, and researchers adopt and manage ICTs initiatives within Pakistani SMEs.

1.10. Dissertation Structure

There are five chapters in this research study.

1.10.1. Chapter 1

We give the reader an introduction in Chapter 1. This chapter is where the thesis' background is brought forth to frame the issue at hand. This chapter begins with a backdrop to the subject, followed by a description of the topic, and finally, the goal and research questions. The thesis outline is set out after this chapter.

1.10.2. Chapter 2

In Chapter 2, some relevant literature is addressed, and a framework for social commerce adoption is established. The frame of reference serves as a framework for obtaining, analysing, and discussing empirical evidence.

1.10.3. Chapter 3

In Chapter 3, the methodology of the conducted research is described. The chapter covers the research purpose, approach and strategy, and the gathering and analysing of the literature and data. The chapter ends with a discussion of the reliability, validity and generalizability of this research. The purpose of this chapter is to describe the scientific method of this study, and in doing that, the reliability of the empirical results will increase since the tools and context of the research will become available for other researchers to understand, repeat, and improve.

1.10.4. Chapter 4

Chapter 4 analyses and discusses the findings reported in chapter 4 utilising and comparisons with the literature represented in chapter 2. The thesis is established while it is shown that the data and literature are added to it. This chapter will frame the thesis while showing its addition to existing data and literature.

1.10.5. Chapter 5

In Chapter 6, the conclusion and implications and direction for future research will be provided. Also, this chapter is designed to address the topic of study and summaries chapter 4. Recommendations regarding SC adoption to SMEs are also presented in this chapter.

1.11. Summary chapter

The goal of this chapter was to provide the reader with an overview of current research. The research context was provided first, followed by the research background. This includes describing the country in which the study took place, the size of the enterprises, the business phenomena under investigation, and the social media platform employed. The dissertation framework was then presented, followed by the aim of the research and research questions.

Because of changes in the definitions of Social Commerce in the previous studies, this definition was established in this study that the use of third-party SNS by vendors such as Facebook, Instagram, and others to create social contact with the customers and between the customers with regards to their business activities, goods and services (Sharma et al., 2018, Nisar and Prabhakar, 2017, Lu et al., 2016). Tuten and Solomon (2017) considered social commerce a crucial marketing tool as it empowers users to evaluate the products and share information with others in online communities. Social media tools can improve the communication between the organisation and their stakeholders (e.g. consumers, suppliers, business partners etc.) (Wamba & Carter, 2016). Organisations can integrate SNS into their business strategy to gain value from customer retention and loyalty, brand reputation and awareness, customer traffic (Montalvo, 2016). Facilitating the interaction between like-minded communities and relying on our society on online peers' opinions facilitate the decision-making process. In the service industry, consumers are now increasingly relying on social media to evaluate the quality and performance of services. It significantly impacts consumers' decision-making process for the travel industry (Kwahk & Kim, 2017).

Many scholars have found that technology can improve business performance and processes in different aspects. For instance, SM use positively impacts customer relationships (Rodriguez et al., 2015). As a result, the current study is relevant in addressing SMEs' adoption and usage of ICTs in developing nations, particularly Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

The research topic area that this study intended to address was introduced in the previous chapter. The research background, research environment, and research goal and questions were all provided. Following that, an overview of the research process and research contributions was presented. Finally, a thesis structure was introduced.

This chapter begins with a study of the differences between the developed and the emerging countries. It also discusses the significance of Social commerce in the hospitality industry and specifically in the Pakistani SMEs context in which the research was conducted. Furthermore, advantages and challenges related to the adoption, to achieve a better overview of the new technologies concerning the previous studies of technology adoption in the SMEs context.

In the study of social commerce literature in enterprises, especially in SMEs, it is apparent that the term social commerce is used interchangeably with other words such as social media, e-commerce and Web 2.0. As a result, section 2.9 describes and addresses the use of social commerce in the organisational context, particularly in SMEs. This section ends with an analysis of the social commerce adoption advantages for SMEs. In the following section, 2.10 addresses the key characteristics of social commerce and their role in adopting social commerce.

This chapter reviews the relevant literature, which is influenced by the research aim and objectives. An overview of the present condition of social commerce in Pakistan and its limitations and barriers found in the literature are discussed further.

2.2. Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

Definition of SMEs enables and generates revenues, assets, employees, and sales below a certain threshold (Cunningham & Rowley, 2008). Each economic organisation and country has its definition for SMEs. For instance, SMEs definition in the United States is not well distinct, whereas European Union uses less than 250 employees (Eurostat, 2019). The European Commission defines SMEs as "small and medium-sized companies." The number of employees and the financial turnover or balance sheet total is the two most essential elements in assessing whether a company is a small or medium-sized business. A small business (SME) is defined as a firm with less than 250 employees and a turnover of less than €50 million (Eurostat, 2019). Roughly 99% of all UK firms are small and

medium-sized firms and are consequently highly essential to the British economy. Millions of people are employed in SMEs and are widely viewed as the primary driver for development and sustainability.

The United States defines SMEs different from the EU definition. According to the SBA (2021), In the US, medium-sized companies with under 500 staff are considered SMEs. Small corporations usually have less than 50 employees, while micro-enterprises have just ten employees.

In addition, in the Asia-Pacific region, SME definition varies from country to country, depending on a country's economic condition. In developed and less developing countries, small- and medium companies have been characterised by various factors such as different industries, employee numbers, production volume, and revenue and asset prices (Majama and Magang, 2017). The overall number of SME employees in some developing economies ranges from 100 to 300.

In conclusion, SMEs have been defined differently, based on the number of employees, yearly turnover, financial assets, input use, manufacturing capability, the technology implementation level, management techniques, and on the particular industry, state, and country characteristics

Pakistan has no single definition for Small and Medium Size Enterprises. For example, different government institutes, the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP), the Federal Statistical Bureau (FBS) and Provincial Labor Department, etc., use their definitions. However, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA), which works under the Ministry of Industries and Production, has proposed an SME definition.

Enterprise Category	Employment Size	Paid Up	Capital Annual Sales
Small & Medium Enterprise (SME)	Up to 250	Up to Rs. 25 Million	Up to Rs. 250 Million

Table No. 2.1: Definition of SMEs in Pakistan

2.2.1 Role of Small and Medium Size Enterprises

SMEs comprise most businesses in most economies, including developed and developing countries. They have a vital contribution to job creation towards innovation and are crucial in the socio-economic development of the nations (Napitupulu et al., 2018). The SME sector also played a significant role in poverty alleviation, economic development and work creation within developing and developed

countries (Zafar and Mustafa, 2017). Since SMEs are the primary source of job creation, growth and innovation, it has improved the global market competitiveness (Napitupulu et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Zafar and Mustafa, 2017).

In Indonesia, a developing economy, SMEs account for more than 95percent of all enterprises. (Rahayu and Day, 2015). On the other hand, the USA is a developed country and SMEs accounts contribute over 70% of its Gross Domestic Products (GDP) (Elbeltagi et al., 2016; Zafar and Mustafa, 2017). While in Africa, its contribution toward employment and the GDP is more than 50% (Elbeltagi et al., 2016; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018). SMEs are the primary source of jobs in the region and run 90% of businesses in Nigeria. (Agwu and Murray, 2015; Gbandi and Amissah, 2014).

SMEs represent 99% of all companies in economically developed nations like the United States and account for more than 50% of workers, 98% of exports and 65% of employment in the new private sector (Elbeltagi et al., 2016). Entrepreneurship development of SMEs has been a popular technique for providing jobs, money, poverty reduction and a socioeconomic growth environment in underdeveloped nations (Elbeltagi et al., 2016; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018; Zafar and Mustafa, 2017).

Several researchers stated that larger organisations benefit from economic growth because they are more likely to create innovation than smaller companies (Harness et al. 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015), while others stated that smaller enterprises play a more critical role in economic development than the larger enterprises (Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Oguet al., 2018). Larger companies are far more advantageous than small businesses such as more extraordinary skills, greater understanding of science, the capacity to utilise economies of scale, access to cheaper and more significant financial resources, and superior risk management (Harness et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Oguet al., 2018).

The benefits that small and medium-sized businesses have over huge enterprises. SME and small and medium-sized enterprises executives have increased flexibility, less bureaucracy, fewer organisational hierarchies to govern and more informal corporate cultures to promote better communication and market reconciliation (Harness et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Oguet al., 2018). In contrast to more prominent companies, small and medium-sized companies' CEOs are better equipped to react to market situations due to their scale, innovation, and flexibility (Napitupulu et al., 2018; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018).

2.2.2 Factors affecting Growth of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

Small and medium-sized enterprises are crucial in economic development, but many problems prevent their growth in developing nations like Pakistan. These problems include insufficient funding; considerably low technology-enhanced infrastructures; inadequate and expensive IT facilities, shortage of skilled people, low business skills and performance, productivity and growth impacts in terms of staff turnover (Gbandi and Amissah, 2014; Tobora, 2014). The national innovation climate, including the government policy, business expenses, and communication infrastructure quality, is a significant element that affects SME growth (Mazzarol et al., 2014). Further impeding the development of small businesses include limited access to technology advancement, limited access to the global market, government policies, socioeconomic factors, availability of financial and non-financial support, weak institutional capacity, low financial strength, leadership skills in top management, lack of management support and organisational culture (Rahayu and Day, 2015, 2017; Tarutè and Gatautis, 2014; Tobora, 2014).

Amid impressive development and contributions, Pakistanis SMEs face common challenges, including the latest technology deficiencies, lack of financial resources, insufficient industrial infrastructure and mismanagement of intangible capitals, not qualified workforce, unskilled management, obsolete production facilities and so on (Khaliq et al., 2015). As per SMEDA, 90% of all businesses in Pakistan are SMEs. SMEs, especially in emerging nations, has grown increasingly important over the years and have formed the backbone of any country's economy. SMEs account for almost 90 per cent of total companies worldwide and have an essential role in producing jobs (Nebel, 2018). The flexibility, adaptation capacity and innovation of SMEs are typically regarded as advantageous (Rahayu and Day, 2017; Zafar and Mustafa, 2017). Therefore, SMEs have been slow to adopt the latest technology due to their small and limited resources.

2.3. The Role of Leadership in SMEs Growth

Leaders are significant to all sorts of organisations and have various roles and functions in the organisation. Currently, the objective of any company is to improve its performance and to retain its entity. Companies must always increase their efficiency to be highly competitive in marketplaces (Prajogo, 2016). Many authors (Choudhary et al., 2013; Vego, 2015; Maamari and Majdalani, 2017)

indicated that Leadership is vital in achieving effective organisational performance previously and till today's literature suggests.

According to Warrick (2017), Leadership is an integral part of any organisation's progress and success. The explanation for this is that all strategies and business decisions are usually taken into account by the organisation's leaders. The market success will have a general impression on effective and expeditious choices made by the company's leaders.

Effective leadership has been the core element for driving SMEs' performance (Madanchian et al., 2015). In SMEs, the literature (Franco and Prata, 2019) illustrates that inadequate and insufficient leadership skills are the key reasons for SMEs' failure. For that reason, SMEs have to improve their leadership skills to lead their organisations through all circumstances of crisis. Exemplary leadership is an essential factor to prevent organisational failure and to have effective organisational performance. As Warrick (2017) approved, Effective leaders, are necessary because of leaders' commitment to an organisation's success.

On the other hand, and since all SMEs are becoming highly competitive, the way they manage human capital often affects a dynamic environment full of changes and problems. Currently, people are seen as human capital (Mayo, 2016) as an essential part of the company's progress, adding to the enterprise greater or less value. However, it will happen if the organisation must recognise them, inspire them to show and acknowledge their capabilities to contribute to the enterprise's success. There must be behavioural engagement that the leader must facilitate, and its effectiveness depends on the management. Franco and Prata (2019) concludes that the Leader is the founder and strives for constructive action amongst multiple SME leaders.

Many writers have discovered several organisation characteristics (Boukamcha and Taylor, 2019) to impact SME leadership. However, according to Maamari and Majdalani (2017), there has been no consensus on these criteria so far. The better you grasp the importance of leadership in small and medium-sized companies, the more you can contribute to their growth.

In the light of global competitiveness and the degree of customer requirements, leadership is becoming more critical. According to Porter (1996), influential leaders must be able to discipline the firm to decide what must be done and adapt to changes to the industry, avoid the dispersion of organisational goals and maintain the firm's identity. Anderson (2009) recommended that the behaviour or role is a

factor that can stimulate SME growth and performance. Slevin and Covin, (1990) Firm's administrative planning is directly linked to the leader's behaviour or role

2.4. Hospitality and Tourism industry

The tourism sector is now recognised globally as a significant socio-economic contributor for developing and developed countries. Tourism is warranted to generate revenue in many sectors such as industries (Transportation Services, Retail Food, Cultural and sports services) and commodities (Accommodation, Transportation, Entertainment, Attractions) (Lundberg, 2017).

It is a multidimensional commercial activity with a high capacity for job creation due to its labor-intensive nature, revenue generation through tax collection, mainly from the hotel sectors, massive foreign exchange earnings and the relationship of cross-cultural apprehension and cooperation, business opportunities for entrepreneurs, and economic development of the country (Adnan et al., 2013; Rana, 2015). This sector generates rapid and widespread fiscal activity, which aids in poverty reduction and peacekeeping. It is often referred to be the most significant voluntary transfer of money from affluent to impoverished countries (Mitchell & Ashley, 2009). Global tourism has grown its importance in many economies throughout the world during the last several decades. Tourism may also be a source of income for students, parents, retirees, and various other individuals by offering part-time employment (Jucan & Jucan, 2013).

Global tourism has a vital role in promoting international peace by facilitating intermediation and building a bridge between civilisations. Global tourism also assists destination nations at the micro-level increase family wages through the two methods listed below. First, it increases efficacy by increasing rivalry among tourism-related businesses, and second, it encourages the use of economies of scale in domestic companies. Tourism development increases family income and produces jobs in both the formal and informal sectors of the target nation. It might be a sector that helps to alleviate extreme family poverty while simultaneously promoting economic development (Khan et al., 2019). Tourism expansion may help middle- and low-income economies improve economically; however, the same cannot be said for rich ones (Malik et al., 2020). Countries with a more significant outward-bound business travel market are more likely to profit from increased exports and trade growth (Khan, 2020).

2.4.1. Hospitality and Tourism industry in Pakistan:

Pakistan is one of the world's top tourism destinations country. It has diverse adventurous, scenic and cultural heritage attractions (The British Backpacker Society, 2018). Becker (2016) illustrated that bad governance and lack of marketing strategies could push tourism down, leading to the degeneration of multiple revenue channels. Together with the total GDP of developing countries and the contribution of tourism to it, Pakistan lags well behind them. Scholar (Khan et al., 2019) pointed to the numerous reasons Pakistan has not taken advantage of tourism's socio-economic benefits. Pakistan has just a 2.8% share in its GDP for travel and tourism, compared to other developed countries of the world, it is about 30%. Alasttal and Burdey (2017) identified the critical reason for Pakistan's slow development in the tourism sector was the shortage of skilled staff. Moreover, employee's attitudes, behaviour and performance, leading to customer loyalty and satisfaction, are the main drivers of service quality in the tourist industry (Malik et al., 2020).

According to the World Bank's World Development Indicators, foreign tourist arrivals and revenues are affected by security concerns. Total tourist arrivals climbed by 8% each year between 1995 and 2000; however, the 9/11 terrorist attacks in the United States and the subsequent security actions in the nation negatively impacted worldwide visitor arrivals in 2001–2003 (–11%). Arrivals of global visitors then resumed to progress and tempted to backsets in 2007–2008. In 2003–2011, the yearly growth rate of worldwide visitor arrivals climbed by 11%, with a peak of 1.161 million tourists coming after that period. Tourist arrivals declined by 17% in 2012 as a result of a series of interior terrorist acts. The improvement in national security in 2015–2016 is positive, and it might be attributed to the subsequent increase in tourist arrivals (World Bank, 2018).

Pakistan is dealing with a significant terrorist problem, which is having a negative influence on worldwide tourism. After the incident on September 11, 2001, in the United States, Pakistan joined the fight against terrorism. The country suffered significant human and financial losses as a result of the struggle against terrorism. Terrorism had a considerable influence on the tourism industry, causing infrastructural damage. Tourism in Pakistan is declining as a result of terrorism and deteriorating infrastructure. Terrorist attacks have had a significant impact on tourism activity (Henderson et al., 2010). Foreign visitors avoid visiting nations that have a frightening atmosphere as a result of terrorism. Empirical research in numerous countries reveals a negative relationship between tourism and terrorism (Apleni et al., 2020; Brondoni, 2017).

Since the newly formed government in 2017, they are taking measures to encourage tourism through the initiatives like e-visa and visa on arrival (Khan, 2020). On both local and international levels, the

current government has recognised the importance of raising awareness in developing the hospitality and tourism sector as one of the country's key economic drivers. Pakistan's hospitality and tourism industry has potential in the shape of cultural sites, religious sites, high peaks, snow-covered mountains, gushing waterfalls and lakes, fairy meadow and the Gandhara strip (PTDC, 2020).

Pakistan has significant tourist potential, various heritages and civilisations, rough mountains, beautiful lakes, rivers, deserts, seashores, and friendly and welcoming people. Pakistan has extremely excellent tourism potential due to its diverse cultures, intriguing landscapes, beautiful beaches, and many attractions and places that cater to both local and foreign travellers.

To contextualise the more extensive debate, the next part offers a quick summary of the evolution of ICTs and their application in SMEs.

2.5. The Evolution of Technology Communication and Its Role in SMEs

Globalisation has accelerated the development of new technology to the point where a significant breakthrough occurs daily (Joensuu-Salo et al., 2018; Oladimeji et al., 2017). ICTs refer to the devices/software used to send, preserve, sort, display, create, and automate information dissipation (Modimogale and Kroeze, 2011). These devices include products like phone lines, mobiles, radio networks, satellite systems, videos and computers, network, hardware and software applications, and all those equipment and services linked to these technologies, including emails, video conferences and blogs as well as social media (Ali et al., 2016). It was further described that ICT is an integrated framework that integrates information/data processing, manipulates, delivers, and transmits the information (Ali et al., 2016). The study also found that all ICTs tools can be categorised into two main categories such as hardware and software. The hardware consists of physical machinery used in different ways to process information. The software consists of information or programmers to define activities carried out by hardware and how they are accomplished. Therefore, ICT can be named "Organised communication networks and data resource" to collect, transform, and distribute information amongst and within the organisation, including SMEs (Foerster-Metz et al., 2018). Hence, ICT can be conceived to deliver information, facilitate interaction, and compete with society and the organisation's information and communication environment.

Due to the development in ICTs, there are various cost-effective and flexible forms of technology available. Prasanna (2019) revealed that revolutionary developments in ICTs have arisen from Web-

based technology as they helped SMEs approach foreign markets. He further illustrates that technology eliminates the economic barrier because it enhances production factors' productivity, capital, and efficiency. Social networking is defined as part of Internet Communication Technology (ICT), based on the Web 2.0 philosophy and technology definition, facilitating the production and sharing of information generated (Chu and Kim, 2011). There are different channels for social media marketing, such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, YouTube, Instagram, LinkedIn and many more. These platforms give users, especially companies, a competitive edge (Pradiptarini, 2011). Technological developments are the process of economic invention and innovation. The design means the scientific research needed to upgrade the economy's production system, whereas innovation means using new technological breakthroughs for industrial purposes.

Kumara (2019) illustrates that technological developments change the fundamental boundary right with a certain amount of manufacturing inputs and disrupt the search for new tools. Developed countries such as the United States of America (USA), Australia, Singapore, the United Kingdom (UK), Canada, and South Korea have achieved economic progress through technological progress.

Several studies have been conducted on the use of internet-based software in businesses, especially SMEs. By examining how SMEs use ICTs as a multidimensional framework, many authors have made diverse and contradictory findings to support the relationship between ICT adoption and a firm's performance. Some studies have found that ICT adoption does not significantly impact productivity (Cardona et al., 2013), although opposite findings are available (Brambilla and Tortarolo, 2018; Gupta et al., 2020). Ghobakhloo and Ching (2019) suggested that the integration and information system and digital technologies must be a strategic priority of SMEs. To support and achieve business goals, these tools must become be a fundamental part of the organisations (Eze et al., 2019).

Furthermore, since the general introduction of ICTs in the 1970s, the cost of purchasing ICTs has fallen dramatically. The modern world, dominated by knowledge, globalisation, growing digitalisation, competition and information sharing, have changed the business mode (Bouwman et al., 2018). This modern technological world is facilitated by a significant level of support in IT and data processing in various industries (Maroufkhani et al., 2020). With these technical developments, the use and adoption of modern IT applications become significant strength for SMEs (Bresnahan and Yin, 2017). Collis and Hussey (2013) identified that an organisation's existing technology plays a vital role in implementing new technology because it determines the latest technology's opportunities and pace to be implemented. Therefore, adopting new technologies will also offer more business gains and opportunities to large companies and SMEs. In the era of digitisation, where everyone uses new digital

devices such as smartphones and social media, technology has become the primary tool for learning, managing, and evaluating at a reduced cost (Alsghaier et al., 2017). Therefore, Investment becomes less critical regarding efficiency, coordination, and adopting new technologies in SMEs (Molinillo and Japutra, 2017). From the point of SMEs, these applications opened the door for the small organisations to achieve possible ICT advantages such as enhanced customer service and growth in sales and revenue. Section 2.9.2 provides more information on the adoption and benefits of social commerce for SMEs.

2.5.1. Digital Information and Technology Adoption in the Organisational Context

In today's digital economy, the usage of IT-based systems is a fundamental tool for the local authorities and organisation. Indeed, ICT has been an instrument for systemic improvements in the fast-changing world's companies (Perkin and Abraham, 2017). Individual user and organisations both are getting benefit from the development and evolution of information technology. Therefore, the literature has shown that this evolution has influenced organisations in different ways. IT innovation implementation consists of many processes that a corporation must implement before introducing new technology into the organisation. In this regard, Rogers (1995) defines adoption as

"... The process through which an individual or other decision-making association passes from first knowledge of innovation to forming an attitude towards innovation, to a decision to adopt or reject, to implementation of the new idea, and confirmation of this decision".

For instance, Damanpour (2017) directs the two most recognisable stages, i.e., invention and implementation. Furthermore, Ongori and Migiro (2010) revealed three changes triggered by the emergence of ICT that alter business practices. First, the evolution of ICT influences the structure of the organisation and affects competition between enterprises. Second, a positive shift in their competitive advantage is realised by firms implementing ICT into their strategies. The third change is related to the direct impact on company activities.

These developments have driven organisations to consider the opportunities provided by ICTs to succeed in the global market. ICT inventions were deemed essential for economic growth, productivity and efficiency (Yunis et al., 2018). Consequently, continuous attention has been provided to the role of ICT in business contexts by academics, and several empirical studies have been conducted in this field. A large number of published articles have also paid close attention to the implementation of

technological developments. This may explain why ICT adoption in the Information Systems (IS) is a commonly debated research stream (Niebel, 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017).

From a business perspective, in developing and developed countries, large and small businesses will quickly become dominant rivals by using ICT to build a competitive edge and become global leaders (Mustafa, 2015; Rahayu and Day, 2017). Organisations can use ICT as a strategy to enhance strategic planning, future research, and business forecasting for both process effectiveness and productivity (Agwu and Murray, 2015; Keller and Von der Gracht, 2014). Adopting ICT influences an organisation's flexibility, where firms whose executives support ICT are more likely to do well on the market and demonstrate distinction in goods or services (Tarute and Gatautis, 2014).

Tarutė and Gatautis (2014) assert that many ICTs have made significant contributions in numerous industry fields such as marketing, networking, communication, and resource planning. Digital technology assists organisations in meeting internal and external business demands (Kroh et al., 2018); to achieve business growth (Foroudi et al., 2017). However, It should be remembered that much of the academic literature discussing ICT adoption in institutions focus primarily on large businesses (Abed, 2020; AlBar and Hoque, 2019; Eze, and Chinedu-Eze, 2018) and in the sense of small companies, little focus has been given to the understanding of ICT implementation. (Busaidi et al., 2019; Sin et al., 2016). This is further addressed in the next section by discussing the ICTs adoption in SMEs.

2.6. Adoption of ICTs in SMEs:

Different scientists have concluded that large corporations gain economic growth because they generate innovation more frequently than smaller businesses (Harness et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2015), Although some have suggested that SMEs play a more critical role than their larger counterparts in economic growth (Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018). Big enterprises have many advantages over small businesses, including more profound specialized expertise, applied science skills, ability to exploit economies of scale, access to cheaper and more powerful tools for funding and improved risk management (Harness et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018). The advantages that SMEs have over larger organizations are inherent in their size. Small and medium-sized enterprises have more stability, less bureaucracy, less corporate hierarchic management, improved coordination and more excellent market proximity in an organisational context; SME leaders prefer to discover and more likely to adopt new and creative ideas (Harness et al., 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018). The size, innovativeness and flexibility of small and medium-sized

enterprises make leaders of SMEs more likely to respond to markets conditions than large enterprises (Napitupulu et al., 2018; Tob-Ogu et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015). A single person, a business owner/manager, can take operational and strategic decisions in SMEs (Napitupulu et al., 2018).

Hence, the perception, experience and IT capabilities of the owners and managers, therefore, act as drivers of ICT consideration and implementation. It is mainly a person's role in small and medium-sized businesses to recognise ICT goals and objectives and determine their companies' capacity for ICT (Rahayu and Day, 2015). The launch of ICT tools and the rapid growth in this field is becoming ever more critical due to the features mentioned above of SMEs (Abed, 2020). These tools have been an essential component in global competition; SMEs recognizes the vital importance of ICT to their performance. The fast introduction of emerging technology in small and medium-sized companies will help them grow and perform innovatively (Yunis et al., 2017; Zafar and Mustafa, 2017).

The role and significance of ICT in SMEs is attributed to several researchers (Consoli, 2012) and emphasizes that failure to implement ICTs has a detrimental effect on foreign market access (Ongori and Migiro, 2010). SMEs are engaged in many technological inventions (Subrahmanya et al., 2018). Therefore, the SME environment has introduced several ICTs app from simple to more sophisticated and advanced IT capabilities. In this regard, several studies have investigated the adoption of different ICTs software in recent years. For instance, adoption of e-commerce applications in SMEs (Rahayu and Day, 2015), Beier and Wagner (2016) investigated the adoption of SM app in SMEs. Similarly, Abed (2020) investigated the social commerce applications in Saudi Arabian SMEs. In addition, Lubua and Pretorius (2018) carried research in Tanzania to identify the demographic factors to adopting social commerce applications, and barriers to adopting M-commerce in SMEs in the UK were explored by (Rana et al., 2019).

In recent research, Ramayah et al. (2019) have also strived to explore the determinants of business intelligence systems adoption among SMEs and Ndiege (2019) investigated the effect of SM technology in SMEs in Kenya. This reflects the curiosity in learning the usage and implementation in a specific country context. Since new information technology is being developed and given access, small and medium-sized businesses are also examined for adoption and usage. The amount of literature on a particular technology is initially small, but the number of these studies is growing over time. The same case applies to social commerce that this study effort is concentrated, and additional information on the research in the area will be given in the next section. However, it is essential to understand the significance and the benefits of ICT implementation for small and medium-sized businesses before moving forward.

2.6.1. Significance and Potential Benefits of Adoption of ICTs in SMEs

Serdyukov (2017) argues that innovation plays an essential role in industry and the nation's economic prosperity and the strategic advantage of a corporation. By introducing new ideas, techniques, goods or services, or improving the usefulness of a product or service, creative entrepreneurs achieve the last ever advantage, hence increasing profitability (Franco & Mario, 2017).

In developed and developing countries, the SME sector plays a significant role in economic growth, poverty reduction, and job creation. Also, the SME sector primarily beats the national economies' average growth in many countries and dramatically contributes to job generation. (Esselaar et al., 2006; Higon, 2011). The same progressive development can be seen about harnessing innovations (including ICT), with businesses moving from easy to permissible technology (Dahlman et al., 2016). A particular role or function is more likely to be needed as an organisation/company increases/expands. In addition, the use of technology and some infrastructures, professional ICT workers, etc., are closely connected and will determine the potential beneficial effect of ICT. Suppose such infrastructures, qualified ICT workers and budgets are in place to invest in ICT. In that case, the private sector will have a positive impact – ICT tools (PCs, mobiles, internet, etc.) have four significant contributions to companies (Manochehri et al., 2012):

- More visibility to business enterprises;
- Provide more information to small firms;
- Allow enterprises to overcome traditional trade barriers;
- Facilitate financial transactions

Researchers have found that digitalization and the implementation of ICT have a growing impact on SMEs' market efficiency and success. In addition, ICT is actively used by SMEs because these innovations help them compete with more prominent firms. (AlBar and Hoque, 2019). SMEs have used ICTs as a competitive tool to enter a larger market and compete with big corporations. The latest analysis indicates that web-based intranet systems in small companies are being used to handle HR, including corporate communications and staff engagement. (Chertchom et al., 2019).

ICT increases competitiveness and market share for businesses and offers a wide variety of advantages to companies, such as helping to introduce new products and services, growing customer awareness, adapting more successfully to market trends and innovating to the enhanced firm-level performance (Gërguri-Rashiti et al., 2017). If ICT is not creative or corporate structures and operating processes are

not strengthened or modified, the ICT cannot boost firm efficiency or maintain a competitive advantage (Cardona et al., 2013). Innovation ICT encompasses all the mechanisms developed to create a new invention, concept or commodity, identified by social, political, and ecological background (Misuraca et al., 2017).

Despite the vital aspect found by using various ICT resources for SMEs and their usefulness and significance, studies indicate a hesitation to implement and eventual sluggish adoption in the small business community (Carcary et al., 2014). This may be mainly linked to several adoption difficulties for small businesses, and the following segment will be explored in more depth.

2.6.2. ICTs Adoption challenges for SMEs:

Different analyses of S-commerce challenges in developed economies have shown that the problems faced by many companies differentiate ultimately from those faced by developing economies. In emerging economies, ICT and SC organisations face particular specific challenges that are more prominent than developed economies (Gibreel et al., 2018). Therefore, emerging economies face many barriers that seriously hamper their social commerce market (Rao-Nicholson et al., 2017). It has also been identified that e-commerce, with its positive effect on trade, investment, company transactions and consumer penetration, will theoretically bring many unparalleled opportunities through modern technical developments (Adam et al., 2016). The outcomes of various research, which pursued these advantages, in both developed and developing countries were, in general, disappointing. Ndiege (2019) noted that most SMEs seemed to have struggled to take advantage of SC by extending access to their markets, improving coverage, improving consumer and supplier relationships, reducing their expense or improving their effectiveness.

Researchers identified many barriers and obstacles to ICTs and, in addition, SC adoption by SMEs, those in the developing countries in particular. These barriers may be categorized broadly as internal and external. Internal challenges occur within the enterprise and can be overcome when they influence the organisation's climate. Usually, these cover organisational culture, scarcity of capital, organisational behaviours and training of employees.

The difficulties faced by SMEs impede their access to many technologies. External challenges of the company include lack of telephone equipment, low internet access, lack of fixed call lines, and inadequate ISP networks beyond the organisation's immediate control. A recent study by Rahayu and Day (2017) further illustrates that the heavy reliance on e-mail services, lack of government support,

lack of ICT experts and lack of financing are all challenges to low adoption by SMEs in Indonesia – a developing economy. SMEs are not organized or structured businesses (White et al., 2014). They are very heterogeneous and differ significantly according to size, industry, age, structure and location.

Mohammadi (2015) also argued that Economic and cultural uncertainty and poor knowledge of information technology impede the adoption of e-commerce in the emerging economy of Iran. Alyoubi (2015) studied SMEs in emerging countries with many challenges and difficulties in implementing e-commerce technologies, which is in line with the results of other surveys.

In Thailand, Small business managers' attitudes and social media marketing compatibility and user satisfaction are likely to be some of the factors which prevent small companies from e-marketing (Kanchanatane et al., 2014). A study in South Africa by Ndlodo and Agboh (2015) found that factors that could discourage the use of ICTs tools for SMEs include the lack of awareness about the platform's functionality, technological incompatibility with the target group, the absence of social media technology preparation for stakeholders, the lack of market orientation and the lack of social media understanding is amongst other factors.

Other problems can be associated with limited ICT application, including a shortage of ICT resources and ICT expertise. Rahayu and Day (2017) argue that SMEs are not sufficiently prepared to incorporate ICT instruments. There is substantial evidence of a lack of IT qualifications and the associated in-house experience. SMEs' awareness of the possible value of ICT for their businesses seems to be directly affected by this lack of expertise. In other words, while the policy makers are the most often interested in IT investment (Abdullah et al., 2012), same as is in the case with big companies, they are not always IT specialist. SMEs leaders (owners/managers) appear to lack the qualifications and experience needed to evaluate the opportunity that ICTs offer (Kanchanatane et al., 2014). SME owners/administrators often tend to carry out minimal systematic training for administrative and company decisions (Bharati and Chaudhury, 2015) and lack appropriate ICTs solutions (Solangi et al., 2019). This may explain why small and medium-sized companies frequently receive outside assistance to address the ICT capabilities (Carcary et al., 2014). However, it is worth noting that SMEs can be supported by non-professionals and can lead to weak ICTs strategies and conceal their ICTs investment (Vanhaverbeke, 2012). It could clarify why few SMEs have similar ICT appearances despite their lack of consistent strategic goals and inadequate internal capability (Ganguly et al., 2019).

Furthermore, Haynes et al. (2015) assert ICTs adoption literature in SMEs established additional restrictions that prohibit the adoption of numerous types of ICT, together with their lack of importance to the essence of corporate activities (e.g., SMEs in the building sector frequently believe that ICTs has no particular effect on their enterprise (Haynes et al., 2015)) and lack of legal framework (Ongori and Migiro, 2010). In addition, more challenges including lack of knowledge about the available technology, shortage of time, bad ICTs experience and lack of support from management (Solangi et al., 2019). Another common barrier to ICT adoption for SMEs is the lack of security (Tan and Eze, 2012). Furthermore, it is noticeable that some contextual issues may be linked to the adoption of new technologies. For example, SMEs in developing countries face other challenges that hinder their use of ICT tools. Small and medium-sized businesses in developing countries have a severe shortage of capital, comparatively uncertain and costly infrastructure and a lack of ICTs expertise (Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013). The financial limitations are also expressed in ICT investment budgets, while most SMEs in emerging countries do not have a dedicated amount to invest in ICTs (Kannabiran and Dharmalingam, 2012). It was also revealed that the risk and security concerns related to ICT adoption cause difficulties for most SMEs in developing countries (Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013; Solangi et al., 2019). Consequently, the sensitivity and benefits of ICT adoption in SMEs in developing countries remain at risk (Manochehri et al., 2012).

Other studies, such as Zafar and Mustaf (2017) and Hassan et al. (2018), have found that SMEs in emerging countries lag behind developed nations regarding ICTs adoption and struggle to stay up with the latest technology. Lubua and Pretorius (2018) determined that ICTs adoption amongst SMEs in Tanzania falls stays behind expectations. As important as, Al-Gharbi and Ashrafi (2010) have reported that cultural difference can be an additional barrier to slow ICTs embracing in non-developed countries.

The findings of (Shafique et al., 2015) indicate that one-third of the private sector companies polled in Pakistan has not taken up the internet in their enterprises since they see face-to-face client contact as the ideal way to do business. To the highlighted facts, it can be proposed that ICT adoptions in SMEs in developing countries are relatively weaker and slow paralleled to developed countries. Regardless of the difficulties, other analysts claim that, because of the features of SMEs, small companies have greater chances to implement emerging technology than their big competitors. Moreover, the development and creation of cost-effective technology could help small and medium-size companies to resolve some of their resources (Karimi and Naghibi, 2015).

2.6.3. Characteristics of Technology in SMEs:

ICTs were classified into three classes: general use of ICTs, communication-integrating ICTs and market-oriented ICT (Bayo-Moriones et al., 2013). General ICT use includes the internet, computer and other basic ICTs tools such as fax machines, scanners, smart phones and more. Although e-mail, intranet, and extranet provide communications-integrated ICTs, e-commerce, websites, and social media apps are market-oriented ICTs. This research concentrates primarily on the second and third groups as they are most commonly utilized in the small and medium-scale sector and their role and effect on improving marketing and corporate efficiency. The research takes e-mail, SNSs and social media as significant variables from these two classes of ICTs. Electronic mailing, often known as e-mail, is essential for fast, affordable, accessible, and easily replicated business communication. An email will help organisations tremendously because it offers a reliable and convenient means to exchange electronic data. Email notifications can include photos, videos, sounds, and text customized to specific consumer categories. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2008; Yusuf, 2013). An email has contributed to the evolution and had a significant influence on businesses. It is used for internal contact with other employees and external communication with customers. In the early sixties, the invention and use of e-mail in correspondence was made as messages could only be delivered to users of the very same computer. Whittaker and Sidner (1996) illustrate that In the 70s, the new e-mail started to use @ sign for the e-mail user names as computers began operating in networks. After the military and educational institutes, Companies began to use email in their businesses. Due to its flexibility, speed and meagre cost, it has been quickly adopted. It has become ideal for companies with foreign subsidiaries and is a cost-effective way to coordinate, verify the transactions and validate shipments. The email is thus nearly 40 times more effective in helping companies to meet and attract new customers. E-mail is an effective ICTs tool for small and medium companies since it has several benefits, including increased promotion of goods & services, good customer relations, enhanced connectivity both internally and externally, and the attraction of new and future customers.

SNSs have been a prominent part of our everyday lives, with annual increases in people's number of people for connecting and exchanging knowledge (Somerville and Brady, 2019). More than 3.6 billion users used social media worldwide in 2020, and about 4.41 billion predicted to rise in 2025 (Tankovska, 2021). Tankovska (2021) further identified in a survey that Facebook has 2.7 billion users, LinkedIn has 760 million users, Twitter has 152 million users, WhatsApp has 2 billion users, and YouTube has 1.5 billion users, 81% of all SMEs worldwide use a social networking site (Brandwatch, 2018). The literature provides a series of social media definitions, and this is because various

individuals and scholars perceive and use the word social media in a different manner. Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) revealed that Social media is a series of Web apps built on the conceptual and technological basis of web 2.0 that enable user-generated content to be established and exchanged. According to Ahmad et al. (2018), this definition of social media is most comprehensive.

The social network offers companies with an already connected Internet broad possibilities to connect to customers conveniently and cost-effectively (McCann & Barlow, 2015). The argument was made to change and control customers' actions with businesses, goods and brands more relevant (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Many scholars have recognized that SM has brought a revolution in new ways for customers to engage, contribute, interact, creation of content and sharing information with other users through new approaches of communication, there is many instead of the conventional one-to-many (Ahmad et al., 2018; McCann & Barlow, 2015).

SNSs can be much more helpful for SMEs as they have restricted financial and technological resources to sell the good and service (Jones et al., 2015). It was claimed that the perceived impact on businesses of SM must not be unnoticed as literature demonstrates, the diverse ways of digitalization, including social media, have a positive effect on SME development, performance and competitiveness (Hassan et al., 2018). Digital marketing and social media will allow SMEs to attract new and will target current customers quickly and cost-effectively and assist internal and external communication (Ahmad et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2015; Taiminen & Karjaluoto, 2015). Therefore, if they want to remain competitive and growing, SMEs must implement and adopt platforms such as social commerce (Taiminen & Karjaluoto, 2015). However, once social commerce is adopted successfully in businesses, SMEs should have a specific strategy for using it and what to use it for (McCann & Barlow, 2015).

The advantages of the internet, including low prices, speed and comprehensive connectivity, provide good opportunities for the global spread of social commerce, bring together countries into a digital networked economy. The online market growth transformed the traditional way of conducting business, particularly the small to medium-sized companies. The analysis indicates that the rapid developments in technology through the internet have given SMEs substantial opportunities to invest in emerging technologies. ICTs development through these resources, such as Web 2.0 technologies, have created enormous opportunities for SMEs to take. The new types of Internet applications can change business operations and impact companies in many ways. From an SME perspective, these apps and platforms have opened the new way to future ICT opportunities for small companies, such as customer relationship improvements and increased revenue. Furthermore, the advantages of ICTs adoption are mentioned above.

2.7. Assessment of Information Technology and Communication (ICT) in Pakistan

Pakistan is currently well behind compared with other countries in the region, such as India, Sri Lanka, China, Turkey, concerning ICTs and business volume. A historical comparison to the previous century is that ICTs are a means for growth or progressive social reforms. In five decades, after the end of world war, western powers have agreed to extend their development determinations in developing countries (Flora, 1986). Currently, technology organisations are actively engaged to spread internet services in developing countries.

The ICTs tools were considered as a significant resource in different sectors, such as corporations, education, telecommunication, agriculture, hospitality and tourism in developing countries, including Pakistan. ICTs tools ensure fair representation and growth of educational, economic, social and security sectors and provide digital platforms to several associations, government, agencies, businesses, non-profit organisations to facilitate the spreading of information, knowledge, ideas at the international level. The technology revolution profoundly influenced the world's working and private society, particularly in developing countries (Avgerou and Walsham, 2017).

Today, the Internet is a massive ICT network consisting of millions of computers that allow ongoing communication worldwide in Pakistan. It could only be achieved from the mid-1990s, and back then, there were minimal computer sales. The Pentium 1 with Windows 95 was seen as a luxury for the wealthy and poor populations in the world. In 1993, in the form of USENET and Imran-Net newsgroups, the Internet was launched. With the help of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the first dial-up connection was formally established in the capital Islamabad, the funded project called the Sustainable Development Networking Program (SDNPK). The SDNPK's primary role was to provide the general public with computer e-mail services and facilitate the government's educational project, sustainable growth, NGOs in Lahore, Karachi and Islamabad. The number of subscribers from outside cities grew as the rates of e-mail messages in conjunction with telephone calls became more affordable than those from other foreign networks such as faxes and dial-ups. This project was financed by the UNDP and expanded to other cities such as Karachi, Lahore and Peshawar for many years, where nodes have been built. However, after several internet service providers (ISPs) arrived in 1995, the idea lost its appeal (ISPAK, 2014). In Between 1995 and 1998, Leading business enterprises like Digicom, PAKNET and Comsats have introduced Internet services for a variety of enterprises in three Pakistani cities and to the general public (Karachi, Lahore and Islamabad) with an

available speed of 14.4kbps to 64kbps at a dial-up price of PKR 100 per hour (ISPAK, 2014). In 1999, the government formally started to give licences to the country's commercial internet service providers (ISPs). By mid-1999, these licenses were given to 100 ISPs, with fifty running on broadband Internet service for several businesses and home users in Pakistan's different cities. In 2002, Micronet Broadband launched the first broadband DSL internet in three cities in Pakistan: Karachi, Lahore and Islamabad, with better cables, better services, and customers simultaneously using the telephone and internet without telephone lines (Dawn, 2010). The first broadband link in Pakistan was obtained later in 2002. In Pakistan, the projected amount of 25 broadband subscribers was 643,892 for 2009 and was expected to hit 1213,000 by 2012 (Pakistan Telecommunications Authority (PTA), 2011). However, Pakistan can still provide high-quality broadband service via various platforms and does not have the appropriate telecommunication infrastructure (Manzoor, 2013). Today, many well-known service providers, such as NayaTel, Pakistan Telecommunications Limited (PTCL), Wateen, Witribe, LINKdotNET, Qubee and Comsats Internet Networks, provide many customers in the country high-speed DSL services up to PKR 6,500 a month at speeds of 100Mb/h. (PTCL, 2018; Saleem, 2015).

The government of Pakistan is currently focused on delivering quality ICT services, the growth of ICTs, and the country's sustainable regulatory framework. In 2018–19, the government agreed to invest PKR 7 billion on development and non-development projects related to ICTs (Ministry of Finance, 2018). However, the Ministry of Science and Technology informed the cabinet committee and the secretary that the current lack of human resources (HR) would make it difficult for them to use the budget effectively to its total capacity (PTA, 2018). Thus, Pakistan has been in the early stages of ICT growth, and the administration has tried to construct a diverse and concrete approach to modernizing citizens' lives (Ud Din et al., 2017). In this regard, the Government and PTA have taken a range of steps to support ICT programs and promote access to most of the nation. Acts include introducing 5G regulations, increasing speed measures on broadband, authorising third-party service providers to promote economic development, device identity registration blocking scheme, No Objection Certificate Online Smartphone Import Platform and online interactive distance learning initiatives, Pakistan 2020 e-vision (Ahmed et al., 2013). In regards to promoting the ICT industry, the GoP declared for the first time that its Digital Strategy (2017) aimed at Pakistan being a strategic facilitator for the development of a knowledge-based economy and socio-economic growth in accelerated digital ecosystems.

In fiscal years 2016, the teledensity rate rose by 12,1% to 70,4%. The major factor was the rise in the number of mobile phone subscribers. The figure for broadband subscribers has crossed 40 million in

August 2018, increasing over 32% from 2015 to 2018 relative to previous years (IWS, 2018). Although, many recent studies (Haider et al., 2015; Ud Din et al., 2017) have indicated Pakistan is still in its early stage of development in ICT-related projects. The latest IWS statistics show (2018) that Pakistan is well behind in Asia regarding internet use relative to other developing and developed countries, at only 2.2%. On the other hand, The number of internet users in Pakistan in the past 18 years had increased significantly, and by the year 2000, it stood at 133,900, but it expanded to 12,000,000 after six years, in 2006. By 2009, Pakistan had 18,500,000 Internet users, which rose to 34,342,400 in 2016. There were 44,608,065 Internet users registered in 2018 (Internet World Stats, 2019). The explanation behind Pakistan's tremendous growth is the appearance of mobile devices and social media; since there are 44.61 million active Internet users in Pakistan, according to the survey, of which 43.40 million mobile internet users are active. The study also reveals that 37 million frequent users use social media, of which 36 million are mobile social network users. (We Are Social, 2019). The new demographic figures in Pakistan show that the country's average number of internet users is much smaller than in the neighbouring countries. For the government and its authorities, the high rate of non-users is worrying. While the growth is very high in the region compared to previous years, the internet penetration rate remains small (22.2%) than other countries in the Asian region, which alarms commercial institutions that provide technology services for many business and home users. This internet penetration rate represents ICT infrastructural facilities, both for individual consumers and the business sector, on a general level.

2.8. Social Media Applications (SMAs):

The internet became well-known in the late 1990s; websites started to appear to enable individuals to generate and upload content. At the end of the 2000s, social media applications had been generally embraced, and some services had attracted enormous numbers of users. For example, Archambault and Grudin (2012) carried research in Microsoft to study Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter and how they are found helpful in corporate interaction and information collection. Growth in SMAs and acceptance was not uniform, with differences based on gender, age and level. The entrepreneur started realizing the value of SMAs for work. Wamba and Carter (2016) found that Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter reportedly increased over the year. Leftheriotis and Giannakos (2014) investigated if workers use SMAs for work purposes, what are the principles for SMA use and if it is connected to their performance? Results suggest that workers use them widely regardless of their age in SMAs for work purposes.

SMA is defined as “the interaction among people which allows them to share, create and exchange information in virtual communities with less effort and time” (Cohen, 2011). SMA emphasise engagement, networking, communication and interaction with online technology (Muqadas et al., 2016). However, The content of SMA needs to be updated frequently to engage users in social media events such as discussions, sharing and ongoing collaboration (Kaplan and Haelein, 2010). SMA grew exponentially across the world.

SMA have several features that make them an appropriate alternative to do the job of small and medium-sized companies (SMEs). These features are not limited to, but include (Cohen, 2011):

- a wide range of content formats (e.g. text, image, video, etc.) and allow combining more than one content;
- provides communication to take place in real-time and to cross one or more applications through social sharing, email and feeds;
- involve different levels of interactions by participants who can create and comment on social media networks; and
- Offer one-to-one, one-to-many and many-to-many communications.

Therefore, SMA give businesses massive opportunities and advantages to boost their market efficiency (Leftheriotis and Giannakos, 2014). For instance, they are a perfect way for firms to increase their business exposure at a much lower expense than conventional marketing. It will help businesses attract more consumers, appreciate and desire their needs, and improve associations with them (Wiegand, 2014). Sharing contents displayed on SMA are more authentic, trustworthy and credible than those shown on other channels (He et al., 2017).

2.9. Background of Social Commerce:

The Internet is a vital networking medium and information source and perhaps the most commonly used tool of all time. Today’s digital era, technology, and globally used social networking sites have opened the door to social commerce. This sort of commerce is based mainly on using the most modern ICT technologies and development systems to extend the world’s market from East to West and around the globe.

2.9.1. What is Social Commerce?

Social commerce includes many fields from psychology, marketing and computer sciences to sociology and psychology. Based on the literature, numerous definitions of SC are presented in table 2.2.

Although there is no standard definition of SC, this study will consider Abed's (2018) definition. Abed (2018) illustrates that "it refers to the distribution of e-commerce activities in the social media environment, mostly by using Web 2.0 software and social networks". Some scholars specifically argued that without knowing the two linked concepts of Web 2.0 and User Generated Content (UGC), the concept of social commerce could not be grasped.

There is no consensus on the elements of Web 2.0. The opportunities for business value creation have been created by the advent of Web 2.0 technology that leads to the popularity of social media (Li et al., 2018). The adoption of Web 2.0 is called Business 2.0 within organisations (Mathaba et al., 2017). Many retailers noticed the shift into social and community features of some big web companies such as Yahoo, eBay, Amazon and Google. They noted that this generated demand and desire for consumers. Since the internet has become one of the primary mediators to gain knowledge and product-related information, people also took advantage of using this info to make better decisions in every aspect of life. For a positive effect on businesses, Web 2.0 tools have passed into organisations. Organisations are mainly involved in using Web 2.0 activities in two locations (Mathaba et al., 2017). These are 1) competence and development progression within the organisation and 2) from the organisation to customers to enhance sales, revenue and customer loyalty. Web 2.0 encouraging online communities to connect socially by creating user profiles, generate content in different forms (texts, photos, blogs, and videos) and making it possible for the users to tag other users/pages, comment, like/dislike and revise the content.

SC provides social networking e-commerce functionality so that users may buy goods and services from areas to which they already are linked (Li et al., 2013). Specifically, consumer shopping behaviours have changed, and a novel type of e-commerce, called "social commerce," is emerging (Sun et al., 2016). The tremendous increase in e-commerce and the popularity of online social networks significantly influence the world economy. Social commerce includes comments and reviews, tags, and user profiles, using social network capabilities branded as "user-generated content" to encourage customers to share their purchase experience with other users. Customers can seek ways of leveraging other people's expertise or influence the purchasing behaviour of other shoppers, not only that of

passive information takers (Pagani & Mirab, 2012). Social commerce specifically altered the online buying environment from a business to a user-oriented one (Busalim, 2016).

In comparison with online marketplaces containing company information traditionally focused on products, social commerce focuses on socially and consumer-driven online markets where social networking sites encourage their users to make social links with peers (Shadkam & O'Hara, 2013). Since social networking users are friends or indirect acquaintances, their sharing of information appears relatively honest compared to recommendations or evaluations supplied by merchants on shopping platforms. Therefore, shoppers prefer information offered on social network purchasing platforms (Bai et al., 2015).

Social commerce is the integration of social media in e-commerce platform (Abed, 2018). People are using social commerce components (SCCs) and social technology to perform social interaction with peers in social networking sites (SNSs), which creates the social climate with the emergence of online social support. A recent study by (Yadav et al., 2013) defined SC as the “exchange-related activities that occur in, or are influenced by, an individual’s social network in computer-mediated social environments, where the activities correspond to the need recognition, pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase stages of focal exchange”. Social networking sites and social media are powerful tools of social commerce, which enable individuals to be creative on the Internet. These powerful tools of social media differentiate e-commerce from social commerce.

Since social commerce-enabled its online users to operate it via mobile devices, business models have been transformed in banking, retailing, fashion and designing, transportation and hospitality. On the one hand, scholars consider social commerce the best marketing tool (Tuten & Solomon, 2017). On the other hand, it also empowers its users to evaluate the product, discover information, innovate, collaborates, and communicate with their peers. Online platforms and social media technologies are the most potent tools where users share information and individual experiences of others in insight, knowledge, music, and photograph (Tuten & Solomon, 2017). Social networking sites and their applications play a pivotal role in the growth of social media (Liang & Turban, 2011). Users and members can seek information, activities, experience, and common interest from online communities of SNSs (Shin, 2010). Yadav et al. (2013) illustrate that since online social platforms empower consumers to communicate and negotiate with each other, it also has enhanced the social commerce purchase intention. Social media technologies are the most vital tools and allow consumers to share information and individual experiences on online social platforms such as forum and communities, reviews and ratings, recommendations, and referrals. Such forums and communities, ratings and

reviews, recommendations and referrals are considered three primary social commerce constructs (Hajli, 2015; Hajli and Sims, 2015).

Hajli (2015) revealed that many companies such as Channel, H&M, Dell, Selfridge, and other brands use social commerce sites. He further identified that such organisations also ask their consumers to like their Facebook page and leave an online comment about the product and service they got. Kim & Park (2013) elaborates from a customer's perspective that a word from the self-governing user is more credible and convenient for purchasing decision. Consumer joins online communities, forums to seek the information or experience of others for the desired product. Alternatively, they may enter the popular SNSs such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and like the pages of chosen firms for the review and feedback of their products. Social recommendations assist others user in making choices among various brands and products (Shadkam & O'Hara, 2013).

In social commerce, customers choose to participate in online forums and social media technologies to learn about the desired product (Huang & Benyoucef, 2015). In this era, customers have more access to social knowledge and other's opinions that support them to make a better and informed online purchase decision. Social media users can freely exchange information about their satisfaction and dissatisfaction with product and service. Businesses are also getting the benefit when their customers leave feedback.

Social commerce is computer-mediated social environments where sustained social interactions exist among community members. In this regard, social commerce creates an environment where firms can harness their brand to deliver incremental value (Hajli et al., 2017) and turn consumers into brand ambassadors by leveraging collective, co-creation processes with other consumers (Cayla & Arnould, 2008). In such environments, consumers have empowered influence brands through SNSs and online communities. Thus, significant brand values are facilitated by online consumer activities (Naylor et al., 2012). Social commerce influences behaviour and brand intentions through social interactions and serves as a business strategy to increase sales and brand values (Tajvidi et al., 2018). However, the proliferation of information technologies (ITs) and online platforms (or channels) have stimulated impulsive purchasing behaviour by increasing consumers' access to products and services (Chen et al., 2016). Advance technology in our lives and the dispersion of social media has changed the way people exchange information, build a relationship, including between companies and their customers (Han et al., 2016).

In line with Vargo & Lusch (2016), recent changes to the core areas for service-dominant logic, integration of resources (i.e. knowledge and information) into social business, rather than a dynamical creation between customers and companies in e-commerce platforms, are carried out by "multiple actors" (i.e. institutions, persons and organisations) (Liang & Turban, 2011). The interchange of operating resources (i.e. non-physical information, ideas, and expertise) between numerous players outside the market enhances the interaction between buyer and seller of operations (i.e. physical, financial and product).

According to Liebana-Cabanillas and Alonso-Dos-Santos (2017), SC significantly improves conventional trade with various distinguishing features. First and foremost, s-commerce facilitates and fosters the interaction of social media users by exchanging views and buying tips and experiences. Secondly, it allows customers to access and explore a selection of items that cannot be achieved offline. Third, social business leverages better access to technology through various instruments, such as regular mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, etc. It also gives social networking payment facilities.

Since 2005, research on social commerce is being carried out (Baethge et al., 2016), and studies in marketing, e-commerce, and information technology have been discussed. Although previous researches mainly focused on user (consumer) behaviour, social shopping, purchase intention, social networking websites, and social gaming (Doha et al., 2019; Hassan et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2019; and a few focused on social commerce website design and enterprise strategies were also concentrated by few scholars (Hajli et al., 2017; Li, 2019). Furthermore, it was defined that consumer engagement is critical for social commerce success (Chen et al., 2014; Casaló et al., 2020). Additionally, active user participation in social commerce, such as contributing content and building relationships, are critical to social commerce growth

Due to a lack of a priori knowledge on which platforms are regularly utilized in the context, a broad classification of social media platforms is being used in this thesis. It is the first attempt to address social commerce adoption in the present study's research context. To put it another way, it was recommended by Lietsala and Sirkkunen (2008), social media is employed as an umbrella word in this study to encompass various general applications. As a result, the researcher is more interested in examining the adoption of numerous social media platforms than in reviewing a single platform. As

Verheyden and Goeman (2013) point out, this avoids focusing on a single platform with an undetermined "life expectancy."

Huang & Benyoucef	2013	An Internet-based commercial application that leverages Web 2.0 and social media to support user-generated content and social interaction assist consumers in the decision-making and acquisition of products and services within communities and online marketplaces.
Yadav et al.	2013	It refers to the exchange-related activities, which are influenced by or occur in the individual's social network in computer-mediated social environments. These activities correspond to the need recognition, pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase stages of a focal exchange.
Hajli	2014	A new concept that enables customers to have a functional space in cyberspace is referred to as social commerce. It is a development in e-commerce that incorporates the network of buyers and sellers and more commonly found in interactive and social forms of e-commerce
Gatautis & Medziausiene	2014	Social commerce is the deployment of social media tools in e-commerce.
Hajli & Lin	2015	Social commerce has been evolved through e-commerce and is facilitated by new advances in Web 2.0 technologies.
Liu et al.	2016	Social commerce sites provide social interactions, such as information sharing, networking, and collaboration, to facilitate communications between consumers
Chen et al.	2017	S-commerce facilitates consumers to share and seek product-related information through eWOM and purchase online through SNSs.

Table No. 2.2: Social Commerce Definitions

2.9.2. Advantages of Social Commerce and its use in SMEs:

Individually, SM platforms were created to connect people personally (Schlagwein and Prasarnphanich, 2014). These platforms allow individuals to communicate with each other regardless of their location (Gündüz, 2017). Therefore, the patterns and trends associated with individual users must be addressed before evaluating, extending, and usage at the SME level. The significant growing user of social media platforms offers an essential motivation for large organisation and SMEs to adopt these emerging technologies. Samuel and Ioe (2016) asserted that social networking sites connect millions of user, and their founders may not have expected the far-reaching impact of such platforms. For instance, As of April 2020, Facebook has more than 2.7 billion active users, the most popular social media site (Tankovska, 2021). Twitter, one of the largest and successful microblogging services (Yang et al., 2019), has witnessed substantial growth to surpass 330 million users as of the first quarter of 2019 (Tankovska, 2021). This vast and rising number of users offers businesses the chance to associate with more customers and increase their social media profile of the organisation (Appel, 2020).

Baur (2017) persists that Information created on social media platforms can become the primary source of data for both government and commercial firms. Therefore, for SMEs, social commerce provides a possible way to gain economic advantages targeting a broader market and carry out sales and promotions at lower prices (Schaupp and Bélanger, 2019). SC may increase site traffic and business exposure and improve search engine rankings at a fraction of conventional commercial cost (Schaupp & Bélanger, 2014). Wirthman (2013) illustrates that apart from Sales and marketing, SC also assists in establishing a relationship with individual customers. Although these relationships are very shallow, they can contribute to substantial brand awareness.

Many organisations are now seeking to integrate such marketing in their promotional strategies to improve customer awareness and purchasing behaviour (Lu et al., 2014). Organisations now understand the importance of social platforms as innovative opportunities to communicate with customers in person and engage the customer more effectively (Bilgin, 2018). Research by Lacoste (2016) highlighted the practical usage of social media networking by consumers and companies to improve overall marketing success.

Several studies have explored different advantages of social commerce adoption (see Table 2.3). In general, the findings imply that SMEs profit greatly from the adoption and usage of social media, including The impact of ewom on buying intent (Erkan and Evan, 2018); brand awareness, brand

image and brand loyalty (Bilgin, 2018); social commerce and purchase intention (Lu et al., 2016); selection of tourism destination (Királ'ová and Pavlíčka, 2015); Marketing and Advertising (Hamouda, 2018); effect of social commerce on revenue and stock (Lam et al., 2019), Social commerce and firm performance (Braojos et al., 2019).

No.	Advantages	Reference
1	The influence of eWom on consumers' purchase intention	Erkan, I. and Evans, C., 2018. Social media or shopping websites? The influence of eWOM on consumers' online purchase intentions. <i>Journal of Marketing Communications</i> , 24(6), pp.617-632.
2	The effect of social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty	Bilgin, Y., 2018. The effect of social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty. <i>Business & Management Studies: An International Journal</i> , 6(1), pp.128-148.
3	Impact of social commerce components on purchase intention	Lu, B., Fan, W. and Zhou, M., 2016. Social presence, trust, and social commerce purchase intention: An empirical research. <i>Computers in Human Behavior</i> , 56, pp.225-237.
4	Development of social media strategies in tourism destination	Kiráľ'ová, A. and Pavlíčka, A., 2015. Development of social media strategies in tourism destination. <i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i> , 175, pp.358-366.
5	Social media marketing and advertising	Hamouda, M., 2018. Understanding social media advertising effect on consumers' responses: An empirical investigation of tourism advertising on Facebook. <i>Journal of Enterprise Information Management</i> .
6	The positive impact of social commerce on the revenue and stock	Lam, H.K., Yeung, A.C., Lo, C.K. and Cheng, T.C.E., 2019. Should firms invest in social commerce? An integrative

		perspective. Information & Management, 56(8), p.103164.
7	Social commerce and firm performance	Braojos, J., Benitez, J. and Llorens, J., 2019. How do social commerce-IT capabilities influence firm performance? Theory and empirical evidence. Information & Management, 56(2), pp.155-171.

Table No. 2.3: Advantages of Social Commerce

Marketing and sales promotion remain the most critical uses of SM (Dwivedi et al., 2020). Social commerce goes beyond simply doing business by SM (Zhou et al., 2013). Apart from these potential benefits, social commerce facilitates customer engagement and a platform to attract new customers through word of mouth (Liang & Turban, 2011). In fact, in an analysis of social commerce and the “tragedy of commons,” Kim (2013) concludes that word of mouth is still the most recommended approach for leveraging social commerce. Therefore, SNS reinforce corporate trend to make use of internal and external input that eventually impact the success of their business. Hence social media platforms are considered the most robust tools for organisations to strengthen their links with consumers around the globe and get helpful feedback (Garrido-Moreno, 2018).

Many social media statistics and analysis were performed on a large organisation, which are expected to benefit significantly from their investments. Due to a lack of resources and expertise, SMEs are far behind large organisations regarding social media adoption (Wamba & Carter, 2014).

Bendror (2014) defined four significant challenges for SMEs to adopt social commerce; lack of time, inability to measure value, lack of budget, and difficulty integrating social media with other business activities. As mentioned in section 1.2, many researchers feel that in a particular aspect, SMEs are different from a large organisation, including lack of information system (Cerchione and Esposito, 2017), lack of expert knowledge management (Casidy et al., 2019), and lower level of available resources (Senarathna et al., 2018). Taylor (2019) defined that SMEs are more flexible, innovative and can generate more revenue than large organisations. Furthermore, Gary (2017) illustrates that just a few people must manage the SME rather than specialized top executives.

Social media has been used in all type of organisations, regardless of their size. It can justify the cost consequences of their use. Numerous studies have found that the adoption of social media platforms do not need colossal investment (Abed, 2020; Radcliffe & Bruni, 2018), suggesting that both large and

small enterprises can use these tools. However, based on the available literature, it can be concluded that these platforms are valuable and significant to SMEs (Kumar and Ayedee, 2018).

2.9. Characteristics of Social Commerce:

Social commerce components (SCC) are defined as the constructs derived through social commerce, such as online forums, ratings, communities, reviews, and recommendations (Hajli, 2015). The information obtained by these social commerce platforms or communities can influence customer purchase intentions or behaviour. The study of social commerce constructs is becoming increasingly popular among researchers (Li, 2019; Shanmugam et al., 2016). These constructs are the facet to successful social commerce transactions. Consumers are more inclined to participate in an online deal or service when these social commerce constructs and virtual groups and forums are present. The experience of consumers in an online environment enabled by social media is different to that of offline, as the customers have social interactions with other individuals.

Today, experts suggest that consumers have sociability due to social media and the growth of social platforms (Naeem, 2019). These social platforms are social commerce constructs (Sheikh et al., 2019), which have emerged from Web 2.0 and empowered consumers to generate content and share their experiences. Furthermore, the interaction between the e-vendor and the consumer is personal (Hajli, 2015). Although SCCs serve the same function of facilitating information exchange and developing social support platforms for customers, they differ in their technological capabilities (Shanmugam et al., 2016).

2.9.1. Importance of Social Word of Mouth:

Humans are social beings. The desire to engage with others and the spread of Web 2.0 technology have resulted in the emergence of several social media platforms. As a result, e-commerce has given way to social commerce. Social commerce encourages customer interactions over the internet to sell a product (Hajli, 2015). Consumers are becoming more engaged in this environment, frequently creating as well as consuming information. Potential consumers (those who plan to buy a product shortly) now have access to a wealth of peer-generated details on that product via social media before making a purchasing choice. It is believed that 97percent of consumers read and are affected by consumer reviews (Ahani et al., 2019).

As mentioned above, there are three elements to social commerce: recommendations and referrals, forums and communities, and ratings and reviews (Hajli, 2015). According to several academics, word of mouth on social commerce platforms has the most significant effect on customers. (Hajli, 2014, Yen and Tang, 2019). Word of mouth (WOM) available online is called Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM), and online customer reviews are one form of eWOM (Hajli, 2015). Yen and Tang (2019) illustrates that positive or negative eWOM is directly related to service quality. The positive eWOM can positively affect purchase decision, and negative eWOM can inversely influence a purchase decision (Naeem, 2019). A positive image about a product and service would be created by a positive eWOM, whereas a negative eWOM would generate a negative impression about products and services (Yen and Tang, 2019). As a result, Social WOM can minimize product uncertainty and boost customer confidence (Hajli et al., 2014), which increases purchase intentions. (Hajli, 2014).

Because of the importance of peer-generated content as a sales driver (Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017), SMEs must consider emerging communication technologies as a strategy to achieve competition and sustainability. Since the research area of social media is getting more attention, research on the implications for the resilience and competitiveness of SMEs, particularly in emerging nations, has been relatively low (Tajuddin et al., 2018). To remain sustainable in the global market, SMEs must improve their dialogue and communication channel with their customers (Konstantopoulou et al., 2019). Doh and Hwang (2009) claimed that “the credibility of websites and eWOM message can be damaged in the long run if all of the eWOM messages are positive”. Therefore, a sense of reliability will be created by both positive and negative eWOM. Online consumers will likely exercise their purchase decision based on eWOM (Naeem, 2019).

Social networking sites are considered suitable platforms for e-WOM (Konstantopoulou et al., 2019). Apart from the daily discussion amongst customers, SNSs allow users to create and promote profiles relating to the products and services of brands. Internet-based social media also allows customers to use online platforms to share their experience and feedback with other users (Matute et al., 2016). People give their feedback and share ideas in written text, pictures, videos and emoticons & emojis. Social media websites also facilitate disperse the social WOM among many people (Sohn, 2014); people can share their thoughts by only forwarding posts or sharing them on their page.

Social Networking Site such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter plays an effective bridge between eWOM and consumers, delivering valuable information and opinions about the product. SNSs have a significant impact on the consumer’s decision-making process as a customer can quickly and easily exchange news and views with personal contacts regarding product and services (Kudeshia & Kumar,

2017). Each social networking site have different characterises and audiences, so they engage their audiences & users differently (Tsimonis & Dimitriadis, 2014). Social WOM makes the decision-making process easier for consumers simultaneously helps to improve sales (Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017). Therefore, studies show that social WOM considered the best marketing tool for marketers and an excellent opportunity for SMEs.

Social WOM can also be a valuable tool to get the attention of new customers, not just from the psychological impact they have on the reader but also by increasing local rankings on the internet. In the UK, 97% of consumers go through online reviews before making their purchase decision, and 85% rely on them (Survey, 2018). In Europe and the USA, consumers are constantly seeking online information regarding product and service (Matute et al., 2016). According to recent studies, 75% of US consumers rely upon consumer's feedback before purchasing and deciding (Bazaarvoice, 2018). Scholars also consider eWOM as an essential mean of influential marketing (Erkan & Evans, 2016).

EWOM of information on social media can arise in diverse ways. People like to share posts about the brands and their products with who they agree. In addition, users can interact with brands posts through liking and comment. Lastly, marketers can also share their product and service information through their official page or account on social media. Nowadays, customers share their knowledge, experience and take part in online discussion forums to benefit. Customers rely more on other people's opinion and ideas rather than just have trust in an advert. Therefore, eWOM substantially influences customers' purchase decision-making (Erkan & Evans, 2016). This stimulates investigating how this kind of collaborative capabilities and the sharing features of SM platforms are effective when infused with social wom. These types will boost the quality and adoption of social WOM communication and serve as valuable indicators to enhance reputation and reliability.

A quantity of social WOM plays a significant role in the purchase decision process (Matute et al., 2016). A website holding a considerable volume of reviews about the product may help customers vindicate their purchasing decisions and reduce the supposed risks because others have previously bought the same product and service (Matute et al., 2016).

E-WOM attracts active and passive customers; active customers share their views and experience with other consumers and post reviews on websites, while passive customers seek information and read other consumers' online recommendations without posting any of their own (Khammash & Griffiths, 2011). These recommendations and eWOM drives customer's purchase information about the online store. To control and gain over online reviews, many organisations leave virtual spaces on their

websites (Jorge Matute et al., 2016); consumers publish their ideas, experience and knowledge about product and service. The most recent example of this is the world's two most popular websites are Booking.com (Consumeraffairs, 2018) and Amazon (TheStatisticsPortal, 2018). Amazon and Booking.com include a virtual space on their websites, where users can organise the reviews, comments and rating depending on their usefulness to make a quick decision.

Various researchers in the broader hospitality environment have indicated that attribute performance is a crucial predictor of eWOM behaviours. For example, Kim and Qu (2020) discovered that restaurant service staff could increase customers' positive incentive to leave remarks. Zhang et al. (2014) investigated the association between attribute performance and eWOM in the context of a restaurant. They discovered that attribute performance affects both positive and negative WOM asymmetrically. They found that “food flavour, restaurant atmosphere, and service all influenced favourable consumer eWOM” (Zhang et al., 2014). Yen and Tang (2019) investigated the association between attribute performance and WOM intents in the hotel scenario. The authors discovered that the performance of cleaning workers has a direct influence on WOM intentions, which do not include satisfaction. These studies also provide credence to the notion that consumers rate service experience based on the performance of the qualities, both individually and collectively. However, the performance of each feature affects customers' eWOM behaviours in distinct ways. Because the core and enabling qualities may have various weights on consumer behaviours, it is believed that consumers' eWOM behaviours may vary depending on attribute performance.

2.9.2. Importance of Website Quality:

Social commerce has enhanced the way people shop online. The emergence of Web 2.0 and SNSs facilitated business to create a new model of online shopping. Internet penetration and rapid internet growth into the hospitality industry encourage users to browse and search information on the internet before purchasing decisions. The internet has become the consumer's first choice in the search for information on tourism destinations. Hence, the quality of a website has become an essential tool for marketing product and services (Law et al., 2014).

The development of the internet and technology has changed the way consumers search, collect information and purchase goods. These developments in technology have transformed the business model and shift the focus in businesses' management and marketing strategies, especially in the hospitality industry (Serra-Cantallops, 2020). Hasanov & Khalid (2015) Elaborates that another critical determinant of website feature is website design. Consumers are positively influenced by a well-designed user interface that encourage them to use a website and purchase product and services online (Giao et al., 2020). Hernandez et al. (2009) assert that system, ease of use, and quality of information are significant factors in assessing a website design.

Online shopping platforms face stiff competition with the increased popularity of the internet of things (IoT) and communication technologies (Huang et al., 2017). Therefore, providing quality website and design to the user is an essential element for online businesses. Business organisations should seek to offer social commerce websites of high-quality design (Huang & Benyoucef, 2017). Jung (2014) illustrates that the first thing customer sees on a website is its design and appearance. Cassandra et al. (2017) elaborate that perception of website quality directly impacts customer's use intention. Many factors, including website quality, can affect purchase intention derived by the intention of use (Nilashi et al., 2016); website quality meets their need and features (Afshardost et al., 2013). Ali (2016) explained that if your business offers a better website to support your customer, customer satisfaction will be higher; however, if the website is not user-friendly and has no valuable content, you will lose the trust and image of customers (Rahi et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the customer will never be happy with complex website features (Rahi et al., 2017). A well-built website can also generate curiosity and attraction for customer activities. Therefore, the website used for the hospitality sector must be flexible to operate.

Many researchers have identified that multiple dimensions of website quality can be categorized, such as ease of use, information quality, enjoyment, and service quality (Giao et al., 2020; Akram et al., 2018). Although, it is a critical challenge to meet customers' needs and offer service quality to customers through the website. Rozekhi et al. (2014) advise that those crucial features could be achieved in successful website design through navigation, aesthetic appearance, and an organized & well-managed content display. The appearance and design significantly impact consumers' decision-making process (Chiu et al., 2014).

Consumers assess the product or service based on the provided information and pictures on the website and customer reviews on it when they engage in shopping online (Hsu et al., 2017). An informative webpage assists the customer to evaluate, compare and enables them to find an alternative product. Plus, an informative website also increases customer satisfaction and make the online purchasing process more convenient (Hasanov & Khalid, 2015). Kim & Park (2013) further illustrates that uncertainty in online transactions can be reduced by containing quality information at provided online platforms. A three-dimensional structure was proposed by (Wang et al., 2015) to measure a website quality comprising hotel website usability, hotel website functionality and hotel website security and privacy.

In the online and offline environment, the confidence concept is the concept that has been actively discussed to illustrate the user action (Jung, 2014). Confidence is an element that constructs and maintain a relationship between business and consumer and further leads to commutation relation. Teo & Liu (2007) defined that a successful transaction will develop confidence. Therefore, the website should be user-friendly in an online context and engage its customers to build their confidence & Trust.

Social commerce enables users to interact with each other. Thus, superior design and website quality will maintain a good relationship among users to share information (Cassandra et al., 2017). Sharing information will increase collaboration by which user can share information. Along with the characteristics of the website mentioned above, Information quality is another factor that also affects users' intention of use and satisfaction (Hsu et al., 2016).

A historical analysis of the actual e-commerce website conducted by (Curty & Zhang, 2013) defined that website's technical features have reshaped the companies' business and marketing strategies. Specifically, relational features strengthened customer and merchant relationships (Wanga & Yu, 2017). Mohammadi and Abrizah (2015) defined that using a website is also a good resource for using comparative advantage in the number of activities for the organisation. Organisations use their established website to share knowledge, maintain business relationships, engage their customers, and conduct business transactions across telecommunication networks.

After the need recognition phase, the consumer falls into the desired product's collection and search information phase. The website is the first contact point between consumers and businesses to collect information. (Zhang et al., 2014) illustrates that a stronger sense of identity develops with the website when the consumer perceives online information. Accurate online information enhances consumers'

perception of a product or service and reduces relational distances between consumers and websites (Zhang et al., 2018). Thus, during the product screening, website quality could reduce the consumer's cognitive effort. High-quality customer service and a user-friendly interface website reduces consumers' information search cost and increases decision-making quality (Zhang et al., 2018).

Loureiro (2015) illustrates that intrinsic product cues, web elements, and web atmospheric have significant influence on satisfaction and online behaviour. Product characteristics could be intrinsic product cues, such as the laptop's specification, flavour for a coffee or engine capacity for a truck/car. Richard & Laroche (2010) demonstrate that web atmospherics plays a significant role in developing and creating positive attitudes towards the website and the advertised product. For instance, design, colour, scents are retail atmospheric and essential for the retailer's success. In online marketing, empirical research has been done on website quality by (Aladwani, 2006). The first attempt to measure apparel website quality was proposed by (Kim & Stoel, 2004). They have considered five dimensions to measure apparel website quality: web appearance (display & visual quality, friendly or unchallenging navigation of website), entertainment (innovativeness of website), information fit to task (provide adequate information), transaction capability (well-supportive website to business functions), the response time (website loading time). Moreover, (Kim & Stoel, 2004) found that only three dimensions, informational content, transaction capability and response time, are more effective predictors to satisfy retail consumers than entertainment or web visual.

Another study indicates that visual design, website content, website design, navigation, and personalization positively influence retail consumer satisfaction and loyalty (Pandey & Chawla, 2016). Emerging of these dimensions is also essential to loyal consumers (Fileri & McLeay, 2014). We might look at different dimensions to measure website quality in the tourism context. For instance; functionality and usability (Inversini & Schegg, 2016), service quality, information quality & system quality (Wen, 2012), aesthetic formality and aesthetic appeal (Wang et al., 2010), characteristic of website design and information quality (Tang et al., 2012). Ease of use and design-visual request, information, content, interactive features are four essential components considered by (Loureiro, 2015) in establishing a perception of the island's website quality.

Past studies and research conceptualize website quality as a multidimensional construct, but there is a consensus that it has several components. There are several website quality components with different names, and they may vary from context to context. Therefore, there is no standard procedure, method

or technique to evaluate a website quality (M.C.Loureiro et al., 2018). Furthermore, M.C.Loureiro et al. (2018) illustrate that there are no standard website attributes or features to evaluate website quality.

For successful SC adoption in an organisation, a successful e-payment method needs to be implemented. Since people are reluctant to pay online due to a lack of security and trust on the organisation, about 95% of customers pay cash on delivery (COD) (Khaskheli, A. and Jun, 2016). This is not the most efficient and most accessible form of payment. Numerous payment options encourage more online shopping, as the consumer feels relax (Zhang, 2020). On the other hand, in developed countries (UK, USA, Canada, Germany, Australia, France, etc.), different options available for the customer to make payment such as online payment, credit/debit card, COD, etc.

2.9.3. Importance of Social Presence:

To analyse people's attitude towards different communication media, scholars defined the term Social Presence. The theory about social presence dates back to the fill-in form claiming Short, William, and Christie in the 1970s. The author (Short et al., 1976) was interested in knowing how media influences and how media communicate. Media studies scholar defined social presence to examine people's attitude toward different communication media. Short et al. (1976) were convinced that some media were superior while creating the quality or state of being 'there' than other media. Also, over time people started contributing to online learning environments. Online educators were interested in investigating how media can influence people communication. Those early online educators were more interested in how teachers and students can make up if they cannot see each other and don't know each other.

Lowenthal & Dennen (2017) illustrated other concerns such as communication with each other if separated by space and time zone. They relate those concerns to social presence and identity in online learning. Moore (2013) elaborates that it could be challenging to establish social presence and identity in the online learning environment due to fewer communication channels and transactional distance. Text-based communication and stories to construct our identity can reduce the distance between online media users (Lowenthal & Dennen, 2017).

Advance technology and the presence of consumers in social networking sites have changed the media landscape (Felix et al., 2017). A buzz for firms how to engage with their customers. As stated above,

Social media networks are a kind of social-virtual environments where people share their shopping experiences and communicate with each other (Hajli, 2013). The social presence theory developed by social telecommunications and outlines in individuals' lives engages them to use social media (Osei-Frimpong & McLean, 2018). For instance, social media's user sees practice, behaviour or sensory experience generates some form of intelligence and social acceptance (Tu, 2000). As compared to E-commerce, more peer interaction and collaboration may exist during purchase processes in social commerce. Therefore, in such a type of commerce, a high degree of social presence can be design and build.

Researchers considered social presence necessary to enhance communication or social interaction between firms and customers (Osei-Frimpong & McLean, 2018). The number of social media users is growing dramatically. According to Tankovska (2021), Facebook has more than 2.7 billion active users in the market. The report further illustrates that 87% of adult-use smart phone in the UK per day alone. This indicates that social media and social sites could target the retail firm to push their advertisement. Based on the united nation estimates, the total population of the UK itself is 66.61 million now (Population, 2018). Around half of the UK the population has an active Facebook account (Statistics, 2018). Retail is second in the top 5 industries on Facebook who has 54,127,676 sums of fans (Statistics, 2018). On the other hand, 75% of people in Pakistan own a mobile phone (Ahmed, 2020).

Social presence theory epitomizes social interaction. Biocca & Harms (2002) highlighted on social presence theory that it sheds light on how social cognition's aspects could be affected and enhanced by technology. On this premise, two concepts associated with social presence were highlighted by (Short et al. 1976): the idea of "intimacy" and the concept of "immediacy". While "Intimacy is the role of eye contact, relationship, the topic of conversation and proximity a psychological distance between communicator and recipient described as immediacy" which is "generated verbally and nonverbally" (Tu, 2000). This suggests that social presence leads to the degree of intimacy because of social interactions, which permit consumers to transfer immediacy or non-immediacy nonverbally (physical proximity, facial expression and pictures) and verbally.

A survey was conducted by (Shen et al., 2010) on social presence to analyse user behaviours in an online environment. The idea of social presence was also used by (Kim & Song, 2016) to explain individuals' behaviour and emotion in a social-virtual climate. They found that social identity and knowledge contribution behaviour in social-virtual environments positively relate to social presence.

The interaction made by the subjective quality of the medium is more salient and social. This also increases customer's social presence (Osei-Frimpong & McLean, 2018). Furthermore, this is more likely to enhance their decision-making process.

The effect of social presence in mobile social network service was explored and found that it contributed to users' enjoyment and intention to continue (Choi, 2016). Therefore, customers' trust and perception of the usefulness of information has been increased through social presence (Han et al., 2016).

There is no doubt that considerable time has been devoted to discernment social presence; positive effects have been focused on in most studies. Negative consequences i-e SNS addiction, has been found of social reality in scant research. An individual's communication style is similar to the traditional style when participating in SNS and communicate with others (Cheung et al., 2011). When individuals perceive a high level of social presence through their interactions on an SNS, they tend to be deeply involved and engaged in the SNS. In this case, individuals are likely to become addicted to SNSs.

The importance of social presence in SC adoption cannot be overstated. Social presence may also increase customer trust through the insight that e-vendors have on their websites with features such as sociability, a feeling of personalization, and sensitive human touch (Gefen & Straub, 2004). One-dimensional conceptualizations of social presence may not be appropriate for virtual communities, as participants engage with the computer-mediated medium and converse with other members and immerse themselves in the environment. As a result, a multidimensional understanding of social presence has been promoted (Shen & Khalifa, 2009). Social commerce is a hybrid of e-commerce and online communities. As a result, SP in social commerce should be seen as a complex phenomenon.

2.9.4. Importance of Trust

Many authors revealed that trust is one of the essential aspects influencing the adoption of both e-commerce (Kim & Peterson, 2017; Shin, 2010; Yang et al., 2009) and SC (Brdsee et al., 2012; Hajli et al., 2017; Ng, 2013). As a result, it is critical to evaluate the literature on trust, particularly trust in e-commerce and social commerce.

2.9.4.1. Defining Trust:

The literature shows a diverse range of researches on trust in several fields such as psychology, sociology, and economics. For example, scholars from psychology and sociology were interested in

many facets of Trust. They were interested in individual features of trust in psychology, whereas, in sociology, they were concerned with interpersonal features of trust (Kim & Park, 2013). However, in economics, researchers focused on trust as an expectation of an individual's interactions or a deficit in acceptance and exposure (Beldad et al., 2010). Trust is critical in online buying settings, but it's much more critical in social commerce platforms. Not many face-to-face interactions and a lot more user-generated material occur (Featherman and Hajli, 2015).

On synthesizing the main characteristics of trust in diverse research, Bhattacharya et al. (1998) and Rousseau et al. (1998) conclude that there are few discrepancies in the concept of trust despite changes in emphasis and methodology in different fields. This may be found by browsing through the many definitions. Precisely, each definition presupposes its frame of reference and viewpoint on the phenomena (trust) without expressing the limitations of that frame appropriately (Lewicki and Bunker 1995). All disciplines look for specific common characteristics that underpin trust, such as its nature, antecedents, repercussions, and influencing variables.

2.9.4.2. Understanding Trust

The previous studies are mainly focused on trust from a technological perspective, addressing such issues as privacy, security, infrastructure, etc. But with the development of the technology and widespread of online e-commerce, online interaction systems and especially artificial intelligence, in other words, human-like technologies, researchers began to address the behavioural aspects of trust.

The first view is that of Friedman et al. (2000), who opines “people trust people, not technology”. They say that technology, unlike people, is not moral and cannot do right or wrong, and hence it should be seen as a participant in a lack of trust between a user and the person who designed the technology. This stance is also taken by Olson and Olson (2000), who claim that technology cannot be trustworthy when people interact. Instead, the connection between two people is distrustful, irrespective of the technology they utilize.

Essentially, these views can be distilled to the following two points, which are:

- - People are unable to form relationships with technology
- - The issue of people trusting technology does not emerge because individuals cannot build a trusting connection with technology since it lacks volition and moral agency (Gulati, Sousa & Lamas, 2017).

Trust deals with “the intention to accept vulnerability based upon positive expectations of the intentions or behaviour of another” (Rousseau et al., 1998, p. 395). In transactional buyer-seller relationships, trust will be increased when the trusted party shows behaviour or other indicators by one’s expectations (Gefen and Straub, 2004). With the rise of the internet and e-commerce in the late 1990s, trust has been expanded into a new context. The limited web interface does not allow consumers to judge whether a vendor is trustworthy in a typical face-to-face interaction, resulting in more significant uncertainty and heightened risk in online buying decisions (Bilgihan, 2016). Many researchers have argued that (Asraf et al., 2020; Pappas, 2016) argued that trust is a critical component in the online context, especially when risks are considered significant. Because SC is a subset of e-commerce that uses Web 2.0 technology, trust will continue to play an essential role in minimizing the uncertainty in online purchases. Indeed, previous research (Widodo et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2015) has found that trust is an essential aspect of the business since it drives consumer behaviour, leading to buy intentions.

The assurances, safety, and security of the environment produced by the vendor's place of business or e-commerce shop form the foundation of trust. The context for social trade itself also impacts consumer confidence (Shin, 2010). When they trust a social trade environment, consumers are motivated to buy a product or services and engage in social engagement. Many various social trade applications are available nowadays, in which users may make purchases on file with their credit card. There are many business transactions on Instagram, Facebook, Line, Twitter and many more sites. Since the market is crowded with purchase options, customer trust in the vendor becomes even more important as a prerequisite to consumer shopping, assessments, and purchase decisions. As a result, it is plausible to argue that consumers with higher institution-based trust in social commerce websites and applications are more likely to purchase a product or service and generate more social WOM content to participate in discussions about the purchasing experience (Wang and Yu, 2017).

As previously said, social commerce allows customers to produce content while also allowing everyone to discuss, suggest, and review items or services. As a result, trust cannot be built just on indications from a social commerce website. The interactions and information contributions of consumers are also crucial foundations for shaping trust. As a result, Farrivar et al. (2017) assert that trust will emerge from two sources in social commerce. The first is connected to aspects of a social commerce website's trust-building cues, such as transaction logs and commitments. This source of trust is referred to as "trust toward a place." The second is determined by the interactions and views of other social commerce users. This type of trust is represented by individuals' readiness to be susceptible

to recommendations, comments, evaluations, and criticism. This type of trust is referred to as "trust toward site members" in this study.

These two sorts of trust may assist customers cognitively and emotionally assure that both experienced consumers and website operators are trustworthy. Some reactions, such as buy intents, are likely to be promoted as a result.

Indeed, academics have demonstrated that trust can impact the adoption of various technologies, including online recommendation agents (Tokushige et al., 2017), commercial information systems, e-commerce portals, and knowledge management systems (Thatcher et al., 2011). Some online forums enable members to exchange their knowledge, experience, ideas, and expertise with one another (Yan and Jian, 2017). One of the better examples is Quora, which is a question and answer (Q&A) community. Users of the internet can seek and exchange professional information (Jin et al., 2015).

Some academics have assessed technological trust using the same human-like trust components that have historically been used to evaluate interpersonal trust: honesty, ability/competence, and kindness (Vance et al., 2008). For example, in research on trust in software agents, interpersonal trust beliefs (i.e., competence, integrity, and benevolence) have been used to represent trust in technology because software agents have some human-like characteristics, such as giving advice and interacting with the user on-screen (Benbasat & Wang, 2005). On the other hand, other studies have quantified technology trust using system-like trust categories such as dependability, functionality, and usefulness (McKnight et al., 2011) to practice.

People, for example, connect with other people on Facebook, but they do not receive advice directly from Facebook or connect with it as a person or quasi-person. While many studies on trust in social networking sites have focused on interpersonal trust qualities, users may trust Facebook in other ways. McKnight (2005), for example, says that people may trust technology because it delivers certain functionality, operates dependably, and is beneficial to its clients. As a result, individuals may be prepared to rely on Facebook (or any technology) since it possesses specific technological characteristics that make it trustworthy to use (Lankton & McKnight, 2011).

In general, trust was a critical factor in the adoption of technologies and user satisfaction with the technology (Kassim et al., 2012), and its absence might lead the user to proceed more cautiously while using the technology and to take an unnecessary time to think through their actions (Constantine,

2006). According to the literature assessment, trust plays a critical role in encouraging online transactions (Wang et al., 2016; Cyr et al., 2010; Quelch and Klein, 1996).

2.9.4.3. Role of Trust in E-Commerce and Social Commerce

The fast development of E-commerce is playing a vital and supporting role in service management and the economy (Huang et al., 2017). Murillo (2017) illustrates that it is becoming more popular than before. Therefore, nowadays, firms seek to increase their profit by providing high-quality products and making online purchase safer and more accessible (Thaichon, 2017; Kim et al., 2016). Previous studies show that potential online customers hesitate to complete their transactions via the vendor's website because of their fear of e-transaction (Fortes and Rita, 2016; Kim et al., 2016; Oliveria et al., 2017). Due to customer's anxiety over e-transactions, online shopping is more risky than traditional (Kim et al., 2017). Therefore, the urgency of an effective s-commerce strategy in the hospitality industry needs to be utilized (Ozturk et al., 2016).

In the context of SC, scholars shed light on trust's role with different aspects such as customers' concerns towards website, web assurance (purchase intention, e-transactions, privacy and security (Oliveira et al., 2017). In social commerce, consumers gather information from different sources to make better purchase decisions (Bai et al., 2015). Thus, social components such as online reviews, customer ratings, and social recommendations are the primary tools for assessing the product and service while making purchasing decisions (Hajli, 2017).

As mentioned above that social commerce is a subset of e-commerce that involve web 2.0 technologies. Thus, trust plays a vital role to reduce uncertainty existing in online transactions. It also enables consumers to share information, create content, recommend and rate the product or service. Therefore, only based on some social commerce content, trust cannot quickly develop. As mentioned above, Farivar et al. (2017) highlighted that trust would be developed from two sources in social commerce. They are social commerce website and users' interaction & opinion. The first one leads to its transaction record & commitment. The second one captures individuals' willingness to be vulnerable to the recommendation, comments, reviews, and feedback. Consumer interactions, information contribution, social support and social presence are also an essential factor to shape trust (Farivar et al., 2017).

As social technology increases and individuals on the Internet-connected, confidence and security are

necessary to enable two parties to decrease their perceived risk for transactions (Hajli & Lin, 2014). Research demonstrates that online buyers seek to limit their risk and insecurity, and trust is also one of the critical drivers of website decision making (Farivar et al., 2017). It is also suggested that if e-commerce effectively describes items or services, people are more confident about the site (Ming-Hsien et al., 2009). Social technologies like consumer reviews, knowledge and experience from others in forums & communities can be made more accessible. For example, when a respectable member of an online forum or community gives favourable feedback to a seller, the other members are more confident in it (Lu et al., 2010). Trust is the component that has dramatically affected social influence, and it is apparent that raising consumer trust on websites for social business immediately increases customer satisfaction (Beyari & Abareshi, 2018).

In today's climate, where people's social contacts establish new kinds of interconnectivity and links between individuals, trust studies might be impacted by people's social relationships and interactions. In business interaction, "transaction cost" can be reduced by trust (Wei et al., 2019). It minimizes the desire to monitor the activity of other parties and is part of the trustworthy penalty system (Beyari & Abareshi, 2018). The information provided by the customers and the given information on the website is different from each other. The information provided by consumers through their comments is more credible (Farivar et al., 2017).

Trust in e-commerce is much more critical because trust is fundamental for every kind of business. Trust is crucial in e-commerce to enhance its economic development and competitive advantage (Morid & Shajari, 2012). In conventional business, clients spend time checking their desired products or services, socializing with sellers, and developing their own opinions and confidence. However, in e-commerce, the consumer and business connection is without any human connection faceless, mechanized and impersonal (Hassanein et al., 2009; Lu et al., 2016).

Research has revealed that the lack of trust is a crucial reason for the loss of e-commerce for users and many companies are untrustworthy of their customer relationships (Kim & Park, 2013). This is particularly obvious when companies sell new items or services because buyers are unsure what they are supplied with (Hajli et al., 2014). However, it has been noted that customers tend to feel comfortable and therefore more inclined to trust the company and make an online purchase when companies have a social presence on their website (Ng, 2013; Weisberg et al., 2011).

In the context of this research, social commerce is considered to be a type of e-commerce. It is defined as "the use of Internet-based media that allow people to participate in the marketing, selling,

comparing, curating, buying, and sharing of products and services in both online and offline marketplaces” (Zhou et al., 2013, p.61). Researchers propose that e-commerce trust difficulties maybe be handled through social commerce. This is because social contacts in social commerce can boost consumer trust and decrease perceived dangers, thereby increasing the possibilities to buy (Hajli, 2013; Lu et al., 2010). The societal perspective will alter when individuals interact and engage and share personal experiences on social networks, blogs, forums, and virtual communities.

Researchers observed that customers are more interested in other customers' suggestions and evaluations (Goh et al., 2013; Hajli et al., 2014). This is acceptable as user reviews bring actual experiences with the use of various items or services. Social business consumers enjoy and respect the views of others because, before a payment and delivery procedure, they cannot evaluate the goods physically. Chang & Chen (2008) subjected it to additional contact between online companies and clients, whether in e-commerce or social commerce, which fulfils the company's specified objectives. Therefore, the social business might benefit both the company and the client by solving confidence problems (Noorian et al., 2014).

Multiple research examined social trade and trust relationships. For instance, Hsiao et al. (2010) carried out social business research examining clients' recommendations and trust in empirical terms. From the point of view of social networks, they observed that perceived ability perceived goodwill and perceived critical mass affected trust in product references. They also discovered characteristics that influence trust, including the website's quality, reputation, and reliability (Hsiao et al., 2010).

In addition, the research by Lu et al. (2016) indicated that the social presentation conveyed by web material, such as photos and videos and the social presence sent through salespeople's interaction, had a considerable influence on the customer's confidence. The Commission also noted that other consumers that have experienced the transaction and the goods had strengthened their confidence with the positive information presented. The integration of social variables (social, technological characteristics) is, therefore, as crucial for online enterprises as structural aspects (safe and vital IT facilitated procedures) (Lu et al., 2016).

To endorse trust in an online environment, it is essential to have some mechanisms to provide credible signals to distinguish among sellers (Wang et al., 2018). For this purpose, social commerce constructs provide recommendations, referrals, and ratings. These constructs give sellers reasons to be trustworthy. In the online context, since trust has been considered one of the key elements for online businesses, increasing customer loyalty (Huang et al., 2014) and reducing perceived risks (Poon et al.,

2017) is essential. Social consumer interactions on social platforms and social commerce characteristics are impacting users' behaviour. Researchers believe in buying social activities in SNS's (Han & Windsor, 2011). This study addresses trust, compassion and credibility on two dimensions. Goodwill is goodwill, whereas credibility is reliable, integrity and honesty (Holmes and Parker, 2018). Trust in SNSs as to the extent to which SNS is prepared to implement its commitments and pledges. Therefore, trust is a fundamental part of SNS's functioning (Chu & Kim, 2011).

Social commerce constructs also influence the trust factor. Research shows customer ratings and reviews influence the level of trust, which leads to more sales on that platform (Swamynathan et al., 2008). Moreover, Ratings will also increase user satisfaction when they undertake a transaction. Kim and Snog (2010) concluded that word of mouth (online reviews) significantly impacts purchase intention through its positive effect on trust. In addition, social context is the other factor that influences social trust (Weisberg, Te'eni, & Arman, 2011). When an online vendor has a social fan page, SC platform, or social presence (Lu et al., 2016), consumers feel more secure and have more intention to buy. Previous research shows that social presence increases trust (Lu et al., 2016) and that SCCs can achieve social presence. Consumers' social interactions create social word of mouth, which positively affects trust (Kim & Park, 2013). It has been revealed in previous studies that consumers are more dependent on the trustworthy mediator, which protect the consumers in online transactions (Shi and Liao, 2017).

Furthermore, it was established that trust played an essential part in improving purchasing intention (Hassan et al., 2018). Also, Trust has reduced perceived risk, which is essential when exploring an online environment for new products or services (Marriott and Williams, 2018; Shin, 2010). The role of trust in social commerce adoption should thus be investigated.

In previous research, several features of consumers, businesses, and platforms be crucial in developing trust online (Kim & Park, 2013; Kim & Peterson, 2017; Yahia et al., 2018). The online trust's often researched history includes trust, reputation, security, quality of service and utility (Kim & Peterson, 2017). Yahia et al. (2018) found that the hedonic efforts of a social business vendor connected to the consumer confidence in the seller but did not consider the influence on product trust.

2.10. Associated Theories and Models with Social Commerce Adoption:

The previous chapters explored the context of technology growth and social commerce and literature on the Adoption/implementation of emerging technology such as SC in developing countries by SMEs.

Numerous models and theories associated with SMEs' use of information technology for e-commerce are discussed in the section. In an organizational context, the acceptance process of any IT has been defined as dynamic and multidimensional. The technology adoption process is linked with multiple variables and factors (Abdullah et al., 2013). The author further identified that it is also related to technical features and the enterprise's internal and external environment. This process has also been explored from several theoretical viewpoints using various frameworks in the broader IT literature. In this section, the strengths and weaknesses of the three identified theoretical perspectives are examined, covering the **Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) Theory, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) Framework.**

The aim is to summarize the factors mentioned above affecting the adoption of SC by SMEs and select the appropriate structure. This section ends by justifying the selection of the TOE model to support this study.

2.10.1. Evaluation of Existing Models and Theories of IT adoption:

For establishing an economic system characterized by multiple countries, the adoption and implementation of SC by SMEs are significant (He et al., 2017; Kendall et al., 2006). For more than a decade, researchers and practitioners in many economies have concentrated on SC and SM adoption. Thus various theories, frameworks and models aim to explain that SC is an innovation in many ways and needs to be more explored. In this regard, Poorangi, Edward, Nikoonejad, & Kardevani (2013) pointed out that one of the key reason being that the SC adoption studies were more focused in most developed countries and Western economies such as Canada, Australia, the USA, New- Zealand, UK and other developed European countries. Hence, the developing economies got less attention. The researcher highlighted that most scientific and development centres are there, scholars have paid high importance to these countries.

Oliveira and Martins (2011) found that five models are commonly used to examined the adoption of the latest technology: the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM); the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB); Diffusion of Innovation (DoI); the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Technology Use (UTATU); and the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) Framework. According to the analysis by Molinillo and Japutra (2017), also argued that six different theories have been established and used to determine the drivers of technology innovation – including the adoption of SC at various levels of SMEs.

Such theories and models vary in their concentration, and each has a specific importance. For example, the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory highlights the features of the technology on implementation. Other areas of study include theoretical viewpoints on behavioural features, making TAM or UTAUT more valid. Several theories and models focus more on the technology adoption from consumers' perspective (TAM, TPB, UTAUT), whereas other theoretical approaches are described as organizational-led (TOE and DOI).

However, after examining many theoretical studies related to the adoption of e-commerce by SMEs, Molinillo and Japutra (2017) and Ajimoko (2018) discovered that the Diffusion of Innovation (DoI) theory (Rogers, 1962); the Technology Acceptance (TAM) Model (Davis, 1989) and the Technology-Organizational-Environmental (TOE) framework (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990) were those mainly used by these researchers in their studies on technology adoption by SMEs. Therefore, the following section considers only these three theories.

2.11. Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory:

Rogers (2003), DOI Theory is often used in research to identify the factors that influence the dissemination in a social system of inventions (Tan et al., 2012). Dissemination provides creativity (new ideas, application, product and technologies) through a particular medium between the social system participants. According to Rogers (2003, p. 5–6), the theory explains Various physiologic variables influencing decisions on IT system invention. This theory has been applied primarily in many sectors, including medicine, education and sociology, geography, communication (Murray, 2009). Information systems are based on theoretical theories for executing their projects (Majanja & Kiplangat, 2005). Innovation diffusion, in other words, subscriber takeover, is a significant determinant of a company's performance (Frambach & Schillewaert, 2002). Rogers (2003) model clarifies the innovation-related variables by 28 behaviours in five characteristics. Developing an attitude towards innovation is a reason behind the success and failure of the innovation.

Any “idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption” (Rogers, 2003) – Five fundamental innovation characteristics impact and are known as innovation adoption rates: (1) relative advantage, (2) compatibility, (3) complexity, (4) trialability, and (5) observability. These characteristics are expected to be the most significant predictors of the rate of innovation adoption, as discussed below.

2.11.1. Relative Advantage:

Rogers (1995) described relative advantage as “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes” (Rogers, 1995). Innovations' financial productivity and expectations of service quality are defined as the relative advantages. Furthermore, Rogers also categorized innovations in two types: preventive creativity, which is a new idea that a person accepts now but receives the incentive or profits, later on, his rate of adoption is therefore weak (Rogers 1995, p.217); and Incremental innovations that produce meaningful effects in the near term (Rogers, 1995, p.17).

2.11.2. Compatibility:

Compatibility is well-defined as “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, past experiences, and needs of potential adopters” (Rogers, 1995, p.224). A shortage of compatibility among information systems and human requirements is likely to disrupt this technology.

2.11.3. Complexity:

Complexity can be well-defined as “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as relatively difficult to understand and use” (Rogers, 1995). The distinction is that complexity is negatively associated with adoption rates. Therefore, the more complicated an innovation is, the greater the challenges and threats to its adoption.

2.11.4. Trialability:

Same as relative advantage and compatibility, trialability is associated positively with adoption degree: “It is the degree to which an innovation may have experimented on a limited basis” (Rogers, 1995, p.243). The different technologies are attempted, the more likely they are to be updated and redefined so that they can be adopted as quickly as possible.

2.11.5. Observability:

In this model, observability is defined as “the degree to which the results of an innovation are visible to others”, which is positively connected to the rate of innovation adoption (Rogers, 2003, p.244).

Although this model was commonly used, DoI was criticized since the core technical aspects of the invention being investigated are considered and do not incorporate other internal or external adopted considerations, which might be critical. Also, DoI may not take into account the impacts of environmental and organisational variables (Amin and Hussin, 2014; Tehrani and Shirazi, 2014), and CEO capabilities are not included. In various ICT adoption studies, which have shown that decisions surrounding technical adoption reside with the owners/managers of SMEs (Abdullah et al., 2012; Warrick, 2017). In addition, several decades of studies have questioned the predictive ability of DOI (Bass, 2004).

Since DOI's technical and organisational aspects are similar to the TOE framework's innovations and organisational contexts. (Amin and Hussin, 2014), Oliveira and Martins (2011) have argued that integrating environmental considerations of the TOE paradigm increases the implementation and adequacy of the framework as contrasted with DoI. Therefore, DoI does not seem to be the most appropriate option for the study.

2.12. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM):

TAM is an additional well-known, stable, moderate model commonly used to describe technology adoption (Chuttur, 2009). It was introduced by Davis (1989) to predict the behavioural intention to adopt technologies. TAM has been widely used in various studies and verified in different situations, conditions, and different objects to assess individual behaviour in technology acceptance (Sanchez & Hueros, 2010). TAM is considered most relevant in predicting the desire and readiness to adopt the technology (Johar & Awalluddin, 2011). The model suggests that technology adoption depends mainly on two variables: perceived ease of use (PEU) and perceived usefulness (PU). Due to its basic structure and few features (Agarwal and Prasad, 1999), TAM was simple to use and was subsequently commonly used for IT adoption (Abdullah et al., 2013; Chuttur, 2009). The widespread use of TAM has contributed to the inclusion of other constructions/anticipates in the model. For instance, Venkatesh et al. (2003) proposed that other constructs (effort expectancy, performance expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions) explicitly impact consumer intention to embrace technologies. Analysis such as the TAM II and UTAUT resulted in many derivatives of TAM (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

The study of Alomary & Woollard (2015) describes TAM undergoing modification and development. In 2000, the attitudes towards usage were eliminated, which means that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use directly affect behavioural intention to use. The continued development of TAM

was recorded in 2008 by adding a new dimension to the PEOU construct. The development of TAM is intended to form basic assumptions capable of predicting and explaining the concept of behaviour caused by technological developments (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000).

There are several reasons why people accept or reject technology, but two are more important and influential. Initially, the user assumes that their efficiency would increase when using modern technology, known as perceived usefulness (Davis, 1989). Secondly, the user believes that it is easy to use the technology. Davis (1989) theorized this as perceived ease of use. These two are primary factors in the consumer intent to use a technological device (Davis, 1989) and significantly influence intention to shop online, which can be extended into investigations on user online behaviour in accepting the B2C model in e-commerce (Pavlou, 2003). The paths in TAM can also apply in e-commerce (Gefen et al., 2003). As indicated in previous research (Hajli, 2012), these paths can apply in the social commerce adoption model to develop an integrated model with the impact of social components.

TAM is a model for studying the adoption of a given technology by individuals. However, some attempts have been made (which are pretty fragmented) to use TAM to evaluate technology adoption in the organization (Abdullah et al., 2013). Therefore, it is not widely used for technology adoption in an organizational context, as this study focuses. Also, Chuttur (2009) argued that the impressive number of studies using TAM has contributed to the model's saturation level and reduced its usefulness in practice. Furthermore, in contrast to TOE, the predictive strength of TAM, the latter is regarded as having the more predictive and explicative ability, which makes TAM not considered the most appropriate approach to support this study. The following section provides the reason for choosing the TOE as a theory for studying social media adoption in SMEs.

2.13. Technology-Organization-Environment Framework (TOE) Theory:

After examining Rogers' process model and attributes, it was clear that multidimensional variables were excluded. In the context of technology adoption in SMEs, multiple factors are essential as adoption is determined by multiple factors (Abdullah et al., 2013). Such factors are internal organizational and external environmental factors. These are significant factors to investigate the technology adoption in any organization (Damanpour & Gopalakrishnan, 1998; Damanpour & Schneider, 2006; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). DOI is limited in focusing only on the technical dimensions of innovation when considering adoption and does not focus on the internal and external variables essential for technology adoption by organisations (Tehrani & Shirazi, 2014). On the other

hand, TAM focuses on technology adoption by consumers and does not have any features to examine the adoption process from an organizational perspective (Abdullah et al., 2013).

Therefore, another theory was urgently needed to understand these facets of adopting technologies in an organization. The TOE framework was considered the ideal way to research ICT implemented in SMEs, as it involves the applicability and the broader exploratory approaches (Baker, 2011; Abeysinghe & Alsobhi, 2013). TOE is a commonly recognized IT adoption model in organizations, including SMEs.

Moreover, when analyzing factors impacting adoption at the organizational level, TOE is more analytical and explicative strength (Oliveira & Martins, 2011). Therefore, factors that influence SM adoption in organizations have been used to research. Abed (2020) TOE model was also employed to look into Saudi Arabian SMEs' SC adoption.

It was first established by Tornatzky, Fleischer and Chakrabarti (1990) as a theoretical framework to monitor the adoption of different types of IT innovation. In addition, it extends engineers and entrepreneurs' creation of technologies to promote consumers' adoption and implementation of innovations in business contexts. It was considered a perfect theoretical structure to predict and describe the use of a known technology (Ndekwa and Katunzi, 2016; Yeboah-Boateng and Essandoh, 2014; Ramdani et al., 2013). It was later expanded, and further studies were carried out by Oliveira and Martins (2010), Srivastava and Teo (2010); Chong and Ooi (2008); Pan and Jang (2008); Chau and Tam (1997).

The TOE framework has been developed as a comprehensive and reliable framework for evaluating various aspects of internal (technological and organizational) and external (environmental) factors that affect the adoption of different ICTs, especially in SMEs. Baker (2012) suggests the TOE structure reflects one segment of the process by which the environment of an organization affects innovation adoption and implementation. Therefore, TOE has strong applicability and exploratory capacity to study a wide range of technologies (Baker, 2012). Since TOE was established in 1990, the adoption and application of different technologies have been investigated in various contexts in developed and developing countries. For example, it was used to research cloud computing adoption (Gangwar et al., 2015), web-based self-service technology adoption in the hospitality industry (Lee, 2016), understanding CRM adoption stages (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2019), Social commerce adoption using TOE framework (Abed, 2020) and challenges of cloud computing adoption from the TOE framework perspective (Al-Hujran et al., 2018). In this situation, this framework comprises an organizational

theory that describes three different factors concerning the decision making of technology, which is: the technological context, the organizational context, and the environmental context.

The context of technology encompasses both internal and external technologies. Internal technology refers to the technology currently used in the business, whereas external technologies are those on the marketplace that are not used in the organization. Internal as well as external technology can involve equipment or practice. The organisation's context relates to different features of the company, such as size, communication processes within the organisation, and the amount of 'slack' resource. The environment encompasses the industry's framework, rivalry and stakeholders' pressure and the regulatory environment. (Tehrani and Shirazi, 2014; Baker, 2012; Ramdani et al., 2009; Tornatzky et al., 1990). it was found that The higher the pressure from business partners/consumers and perceived SME rivals, the more likely the technology was to be adopted – especially SC -to be competitive in the market.

It is essential that social commerce adoption among SMEs be better understood and predicted. Hence, The TOE model has been chosen to underpin this study as a theoretical framework. This choice is justified for many factors. First, In an organisation context, TOE is appropriate to research adoption, As in the current study, where SMEs are the subject of the research. Secondly, Amin and Hussin (2014) defined that TOE has a sound scientific foundation and consistent analytical assistance. Third, It complies with other theories of IT innovation at the organisational level, such as DOI (Jain et al., 2011), to reinforce and expand the explanatory capability of the network (Al Nahian et al., 2009). Fourth, this is seen as comprehensive and can also be used to research the adoption of any IS technology. (Zhu et al., 2002). Fifth, the integration of the three contexts (technology, organisation and environment) Compared to other adoption models, TOE offers a holistic view of factors affecting IT innovation adoption (Gangwar et al., 2015). Finally, the TOE framework has been applied to study the adoption of several innovations, as stated earlier, indicating its suitability for social commerce study.

The TOE framework is an interactive model, assuming that improvements in an entity are interpreted not only by an organization's individuals but also by the features of the organization in which they function. This interactive perspective allows the researcher in a diverse sense to explore both variables and their relationships (Molla & Licker, 2005), and the introduction of e-commerce innovation should be described (Rahayu & Day, 2015).

However, despite several favourable opinions on the TOE, limitations of this theory remain. For example, Altayyar and Beaumont-Kerridge (2016), Ghobakhloo and Tang (2013) and Rahayu and Day (2015) revealed in their respective studies within Saudi Arabia, Iran and Indonesia. As Ghobakhloo and Tang (2013) proposed, one criticism is that the variables related to individual characteristics of managers' and owner-managers roles in small companies are overlooked in this model. Furthermore, they found that the TOE system established a systematic theoretical foundation for studying e-commerce determinants in organisations in developing economies but does not concentrate on individual factors, such as owner-managers and management, including administrators and employees. However, Pudjianto and Hangjung (2009) claimed that The TOE structure has been previously confirmed to be adaptive and can be further expanded to identify and add more variables and categories that help discover and find drivers and challenges relevant to the adoption of technology. Zhu et al. (2006) further believed that the study could introduce more themes and sub-themes to the TOE structure. Thus, this study concludes that an additional context should and must be included; the expanded single factors that affect S-commerce adoption by SMEs in the Pakistani context. This is because understanding SMEs's-commerce adoption in emerging economies needs frameworks that are sufficiently flexible to accommodate changes (AlSharji et al., 2018). The following section of this study discusses the original dimension and the expanded (extended individual context) dimension of the TOE structure. It Uses the TOE framework to examine the identified factors in the literature.

2.13.1. TOE's Background:

TOE has three contexts: technology, organisation, and environment. This section provides descriptions of the factors that support each context. It is worth noting that some of the factors are widely debated in the literature on IT adoption. Each of the context and their corresponding factors 'details are given below.

2.13.2. Technology Context:

The technical background relates to adopting developments in the SME environment using various ICT systems and other associated network technology (Soto-Acosta et al., 2018). An analysis of current IT adoption literature by TOE reveals that the benefits of technical features have long been accepted. Many studies have argued that the adoption process has a series of technological characteristics (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990).

In addition to Rogers' technological factors, several scholars have also found other technological factors (Altayyar & Beaumont-Kerridge, 2016; Shemi & Procter, 2013). Technological preparation (Zhu et al., 2006), protecting technological frameworks and online transaction protection (Steeves et al., 2015). Furthermore, Machado and Chung (2015) defined that enhanced software and technology integration infrastructure. However, the costs associated with technology in developing economies were the most common factor among all researchers.

2.13.2.1. Complexity:

Another technical factor that is a deciding factor for emerging technology embraced by SMEs is perceived ease of use (Gangwar et al., 2015). Rajan and Caral (2015) suggest a negative relation between the perceived difficulty of IT and the decision on adoption. In short, the study has demonstrated the need for simple use and comprehension of emerging technology to support the implementation of decisions. Moreover, SMEs tend to be less likely to implement more difficult technologies.

2.13.2.2. Perceived Compatibility:

Several studies show that ICT compatibility and the decision to implement in SMEs are positively linked (Alshamaila et al., 2013; Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2013). It was suggested that the implementation of emerging technology could lead to changes in the organisation's values, and the existing organizational structures may also be interrupted. Furthermore, Changes to the current technical infrastructure could be required. Therefore, it is essential, especially for SMEs, that the future improvements be compatible with the organisation's values, requirements, work practices, and current technological infrastructure (Kurnia et al., 2015). For a given technology, a high degree of perceived compatibility is essential from the point of view of an SME owner-manager to be implemented.

2.13.2.3. Electricity Shortfall:

Small and medium-sized enterprises in developing (mainly in the South Asia region) countries face an energy shortfall as another technical driver. SMEs cannot use ICT units for the SC system without electricity. Several studies (e.g., Hyder & Lussier, 2016; Shemi & Procter, 2013; SMEDA, 2017) have shown that many SMEs have not taken over technology innovation due to a lack of consistent energy in developing economies. Even when the internet is available, continued use by SMEs, especially in rural areas, is hindered by a lack of energy.

A strong relationship found between electricity shortfall and the performance of SMEs in developing countries (Scott et al., 2014). The analysis indicates a positive relationship between the power shortage and the costs of business activities of SMEs. Electricity outages in the context of high alternative power generating costs in SMEs are higher, as they could affect the production and damage of equipment. In addition, outages of energy lead to high production cost and decrease SME efficiency (Doe and Asamoah, 2014; Tarun et al., 2013).

2.13.3. Organizational Context:

Many research at the organizational level tends to concentrate on organisational features – SMEs in particular (Vongsraluang and Bhatiasevi, 2017). Literature reviews have highlighted that organisational factors like managerial support, financial support, the size and structure of the business, organizational culture, and leadership role significantly affect ICTs adoption in SMEs. (Vongsraluang and Bhatiasevi, 2017; Ali et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2018). Among these, it was found that firm size (Martins et al., 2015) and Top management encouragement is a critical factor in emerging economies' acceptance of technologies and positively affects the adoption of SCs by SMEs in developing economies. (Martins et al., 2015; Ali et al., 2019).

2.13.3.1. Enterprise size:

The size of corporations is one of the critical influence factors in technological innovation (Oliveria et al., 2014). It was argued that large companies are most likely to embrace new technologies such as SC adoption (Abed, 2020). The key factors are that large organizations have more financial and human capital. However, the financial model of cloud computing services makes it attractive to SMEs, meaning that enterprise size is one of the determinants to investigate concerning cloud computing adoption.

2.13.3.2. Top management support:

Top management support refers to the level of support offered by the upper management in adopting technologies for business use (Grover & Goslar, 1993). Vongsraluang and Bhatiasevi (2017) suggested that Top management assistance is one of the three most crucial organizational determinants for IT innovation adoption. Furthermore, TOE-based research into technology adoption has recognized that the support of top management in the organisational decision to implement innovations has an essential and positive correlation, especially in SMEs (Oliveira et al., 2014; Ramdani et al., 2009; Ali et al.,

2019). Consequently, organizations with more incredible top management support for new innovative technologies are likely to embrace more social commerce.

2.13.3.3. CEOs' Innovativeness:

In SMEs, CEOs make significant decisions (Isma'ili et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 2015; Dahnil et al., 2014). Significant decisions are the one which is taken to attain or retain a strategic advantage, the receptiveness and attitude of SME CEOs towards new ideas is correlated with this aspect. It was claimed that innovative CEOs “would prefer to apply distinctive and risk solutions such as IS that modify the structure in which the problems are generated”.

This aspect represents an enterprise's degree of receptivity to innovations, including new ICTs. Social commerce adoption is one possible approach towards a competitive edge. Therefore, once CEOs understand that social commerce is one of the best ways to achieve a strategic edge, they improve their constructive approach to social business (Ali et al., 2019). It indicates that SMEs with more innovative CEOs have stronger beliefs about the usefulness of social commerce

Al-Qirim (2008) reported that innovation by the CEO is one of the critical factors in deciding to embrace e-commerce. Many published studies have investigated the factor (see, for example, Siamagka et al., 2015; Alshamaila, 2012; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; AlQirim; 2008). For instance, Thong and Yap (1997) have directed that Small companies are more likely to accept IT if they have a more creative CEO and a constructive outlook towards IT acceptance. Therefore, CEOs' innovativeness plays a significant role to adopt social commerce in SMEs.

2.13.3.4. Organizational Readiness:

Organizational readiness is another construct in an organizational context, referring to the amount of available technological and financial resources for adopting new innovative technologies in the organization (Puklavec et al., 2018). Ramdani et al. (2013, p. 738) well-defined organizational readiness as “the availability of the needed organizational resources for adoption”. Rogers (1995) proposed that the availability of organizational capital has a significant and beneficial effect on innovative technology adoption in any organization.

Fathian et al. (2008) examined the models for e-readiness assessments and established core factors for SMEs. Aboelmaged (2014) recently found a clear positive link between production firms' e-readiness and technological competence and infrastructure. Similarly, the empirical study of Oliveira et al. (2014) suggests that employee's IT capabilities and technological infrastructure have made it easier

for both manufacturing and business businesses to embrace cloud computing. In addition, the IT experience of employees facilitates new application growth within the organization. Thus, with the requisite infrastructure and IT experience, modern technology can be implemented and embraced more efficiently (Oliveira and Martins, 2011).

2.13.4. Environment context:

The TOE framework's environmental context covers the market structure, the distribution of technology resources to vendors, and the organization's dogmatic climate (Awa et al., 2016; Baker, 2012). The environmental context is the third number of factors found in the TOE system for implementing IS technologies in SMEs. The literature on IT adoption indicates that exploring the context under which SMEs work helps explain ICT adoption within those businesses (Gangwar et al., 2015).

The area in which a business works is assumed to be a primary catalyst for implementing technologies as companies adapt to changes in the external climate. (Alshamaila et al., 2012). The environmental context of a The TOE paradigm aims to explain better the role of external environmental pressures on the acceptance of organizations (Taylor, 2019). Several environmental factors have been described as shaping the decision of a company to implement emerging technology, such as competitive pressure, industry type, and market scope, external IS support, and customer pressure.

2.13.4.1. Government Support:

In several countries, the government's position in promoting SC adoption by SMEs has not been overlooked. Government policies play a crucial role in the growth of social media in the commercial sector of a region (AlSharji et al., 2018). Furthermore, Government involvement is also seen as necessary to promote technological developments in SMEs. By developing a supportive system, the government may support the country's business sector, which entails creating an acceptable regulatory framework and helping local business institutes implement beneficial and efficient SME technology policies, and providing financial and technical support by financial regulatory agencies of the government and banks, Improving ICT technology for SMEs and enforcing commerce laws and regulations (Hassan et al., 2018). According to Al-Qirim (2008), for the economic growth of developed and developing countries, the institutional environment built by governments through policies and interventions is essential. In support of this statement, the SMEs in developed countries are adopting the modern ICTs more effectively, as the local govt provide them with an ICT infrastructure to support small businesses (Lim et al., 2018).

Rahayu and Day (2015) illustrated that developing countries face corruption, poverty, elimination of hunger, and a higher illiteracy rate. Further, Chatzoglou and Chatzoudes (2016) and Durbhakula and Kim (2011) concluded that e-government implementation that facilitates online participation and the Government's vision and policies have a statistically relevant influence on the growth of the SC. While studying the role of government in developing economies, (Rana et al., 2017) concluded that Governments should support SMEs to encourage ICT use, provide training and build a regulatory structure. Competition between multiple providers – irrespective of the market – will have a beneficial influence on accessibility, expenditure and the implementation of emerging technologies in government policy. Therefore, developing countries need to have free and competitive telecommunications markets with the assistance of different ISPs; it provides various technical solutions and superb network services (including broadband) to users, who then preferred different new technologies to support SC and reliable broadband networks.

2.13.4.2. Competitive pressure:

In addition, it is used as an opportunity for innovative technology for companies in the same sector. A significant number of organizational IT adoption literature recognize that competitive pressures play an essential role in the adoption process. According to Bhattacharya and Wamba (2018), Organizations are more likely to introduce emerging innovations in response to intense market competition to increase efficiency and overall survival. It is now more necessary to achieve competitive benefit since many companies today are subjected to compete globally. In the context of SMEs, Several studies have found a significant competitive impact on the use of different forms of technology (Bhattacharya and Wamba, 2018); Ifinedo (2011); Molinillo and Japutra, 2017).

According to Ochola (2015), Competitive strength is associated with the degree of SC adoption, and competitive pressure is a deciding factor in SME SC adoption. Furthermore, Wang and Zhang (2012) explained that competitive pressure and business trend expectations could influence the decision of the company to use SC as a technology. Ochola (2015) confirmed that there is also a relation between the strength of competition in a market and the level of SC adoption. However, only a few studies have examined the impact of this factor on SC adoption in developing economies (Abed, 2016; Hajli, 2013; Makame et al., 2014).

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction:

The development of different ICT features has been adopted in many different countries and Social Commerce innovation in SMEs. However, in the SMEs context, only limited developments have taken place regarding ICT and SC adoption in SMEs in developing countries. Many publications that offer details about the acceptance and growth of S-Commerce in SMEs in emerging economies have been analysed in the last chapters of this study. This study mainly aims to discover the hidden factors behind S-commerce adoption between various SMEs in developing economies, such as Pakistan. This chapter addresses the qualitative research methodology in conjunction with the collection from many variables and steps of the relevant research philosophy. In this research, the research design phase is split into numerous essential parts based on the "research onion" (Saunders et al., 2016, p.124).

This chapter is intended to show the research design used in this study to explore the motivation behind SMEs' adoption of social commerce in Pakistan's private sector. The chapter first discusses the opinion of the other scholars about the philosophical conclusions that underpin the study. This is necessary to identify the reach and limits of research design and discuss different research strategies in the ICT & IS, where research design has been selected. Furthermore, the research methodology is explored further and briefly introduced and explained the chosen research methods. Therefore, the significance of this chapter is to lay the groundwork on which the research design can then be addressed.

Figure 3.1: Research Onion

Taken from (Saunders et al., 2012)

3.2. Research Philosophy:

The research philosophy embraced by numerous researcher is based on core conclusion about their understanding of the universe (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Denzin & Lincoln, 2018; Saunders et al., 2016). According to Oates (2005, p. 282), the research philosophy refers to: "A set of assumptions or ways of thinking about some aspects of the world". These assumptions support the strategy for research design and the methods chosen for the analysis (Saunders et al., 2016).

In general, it is said that ontology, epistemology and axiology are three philosophical fields related to methodological queries. This study addressed each of the philosophical assumptions, explaining in detail how to use them in terms of the current research, and then links them to different interpretative frameworks that operate at a more specific level of the research process; as indicated in the research onion (Saunders et al., 2016).

The research onion reflects various routes or centres in which data collection strategies are first chosen, and then analyses proceed. The onion centre demonstrates how precisely data can be gathered to address questions from the study. This centre can be reached by removing vital layers during the final stage of data processing. The critical layers that must be removed to access the middle, i.e., data collection methods, include the philosophy of research, research paradigm, types of research, research approaches, the research strategy, and the data collection techniques (Saunders et al., 2016).

3.2.1. Ontological Philosophy:

Saunders et al. (2016, p. 147) illustrate that ontology refers to "assumptions about the nature of reality or being and its characteristics". The definition of ontology has created misunderstanding for many people, as many other philosophical definitions were identified before (Eke, 2012, p.60). Ontology is defined as: "the study or science of the nature of reality" (Eke, 2012, p.60). Multiple socially structured realities are present in ontology (Mertens, 2007, p.216). In other terms, ontology seeks to recognise "what is" (Kanamugire and Ndayishimiye, 2016, p.20).

From their perspective of vital, realistic ontology, Perlesz and Lindsay (2003, p.33) illustrated that reality already exists, but they assume it cannot be achieved entirely. Ontology is divided into two parts: objectivism and constructionism. The distinction is evident in social science - 'Organisation' and 'culture' (Kanamugire and Ndayishimiye, 2016, p.19). Organisations, seen as a phenomenon, take place through the interpretations and behaviour of people who work there (Eke, 2012, p.60).

Creswell and Creswell (2018) explain in more depth this assertion and state that when various researchers perform qualitative analysis, they embrace multi-reality ideas, much like the people researched and the readers of those studies. Qualitative scholars seek to illustrate these different realities as part of the study of individuals. The Multiple Truth Test involves multiple quotations based on individuals' actual words; therefore, multiple people's opinions are presented. Furthermore, in a study by Eriksson and Kovalainen (2016), Ontology refers to the nature and interactions between persons, community, institutions and the environment in general. This suggests that reality is dependent on emotions and perceptions that may vary for each person and organisation, and over time and context, this may change. However, it is possible to share the intellectual experience of reality. Two competing ontological positions have been extended: objectivism (realism) and subjectivism (nominalism). According to Bryman (2004), objectivism indicates that the social thing in issue conforms independently to the researcher's consciousness to an external objective reality. On the other hand, subjectivism means that social institutions can and should be treated as social structures dependent on social actors' expectations and behaviour (Irene, 2014).

Furthermore, social science also revealed that social science covers the individual's behaviour and the existence of social facts, respectively categorised objectivism and constructivism (Bryman, 2016). However, these four ontology types are extremes. Therefore, Easterby-Smith et al. (2015) provide insight into four central continuum ontological positions (see Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.2: Four Different Ontologies

3.2.2. Epistemological Philosophy:

Epistemology is described as "the paradigms of structure is objectivist, meaning that truth exists and that knowledge of the truth can be discovered empirically" (Hadley, 2012, p.21). Epistemology is defined as a philosophy that addresses the nature of knowledge and how knowledge can potentially be gained (Eke, 2012, p.61). It was mentioned by Hornstein (2007, p.146) that epistemology is "taken as trying to account for how beliefs arise, how they relate to each other, and how they relate to the world". The multidisciplinary business and management context ensures that various forms of knowledge are available. Reality, perception, narratives, or stories, from digital to textual and visual data, should be considered legitimate (Saunders et al., 2016).

More recently, Creswell and Creswell (2018) have better described the epistemological assumption, stating that this epistemological assumption enables various researchers to get as close as possible to the organisational participants with the qualitative analysis. In practice, qualitative researchers perform their research in the "field" where participants live and work. Suppose the researcher remains in the

field or aims to get more participant's information. In that case, it's easier to get to know them and then get new insights and knowledge about the phenomena from participants.

Kanamugire and Ndayishimiye (2016, p.20) described that the utilisation of epistemological philosophy benefits scientists in two significant ways. Firstly, this helps the researcher define study methods by allowing researchers to design research and determine the research strategies, the type of analysis, where data is gathered, and how it is viewed. Secondly, it helps to assess an appropriate or inappropriate design depending on the defined goals. (Thorpe and Lowe, 2002, pp.103-105; Kanamugire and Ndayishimiye, 2016, p.20). Several scholars have reported many types of epistemology: positivism and interpretationism (Bryman, 2016, p.24-27; Kanamugire and Ndayishimiye, 2016, p.20).

In conclusion, Researchers strive to minimise distance or gap physically (Guba & Lincoln, 1988, p. 94) between the participants and themselves. Studying these participants' experiences can only be recorded by listening to them because they have been through the process (Kreiner et al., 2009). In this light, thus, knowledge is considered by epistemological purists as a subscription to the paradigm of humanistic studies "interpretivism" – a subjective stance. The other extreme stance, which considers information objective and tangible, aligns with natural science approaches and is related to an epistemological role known as "positivism" (Irene, 2014). Objectivists aim to uncover the reality of the social universe by measurable facts, through which generalisations like the law can be made regarding fundamental social reality. In contrast, subjectivists believe that reality is created through social interaction, in which Social stakeholders partly establish traditional definitions and realities (Saunders et al., 2016). In other words, taking an extreme subscription to either a subjective/objective ontology or an interpretivism/positivism epistemology, pure commitment to qualitative/quantitative analysis emerges (Irene, 2014).

In this research, the researcher focused on SME owners and employees' quotes and testimonies. This included working with other managerial members, investing time in the field, and becoming an "insider" to thoroughly grasp the social process of embracing s-commerce in a specific SME. It was done to analyse several factors which encourage s-commerce adoption in Pakistan's SMEs. Based on the epistemological philosophy, the researchers analysed the present general condition of the selected organisations in greater depth, including historical, geographic and socio-cultural backgrounds. The aim is to consider the case and the way their realities are lived in their technological climate. Therefore, in this research, the researcher was formally and non-formally communicating with the organisations. Thus, an interpretation is established of the phenomena. After choosing an appropriate philosophy, the

researcher was interested in opinions and narratives after adopting an appropriate theory that could explain participants' diverse social realities in organisations.

3.2.3. Axiological Philosophy:

The study process's role of values and ethics is axiology, essentially, how researchers and participants treat their values (Saunders 2016, p. 128). All researchers apply values to a study, but qualitative researchers expose their values through a study. It is the axiological theory that defines qualitative research. Similarly, Creswell and Poth (2016) stated that in a qualitative study, researchers understand the essence of the study's value and announce its beliefs and prejudices vigorously and the essence of the value of the obtained knowledge in the region.

Creswell and Creswell (2017) defined a more recent study that researchers "position themselves" in a study. In the biography of interpretation, for example, the researcher's presence is apparent in the text. The writer acknowledges that the stories expressed reflect the author's understanding and presentation and the subject of the study. As a result, the worldview of the participants affected the kinds of questions raised. This is not limited to data collection because the findings are evaluated after the analysis. The extrapolation of subjects is often impacted by the values of researchers' knowledge and worldviews which are not in this form of research. At the same time, participants' beliefs, perceptions and world views connect with researchers' values to expand the study (Kreiner et al., 2009). The researcher did not aim to "position" himself throughout the data gathering process.

The aim was to devote as much time as possible in small and medium-sized businesses to acquire actual knowledge on the phenomenon; with the experience of various participants at different levels of organisations without any impact and to disclose their importance, values, and biases when collecting data. Therefore, the axiological hypothesis as a philosophy of research is not appropriate for this form of research. The three sets of the above discussed philosophical assumptions have an evident influence on the fourth set of methodological assumptions (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Neuman & Robson, 2020), as described below.

3.2.4. Methodological Philosophy:

The methodology refers to the organisation's values, providing a procedure to facilitate the study and research design (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2015). The methodology is sometimes called the philosophy of methods. The critical point of the methodology is to explain how to research a specific problem. Buckley and Chiang (1976) defined research methodology as an architectural research technique or

practice in which the researcher approaches problem finding and resolution. Silverman (2013) also pointed out that methodologies should be briefly defined and schematically (e.g., quantitative and qualitative methodologies), or narrowly and accurately (e.g., substantive theory, case studies and ethnography), and that methods have also been categorised into data collection methods (e.g. interviews and observations). Crotty and Crotty (1998) confirms that the methodology is a global investigative strategy that defines the collection and use of particular techniques linked to anticipated findings of researchers. Furthermore, the selection of the research approach is based on the search problem type and characteristics. In addition, Creswell & Creswell (2017) described the methodological theory and identified qualitative research methods in detail – they are characterised as inductive, emerging and shaped by the researcher's experience in collecting and analysing data.

The researcher explored numerous approaches and analytical strategies in this study, then found the best approach for the design and compilation of evidence during field visits to investigate different factors in SC adoption in SMEs in Pakistan. According to Kreiner et al. (2009), using a qualitative case study strategy and by carrying out detailed face-to-face interviews with open questions, the researchers can better understand what the participants experienced. The researcher supports something in the analysis. This study also confirms Creswell & Creswell's (2017) Statement that the qualitative researcher's methodology is inductive at first, rather than being entirely expressed by the idea or viewpoint of the researcher. Sometimes research questions changed in the middle of the study to better answer the research questions needed to understand the research problem. In response, the pre-study data collection strategy should be modified to accompany new questions (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The researchers pursued a data collection trajectory to establish an ever more comprehensive knowledge of the subject through analysis (SC adoption factors) further down study. The researchers have experimented with details before generalisations; the researcher detailed the studies background and updated questions from tests in the field and the pilot study.

Two research paradigm are described in the next section that shapes this research study.

3.3. Research Paradigm:

Due to their fundamental importance, a researcher must consider leading the method and shaping the study's methodology. This has been argued to profoundly affect the end outcome of the study and concerns of the conclusions (Bazeley, 2013; Mingers, 2003). These terms, such as paradigm, worldview and theoretical purpose, are interchangeably used (Doyle et al., 2009). The philosophy of a particular study is used to mean "paradigm." and is viewed by Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) as

being the research culture, representing a set of beliefs, values and assumptions about nature and conduct of research. Creswell and Poth (2016) define a paradigm as collecting beliefs and practises that drive study. A similar definition is given by Guba and Lincoln (1994), who defined that a paradigm as "a basic set of beliefs that guide action". The research paradigm is mainly influenced by the researchers' perspective of knowledge development (Morgan, 2007).

More recently, authors such as Lincoln, Lynham, and Guba (2011) and Saunders et al. (2016) have stated the fundamental relation between the research paradigm and three concepts: ontology and epistemology (Crotty and Crotty, 1998), and methodology (Neuman & Robson, 2009), as previously discussed.

Choosing an appropriate research paradigm is a crucial task. It is a central and significant part of the research effort, from research design to data analysis to data interpretation. In this regard, it has been suggested that paradigms affect researchers' knowledge, perception of reality, beliefs, and methodologies used in research (Doyle et al., 2009; Morgan, 2007). From this perspective, Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991) suggest that Researchers should be familiar with research paradigms and follow a consistent research methodology. This requires that the underlying philosophical concepts be well understood and that researchers place their study in the context of a selected paradigm (Doyle et al., 2009; Bazeley, 2013).

There are two key competing positions in each definition, called paradigms for research. Researchers have suggested a significant number of research paradigms. Still, those such as Creswell and Creswell (2017), Denzin and Lincoln (2018), Neuman and Robson (2020), and Saunders et al. (2016) suggest they can all be divided into three primary taxonomies; namely interpretivism, positivism and critical paradigms. However, this study took epistemology as a practical philosophy, as discussed previously in this chapter. Therefore, research paradigms are based on epistemological philosophy in the following section and include positivism (reality is external, and there is objectivity and truth) and interpretivism (the world is subjective without permanent truth) (Creswell & Creswell, 2017, p. 6; Oates, 2005, p.282). Denzin and Lincoln (2018) directed that answering questions about subjective epistemology provides a quality interpretation structure that guides the whole study process, including strategies, methods, and analysis. Each of them is defined in the following section.

3.3.1. Positivism Paradigm:

The positive paradigm of social reality exploration is based upon the French philosopher's August Comte (1798–1857) philosophical ideas, who argued that observation and reason represent the

appropriate means of understanding human behaviour. Furthermore, positivism is based on the foundations of naive realism that implies a single truth that is interpreted directly by the human senses; consequently, ontologically, the reality is viewed as objective and fixed. Positivism is based on causal laws and a deterministic interpretation of reality. Its expertise helps researchers to forecast the outcome of natural and human behaviour. Humans are known as rational beings who experience reality regardless of their consciousness. Human behaviour is acquired through experience and observation, driven by external sources that elicit reliable behavioural effects. Positivism implies a dualistic and objectivist view of epistemology. For interference and bias prevention, the researcher should be independent of the analysis's target to obtain accurate, reliable and replicable outcomes. Methodologically, given that reality is considered accurate and precise, it can be measured through empirical, primarily quantitative methods used to verify hypotheses (Guba & Lincoln, 1994).

Similarly, Creswell and Creswell (2017) stated that Post-positivist researchers concentrated on understanding consumer behaviour using highly structured tools to collect measurable evidence, such as Psychological tests and questionnaires with exact written questions. For this qualitative study, therefore, the post-positivist model is not sufficient since the research questions in this study provide accurate information on SMEs and what happens in the organisational business environment. In a study by Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991), they suggested that Positivist studies are focused on the nature of a priori set phenomenon relations and are generally investigated with limited structural methods. These studies are mainly used to test the theory and improve the predictive understanding of phenomena. This research did not use traditional instruments, high-standardised tools or psychiatric assessments to study and assess the phenomena. During the interview process, an open questionnaire was used as an instrument. The research questions were intended to define the unknown s-commerce adoption factors by face-to-face and phone interviews that describe contextual factors of different SMEs to build the theory within the information.

3.3.2. Interpretivism Paradigm:

The theoretical structure of most qualitative studies views the universe as socially built from an interpretivism point of view: Individuals have been perceived and observed in relationships and with wider social systems (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Saunders et al., 2016; Pham, 2018, Pulla and Carter, 2018). According to this paradigm, the essence of the survey is interpretive and naturalistic, and the investigations are structured to explain a real phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2016). In the Interpretive paradigm, scholars are naturalistic and social constructivists, claim that people would like to know in

the world they live and work. In this way, people create subjective interpretations of experiences guided by particular reasons or things. Interpretivism seeks to focus on the participants' opinions and the situation under discussion (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). In this study, the researchers have become interpretive and have spent a good amount of time with owners and other SMEs to understand the studies' phenomena. There are no "correct" or "incorrect" theories in the interpretative paradigm (Abdulkareem et al., 2017). Instead, their "interest" in social constructivists and others who work in the same direction should be monitored. Pham (2018) elaborated that Interpretation research does not predetermine independent dependent variables but concentrates on the difficulty of constructing human interpretation as the circumstances develop. This interpretive approach attempts to clarify the subjective motives for social action and its importance. Interpretivists are not involved in constructing a new theory but in assessing, reviewing, and updating interpretation theories. (Antwi & Hamza, 2015). Further, Pulla and Carter (2018) have claimed that the Interpretivism paradigm is the most productive way of analysing social order that is accomplished through the individual perception of the participants; For instance, interviewing various respondents and reconciling the differences between their participant's responses. Packard (2017) further defined that Interpretivist frequently uses limited groups and detailed observational surveys in social analysis of data collection techniques.

Pulla and Carter (2018) determined that People create definitions when immersed in the environment they perceive. Therefore, interpretivism prefers to use open questions to allow participants to express their views by gathering personal experience on the ground (Pham, 2018). The qualitative interpretative analysis method is mainly inductive. Therefore, researchers establish context from the data gathered in the field. This research is based on an interpretative model without testing or confirming a theory and recommending to SMEs to adopt SC more efficiently.

3.3.3. Reason for Choosing the Interpretative Paradigm:

According to the interpretative paradigm, Useful data can be collected as interpreters use their observations to direct the process of analysis (Chowdhury, 2014; Walsham, 1995). However, Lin (1998) explained that interpretivism scholars investigate the presence or absence of a causal connection and its representation and the sense in which it exists. Consequently, it will lead the researcher to what has happened and how it has happened (Chowdhury, 2014; Lin, 1998).

The interpretive model is considered the most suitable for this analysis because it can produce new insights into an evolving concept in social sciences, a concept studied in current research. Owing to its integration with the world of human activity and its importance, functional knowledge is often justified and needs to be appropriately examined from an interpretative paradigm (Pham, 2018).

Moreover, the research philosophy implemented in this study is focused on knowledge creation through questions, insights and dialogues in which participants and owners of SMEs shared their experiences in interviews. Denzin and Lincoln (2018) provided another explanation for Interpretive approaches to produce detailed accounts of participants' sentiments, viewpoint, and perception, and they interpret the importance of their behaviour.

Concerning the adoption of e-commerce, Thanh & Thanh (2015) showed that interpretative research findings create a specific and profound relationship between information and various communication technologies within SMEs. Studies by Chalhoub-Deville and Deville (2008), and more recently, Rahman (2017), also confirmed that Interpretation techniques are best utilised to explain better SC adoption, its associated requirements, e-commerce availability and use of different ICT devices in SMEs. The research aspect of the analysis was also focused on the interpretative model based on the previous debate and the reasoning for previous experiments. This theoretically supports the study of the interactions of subjects based upon their value.

This research aims to provide the recommendation to SMEs in Pakistan to adopt SC more effectively. To critically examine the current state of adoption of SMEs, both face-to-face and telephone interviews were conducted, along with other data collection techniques such as analysis of documents, websites and observations.

The researcher spent considerable time as an interpreter with owners and other SME staff capturing their thoughts, impressions and comments about technological acceptance and numerous innovations like the SC. The data collected allowed the investigator to understand a condition and the actual overall status of the SMEs engaged in the SC adoption analysis using multiple techniques. Along with support to adopt successful SC and to implement technical applications effectively through local and government agencies. Also, this study focuses on factors in Pakistan that inspire or demotivate SMEs, such as the adoption challenges that influence SC performance and How SC as tech will support these SMEs.

The next stage of the research onion comprises the research type, which is introduced in the next section, following suitable research philosophies and the research paradigm to construct this study.

3.4. Research Types:

Five types of research studies should be formulated to fulfil the research goal (Creswell and Creswell, 2017; Saunders et al., 2016, p. 140), such as descriptive, explanatory, exploratory, deductive and inductive. Each will be discussed in the next section.

3.4.1. Descriptive Study:

Descriptive studies are designed to obtain a detailed summary of incident, individuals or circumstances (Saunders et al., 2016). These type of studies generally have one or two driving questions but are not inspired by structured hypotheses. Since these study styles are mainly aimed at explaining demographic factors from the samples, probabilistic sampling methods, such as simple random sampling, are often required. Qualitative or Quantitative analysis data can be descriptive, but quantitative reports are restricted to frequency distributions and statistics, Such as arithmetic mean (Simons et al., 2018). Therefore, this study is not suitable for qualitative analysis.

This research aims to achieve understanding between owner-managers and other SME participants through an intent sample technique not to define the characteristics of the participants during data collection stages. This encourages the questions to be answered, mainly "what" and "why". Descriptive analysis inquiries are based on descriptive research (Saunders et al., 2016) – "how, when and who", and this significant for the broader view of the phenomenon. Therefore, it was not deemed appropriate for this analysis.

3.4.2. Explanatory Study:

The focus of the descriptive study is to analyse a circumstance or dilemma to understand the relationship between factors. Schupbach (2018) illustrated that Probabilistic samples could be an explanatory analysis prerequisite since the purpose is to generalise the findings to the population in the study. In quantitative research, almost sampling data is statistical. Therefore, an explanatory study requires to test the regression and to assess the validity of the relationship.

On the other hand, the qualitative analysis does not aim to generalise the findings but at evaluating the phenomenon from a whole new perspective to consider and evaluate the phenomenon in the field. According to the qualitative data perspective from the various interactions and experiences of SMEs' top leaders and other employees, it was not deemed appropriate for this research.

3.4.3. Exploratory Study:

The search of new theories poses questions and evaluates phenomena in a new perspective that is unknown and little researched. An exploratory analysis is an ideal way to explain what happens (Saunders et al., 2016). This generally means that little was published on the topic. The sample community and that the researcher intends to listen and establish an interpretation of participants based on what is said (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). If a researcher needs to demonstrate the understanding

of a problem as if they are unaware of the actual existence of the problem, exploratory studies are supportive. A literature search, a group conversation or case studies will launch this exploration. No effort is made to investigate a random sample of a population while an investigation is performed for experimental purposes. Exploratory researchers usually aim for people with experience of a concept or procedure. In addition, exploratory research typically aims to establish hypotheses instead of evaluating them, and knowledge from exploratory studies appears to be qualitative (Sue & Ritter, 2012). Hence, the exploratory analysis was found to be more suitable for this qualitative study. The justification for selecting exploratory studies for this research is that the primary focus of exploratory studies is on "what". Yin (2018), argue that these type of research questions are justifiable by executing an exploratory study.

This study aims to make recommendations by identifying different factors linked to the TOE model that prevent SC's successful adoption. A research methodology focused on exploratory case studies has been adopted (Yin, 2018). In that way, the researcher understood and analysed factors for the adoption of SC in the field with the aid of qualitative data produced from owners, manager, and interaction with other employees. Even though SC adoption has been examined in developed and developing countries, this research analysed it in a particular way to fill the gap and bring new knowledge through a different perception in Pakistan. As seen in the literature review, SMEs have already done multiple studies in developing and developed economies in different sectors. This research mainly focuses on SMEs in the Hospitality and Tourism sector located in two main cities (Islamabad and Rawalpindi) in Pakistan to identify the drivers and challenges faced by SMEs to adopt SC. The most suitable for this analysis was an exploratory approach focused on case studies as a research plan (Yin, 2018). adoption of emerging technologies such as SC in SMEs in Pakistan. As a consequence, a qualitative

3.4.4. Deductive and Inductive:

Deductive reasoning can be defined as *"a study in which a conceptual and theoretical structure is developed and then tested by empirical observation. So, the deductive method is referred to as moving from the general to the particular"* (Collis and Hussey, 2013, p.8). Malhotra and Malhotra (2012, p.197) defined deductive reasoning as *"a form of reasoning in which a conclusion is validly inferred from some premises, and must be true if those premises are true"*. Yin (2018) argued that in the formulation of research questions and objectives, researchers might also use current theory to develop

a framework to help organisations and interpret data. Furthermore, Rahi (2017) argues that the theories and technique developed by the research for testing a hypothesis are called the deductive method.

Inductive reasoning is defined as *"a study in which theory is developed from the observation of empirical reality. So it involves moving from the specific to the general"* (Collis and Hussey, 2013, p.8). Inductive reasoning starts with gathering data and then investigating the following topics, groups or trends (Saunders et al., 2016). One important inductive aspect is that before embarking on research, the researcher should not suggest previous ideas or hypotheses on what they might discover and examine. The theory is generalised to evaluate data and develop new hypotheses by grounded theory (Malhotra et al., 2012).

Saunders et al. (2016) highlighted that studying using an inductive approach is likely to be particularly concerned with the context in which certain events occur. Therefore, it might be more suitable for studying a limited group of subjects than the deductive process. Inductive researchers are most inclined to use qualitative evidence in this tradition and use a range of qualitative approaches to gathering this knowledge to create diverse views of the phenomena (Rahi, 2017).

Thus, the reasoning of the qualitative research method was inductive in this study because the purpose of this study is to make recommendations for SMEs to adopt SC more effectively in Pakistan by identifying the critical success factors. Saunders et al. (2016) found that in an inductive approach, several variations of qualitative research began, using a realistic and evolving research plan to establish a deeper theoretical perspective already present in the literature. Factors linked to SC adoption were not well established in this study among SMEs in developing countries, specifically Pakistan as a developing country. Thus, an inductive method was found to be the most suitable. Table 3.1 demonstrates the rationale behind this study's inductive approach.

Based on the literature, the data was then collected through Skype and telephone interviews, direct observations, and background information provided by the owner, managers and other management staff/employees, an analysis of SME websites, as appropriate. The Skype and telephone interviews lasted between 30 and 65 minutes. Interviews were conducted using an open and guided questionnaire as a study method to consider each SME's level of S-commerce adoption (business objectives). The questions allowed the researcher to manually record the answers of participants and their various points of view, such as the knowledge of owner, managers and employees about SC adoption, their personal experience about using the technological systems, and a detailed description of their associations and

the engagement of the company. For the final study, handwritten notes were then used to provide answers to the research questions.

The study's next step is to clarify the various methods to research as described in the following section of this thesis.

Deductive	Inductive
Scientific principles	Gaining an understanding of the meanings human attach to events
Moving from theory to data	In-depth knowledge of the topic
The collection of quantitative data	The collection of qualitative data
Highly structured approach	More flexible structure to change research emphasis

Table No. 3.1: Summary of Deductive and Inductive Types
Adopted from Saunders et al. (2011)

3.5. Research Methodologies:

The two primary methods of data collection are qualitative and quantitative approaches. A data collection approach is chosen by researchers depending on the nature of their research (Malhotra et al., 2012). Researchers require either one method or another or a mixed type of data collection in some circumstances, representing a mixed-method approach (Saunders et al., 2011). The decision to follow a qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods approach can be based on the theory and the researcher's philosophy (Easterby-Smith et al., 2015). Table 3.2 explains three methodological approaches.

Quantitative	Mixed	Qualitative
Predetermined	Both predetermined and Emerging methods	Emerging methods
Instrument based questions	Both open and closed-ended questions	Open-ended questions
Performance data, Attitude data, Observational data, and Census data	Multiple forms of data drawing on all possibilities	Interview data, Observation data, Document data, and Audio-visual data
Statistical analysis	Statistical and text analysis	Text and image analysis

Statistical interpretation	Across databases interpretation	Themes, patterns interpretation
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Table No. 3.2: Summary of Data Collection Methods

Adopted from Creswell (2003)

3.5.1. Quantitative approach:

Quantitative analysis is based on the processing of numerical knowledge, evaluating, checking and testing the proposed hypotheses (Saunders et al., 2016). Quantitative research is an approach that explores the relationships among variables to test objective hypotheses (Creswell, 2017). These variables may usually be measured with high standard tools (software), statistical tools can be used to analyse such numerical data (Creswell, 2014). In conducting consumer surveys, Quantitative methods were considered useful (Malhotra et al., 2012).

The quantitative analysis approach aims at "how much" and "to what extent" to analyse answers to questions (Rahi, 2017). In simple words, the approach stresses the measurement of the variables existing in the social environment. Furthermore, Creswell (2016) confirmed that quantitative analysis involves the paradigm of positivism, and the paradigm of social science analysis is accompanied by qualitative research.

3.5.2. Qualitative Research Approach:

The qualitative analysis reflects a method to examine and understand the significance of the social or human challenge ascribed to individuals or groups (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The Qualitative is commonly used as a synonym for any data gathering method (e.g. interview) or an analytical approach (e.g. categorisation of insights) (Saunders et al., 2016). A qualitative analysis approach refers to research that produces primary findings not generated through statistical or other measurement methods. Rahi (2017) illustrated that Qualitative research might contribute to primary experimental research such as actions, feelings and emotional state of individuals. Also, its focus on organisational behaviour, social movements, cultural phenomena and interactions. Therefore, Qualitative research does not involve statistics and various realities.

Rahi (2017) stated that Qualitative research is conducted by profound, long-term encounters with naturalistic subjects to analyse people, communities and societies' every day and extraordinary lives on the spot; through findings, interviews and documentation. Creswell & Creswell (2017) also summarised several methods for doing qualitative research, including narrative and phenomenological plans.

Yin (2018) have suggested that the design of case studies requires qualitative approaches. Rahman (2020) observed that Qualitative analysis aims to examine the subjective significance of problems or social production by gathering non-standard primary data and evaluating texts and photographs instead of numbers and figures, incidents or activities. As a result, it highlights that how people in the world make sense. Yin (2018) elaborated that Qualitative analysis has been related to a philosophical understanding, in which researchers have had to understand the subjective and social importance of the observed phenomena.

As mentioned earlier, in the background of Pakistan's SMEs, there are relatively few subjective studies on the acceptance of social commerce. Mostly they are quantitative and apply different research approaches (Hassan et al., 2018; Solangi et al., 2019; Talat et al., 2013). A single study considered a qualitative approach to identify the critical success factors to adopt social commerce from an SME perspective. Therefore, this research will contribute to the lack of literature on social commerce adoption in SMEs in Pakistan and establish deep qualitative knowledge from SMEs perspective. Thus, a qualitative research methodology with the case study selected for this study as the research plan because, Primary data have been gathered to address questions that require detailed explanation (Thomas, 2015).

3.5.3. Reason for Choosing the Qualitative Research Approach:

In this study, the qualitative approach was chosen for different reasons. First, the research was explained by understanding a qualitative nature as an examination of the influence of the embedded heightened understanding of the adopted SC in SMEs. More importantly, to contribute to the current literature, this study aimed to define qualitative factors. As such, the study was intended to produce a complete description with a comprehensive interpretation.

An exploratory qualitative study, In SME, studies the exploration concentrated on "why", "what", and "how" of the phenomena, the result was thus supposed to be flexible. In some cases, research results are more significant if the conclusion is unpredictable. No strong prediction of the outcomes could be assumed in this particular case. Creswell and Poth (2016) propose that theories are needed to describe

the phenomena arising from the observed occurrence in most study cases. A hypothesis, which also consists of the hypotheses or from research questions, is required to predict the outcomes of a study (Pham, 2018). In this analysis, however, no theory was necessary since there were no projected outcomes.

Qualitative research is critically considered best suited for a rich data context to study natural events (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2015). A study can be flexible and contextual with strategic planning. The advantages of qualitative analysis are that it offers numerous information and explanations of variable results (Abdulkareem et al., 2017). The techniques used in qualitative analysis allow scholars to investigate and concentrate on the complexities of exceptional cases and obtain an in-depth understanding of the subject under review (Antwi and Hamza, 2015).

In addition, Denzin and Lincoln (2018) revealed that qualitative research could be categorised as reliable and comprehensive. This highlights the systematic approaches used to collect and interpret data which are flexible and contextual when handled strategically. The qualitative analysis enables collective philosophical problems to be explained, contributing to broad causal conclusions (cause and effect). This research aims to discover the causes of limited SC adoption by SMEs in Pakistan and provide them with a framework to adopt SC more efficiently.

Therefore, to identify the challenging factors to planning the adoption and implementation of social commerce technology in their business model, it was necessary in Pakistan to carry out a qualitative exploratory case study. This was done by qualitative data collection methods based on Skype interviews and telephone interviews, observations, documentation and a comprehensive website analysis capturing participants' various perceptions and opinions.

The next step of analysis in this qualitative interpretative research study would be to analyse the relevant research approach to include information on the critical success factors related to SC adoption by SMEs.

3.6. Research Strategy:

The study techniques for qualitative interpretive research, including the compilation and design of data, have been illustrated by authors (Malhotra et al., 2012; Saunders et al., 2016; Yin, 2018). This author notes that qualitative research can be used to direct the design, compilation, review of the data and to guide the search for secret phenomena through various research techniques (design, imagination, experimental research, research, field study, ethnography, action research, archival knowledge, and case studies).

To clarify the expectations and behaviour of SMEs in social commerce adoption, the approach of this analysis is based on an interpretive model. As part of this qualitative search was chosen, as seen in past sections, for inductive forms and approaches. Yin (2018) found that case studies are frequently used to analyse the significance, secret and origin of the phenomenon examined in social science research. This segment explores how a search method for this research design should be chosen to gather data from multiple sources for a specific case study.

3.6.1. Case Study:

A case study was introduced as a research method in this qualitative study. Robson (2002, p. 178) describes a case study as 'an observational research approach which uses multiple evidence sources to examine a specific contemporary phenomenon in their real-life context.' The case study is of tremendous importance to obtain a rich understanding of the research context and processes (Harrison et al., 2017).

The case study approach is also capable of presenting answers to questions on "why", "what", and "how", which is why case studies in exploratory research are more widely used (Saunders et al., 2016). The case study is the opposite of the laboratory strategy, where testing is carried out in a stable environment. The case study is therefore different from the survey approach. The opportunity to analyse and consider this context is constrained by the number of variables on which data can be gathered when the analysis is performed in context (Harrison et al., 2017). In addition, Ridder (2017) stated that the design of the case study was based on the assumption that the case studied was a typical (concerning the type) case and that a single case could therefore provide an overview of the events and various situations. Kumar (2014) also claimed that the architecture of the case study was built on the premise that the case studied was a standard case and that only one case could provide an overview of the events and different circumstances.

The study of cases has been widely used in social science and has been especially useful in specific fields, such as education, government and social work. However, Yin (2018) confirmed that case studies had been given little recognition among the different study methodologies in social science, considering their long history and commonly use. This is why, as a research approach aimed at exploring the latent causes of social commerce adoption in SMEs in Pakistan, the social constructivist researcher followed a case study.

3.6.1.1. Case Study 1: Company A Profile:

Company A (Hospitality and Tourism industry) was established in 2001 in the financial city Rawalpindi. It is a company with 47 employees that meets the small business classification requirements. The first pilot interview was conducted with the owner and the social media manager of this company. Company A has two branches in two different cities Rawalpindi and Islamabad.

Company A is a family run business, and they are operating two branches in the cities mentioned above. They are looking to expand further within the next two years. They offer 33 different rooms to choose from, with an indoor pool included and a complimentary breakfast. The primary target customers for company A are tourists.

The researcher interviewed the owner and social media manager over Skype. In the interview, it was revealed that the organisation's owner worked hard to adopt new technologies for the organisation. The owner of the restaurant noted that through social platforms, they have responded to so many queries. This technology also enabled them to target their local and international customers. They are also working with other companies, such as tour guides for the northern areas of Pakistan.

Its mission is to provide outstanding lodging facilities and services to their guest. They are mainly focusing on the individual, leisure travel and travelling associated with group tours. Continuous improvement and sustainable development towards more significant achievement is another goal. Their online management system ensures them to deliver daily operations and quality services to their guest with the lowest impact to the environment. They call their management system a backbone of their operations. It provides its staff with a comprehensive set of tools to fulfil its mission effectively. Company A's two branches are considered as average price hotels with easy cancellation and refundable policies. It indicates that they are affordable to both middle and upper-class society, making the Pakistani community the target audience.

3.6.1.1.1. Process and Adoption Stages of Social Commerce:

Decision:

Two significant elements influenced the choice to employ SC in Company A: necessity and personal interest. This was driven from the management hierarchy's bottom up. Personal expertise and enthusiasm for adopting SM were the primary motivators for Company A's initial adoption of SC. "One of us is skilled in SM and proposed we utilize it in the firm," says the CEO. "It's the need; we needed it, so we used SM," the CEO stated.

The speed with which the decision to utilize SM was made was influenced by knowledge awareness. "In fact, when I reviewed some multinational companies' SM accounts, I was astounded by the benefits SC can provide to organizations," the CEO said. I discovered that they use social media for marketing and customer service. 'Why don't we do the same in our company?' I wondered. And now we're here, live on SM."

The CEO highlighted simplicity and ease of use, ease of testing, and accessibility as the primary considerations that influenced the choice to implement SM. He also emphasized the importance of "affordability... SM is less expensive than traditional marketing and advertising media like magazines and newspapers, which is beneficial to the company."

Implementation:

Instagram was extensively used by Company A as a social media tool. "We tried to use Facebook and Twitter, but we found them difficult and less appropriate for us," the marketing manager explained. As the SM account manager, the corporation has given him full control for the SM materials, such as what to post or publish.

"...so many things I have free control over... the images and media," the SM Manager noted, though management did occasionally offer comments and points of view. Since there had never been a dedicated SM Manager before, the post was handed to the IT manager, who had some commercial expertise with SM as well as a personal interest in it. "He is responsible for both SM and IT," the CEO clarified.

SM adoption took place in stages, with insufficient planning at the outset. According to the marketing manager, the company began with simple use: "At first, we had an account and tried Facebook." They gradually improved their SM functions after that. "...one account we attempted in the beginning... he selected several photographs of our products and projects, enhanced them to be utilised on multiple SM platforms, made nice comments, then posted them," the marketing manager explained. Then we tracked how customers interacted with the post to figure out how to get more people to visit."

Performance Evaluation:

"We utilise the amount of followers we have and people's reactions to and interactions with what we publish," the marketing manager said of Company A's use of SM analytics as a gauge of SM

performance. As a result, while evaluating SM success, the corporation looked at the number of 'likes' and 'followers.' They took public interaction into account in this way. When Company A asked customers how they heard about them, many of them said Instagram. "We ask clients whatever social media site brought them to us, and we quantify sales driven by social media," the CEO added.

Performance Improvement:

Company A agreed to devote more time and effort in planning and coordinating more effective SM adoption, including leveraging analytics tools to assist more effective use of SM data and information, in order to improve performance and SM usage.

Another tactic suggested was using Snapchat to acquire more attention and customers. According to the CEO, however, they would have required to recruit a specialized SM Manager to complete this task: "...for example, when Snapchat initially came out, we wanted to get into it, but the time we had here was not useful... it required a devoted person."

However, in order to increase productivity and customer experience, the organization devised a systematic approach of posting on SM that was tailored to each SM platform uniquely. The benefit of this technique was explained by the SM Manager as follows: "Everything has a different method, working with photographs for Instagram or Facebook... I put the logo in the center of the photographs and add a caption. Products are organized by colour, with each colour representing a category of products."

They also began to compile a database of products and photographs. They purchased more modern equipment to implement this, which increased user experience and happiness by producing high-quality SM content. "I started preparing the ground," the SM Manager explained. The photographs were safeguarded.

Other Corporate Functions:

Company A made increased their sales via social media channels, mostly Instagram. "We sell things when customers place orders over WhatsApp or the private comments' function," says the CEO. Because our consumers are young and can't pay online most of the time, paying by cash on delivery

allows us to use SM as a sales point... Cash on delivery is popular because we trust buyers and they trust us."

They also began to compile a database of products and photographs. They purchased more modern equipment to implement this, which increased user experience and happiness by producing high-quality SM content. "I started preparing the ground," the SM Manager explained. The photographs were safeguarded.

Overall, the benefit of SM is that it can be accessed from everywhere in the world as long as there is an internet connection. Interactive communication, such as responding to comments, can take place at any time and from any location on the planet.

"The beautiful thing about SM is that customers may express their comments and queries at any time, and we can answer them whenever and from wherever as long as we have an internet connection," says the SM Manager. As a result, it was widely assumed that SM offered customers with open and direct contact, allowing the company to "go the additional mile." "...it is critical to have SM for efficient direct customer service," the CEO continued.

The corporation only kept positive comments in order to maintain the integrity of SM material and improve the image of the product. Negative comments were removed to protect the company's reputation. "We block non-serious people and nasty remarks if they are repeated; we erase negative comments," the SM Manager added. "We only handle comments regarding the product itself and respond to call us or visit the store."

Advantages of Adoption (Marketing Perspective):

According to the marketing manager, "we perform a marketing campaign on SM before we order the products, to evaluate the market requirement and ensure the products will be sold." "SM assists in marketing and creating brand image and awareness in the market for our products... it is a strong advertising channel," the marketing manager said. "On SM accounts, we can notify clients with deals, new releases, and best sellers faster," according to the SM Manager.

Furthermore, as the marketing manager explained, SM strengthened its brand image in the market by participating in national events: "We use SM accounts to engage in national and religious festivals; we post greetings, prayers, and make offers... sales grow whenever we do this."

Barriers to Adopt SC:

The business's successful use of SM platforms without external assistance was a major motivator for SM adoption. The SM Manager emphasised this, saying, "There's no need for outside help; we can

learn on our own." However, the limited knowledge and lack of formal education on how to use SM effectively limited the company's full use of SM. Overall, SM functions and use were reliant on a single person rather than the company as a whole. The company relied heavily on the SM Manager to carry out all SM activities, and nothing was documented, which could have serious ramifications for the business if the SM Manager left. "Nothing is written... or organised as rules for SM use," the SM Manager affirmed. "If I leave them, they will collapse on SM... since they do not have adequate expertise."

Negative remarks from consumers or SM users on company accounts, meantime, inhibited the company from fully embracing SM, as the CEO pointed out: "If customers say something, it affects others."

Future of SM Adoption:

Company A benefited from the use of SM to boost sales in this scenario. The company went from a traditional retail to a semi-online operation after adopting SM. "SM can be a medium for sales and can replace real stores," the CEO asserted emphatically. "We are thinking of closing the store and concentrate on Instagram." By opening up new prospects, SM adoption shifted Company A's business model. Furthermore, the SM Manager noted how SM celebrities' impact aided business growth by acting as role models for others and helping the organisation attract new customers: "...the support certain SM influencers provide for SMEs on their SM accounts helps us grow."

3.6.1.2. Case Study 2: Company B Profile:

Company B is operating since 2015 with a total of 29 employees. The company's general situation is typical, as most of its clients are local and domestic or independent business owners who frequently visit Islamabad for leisure and business purposes. It serves the best continental food to the Pakistani community in a professional way.

Company B has only one branch in the city of Islamabad. Like Company A, it's a family business too. They have more than 100 dishes to serve to their local, domestic and international community. They serve breakfast, lunch and dinner with the highest quality possible and made of local ingredients.

In the beginning, company B mainly focused on targeting single males and females as they are the decision-makers in the families regarding where to eat. They have set their meals to attract the students and single males within the city and packages for the families too. Their unique continental dishes

attract foreigners too in the capital of Pakistan. Along with the best quality food, they offer free wifi, free and secure car park, card payment, etc., to their customers.

The organisation owner indicated that with the help of social media platforms (Facebook and Twitter), they expanded their business and approached more audience. With less effort and time, they have achieved their desired target. The owner feels that he is like a famous brand in the city and getting requests from customers on social media to open more branches in other cities.

Company B is trying to formalise their department. The owner of the business revealed that social media marketing had given rise to their business. The dramatic rise in the sale is willing to open new departments within the organisation, such as Marketing, Research and Development (R & D). Company B is trying to innovate new things and believe in technology. Therefore they have their menu on tablet devices and online service to deliver the food to their doorstep.

For adequate information and communication, Company B is looking to recruit technical experts to run social media. Being a casual dining restaurant with affordable prices, they are targeting their local customers. Providing fresh, healthy, nutritious, and great tasting food at reasonable prices in a clean, friendly, and convenient environment is their mission. Their accomplished team are striving to ensure that each customer receives professional, friendly and courteous service.

3.6.1.3. Case Study 3: Company C Profile:

The fourth interview was held with a General Manager and ICT executive of Company C. Company C was incorporated in 2015. It has 27 employees in total that meet the small-medium classification requirement. This organisation is located in the central hub of Islamabad.

This organisation is a busy café in the main centre of Islamabad. Thus, it falls into the hospitality sector. They are famous for their coffees, tea, snacks, sandwiches, and sweet products like doughnuts and slices. This café has 50 seating capacity. Company C is doing business differently from its peers. They take pride to serve lovely coffee in the most calming atmosphere with the smell of fresh snacks. It is the first café in Islamabad that offer their customer to book their table through social media. To attract youngsters to the city, they have adopted different social media platforms. They provide a luxurious environment for their customers to feel at home. Young people and university students can come and stay inside the café as long as they want to stay.

In the interview, it was revealed that there was no social commerce trend when they start operating in 2015. Different platforms of social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter were available for fun activities. In 2015, Company C made their social presence on available famous platforms to promote their business activities. It helped them a lot to adopt social commerce.

Company C welcomes all age of customers. There is a separate space for females and families. They claim that their customers are very loyal to them who visit them daily. They have set discount for university students. They also offer a membership scheme; customers can get one cup of free coffee with selected snacks daily. Company C is using different tactics to engage their customers. Once a year they arrange a quiz competition for their customers. Their mission is to serve others better than they serve themselves.

3.6.1.4. Case Study 4: Company D Profile:

Company D started their business in 2016. It was a team of two people at the start and now five people working in this organisation. They are based in the city of Rawalpindi. They offer their service to domestic and international tourists. Their core business to provide service to the tourists. People who live in the south of Pakistan are always keen to visit the northern areas.

Company D offers transport service to tourists from the airport to hotels and hotel to tourists spot along with the guide. They have contract with different hotels, transport companies, restaurants and health & safety units in Islamabad, Gilgit and Hunza (North region of Pakistan).

They take the tourists in the groups to the northern areas for three days to 1 week. They have very affordable packages for single male, females and families. They also work along with the educational institutes to take their students on the trip.

In the skype interview with the owner and ICT managing director, it was noted that a team of 5 are in their early 30s and they all are fully dedicated to their job. The owner mentioned that in the peak season they recruit temporary staff on the contract.

Company D rely on social commerce and social media platforms. They run paid ad on social media channels and approach their customers more strategically. Company D taking full advantage of social media. They have more than 10K followers and almost 2.5K reviews on social media. Their team of 5 are very active on social media platforms. They respond to their customers instantly and update their pages by adding pictures and content daily.

Currently, the company is operating from Islamabad, but they are very motivated to open more locations within the country. They classified their customers into three categories, family and youngsters, school/college and university student and corporate sectors for their away days in the northern areas. Company D has various customers and adds extensive effort to their advertisement and marketing to approach more customers and expand their business.

Company D is benefited from its location and their skilled people within the organisation. They feel they do not have much competition in the region, as many companies offer the same service.

3.6.1.5. Case study 5: Company E Profile:

Company E was established in 2010 and had 15 employees. This company started their small operation with ten rooms and recently expanded to 25 rooms with different categories based on Rawalpindi. They approached the local and international tourist coming from different places. They also aim to provide the best room service. Hence, have a lot of choices available for their customers.

The hotel owner took the initiative to adopt different social media channels to promote their business locally and internationally. It was revealed that they created social media pages for marketing purposes too. Company E wanted to target their audience more efficiently. Hence, they outsourced the project. During the interview with the owner and the manager, it was revealed that the SC project was handed over to the IT Vendor due to a shortage of technical staff. At the same time, they acquired hardware devices such as smartphones and high tech desktops to answer customer queries in time. They also highlighted the influential factors such as the role of leadership, financial capabilities and role of the government.

The owner of company E indicated that the whole project carried out by the vendor. The technical aspect of social commerce technology was the main challenge for them. They mainly focus on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter but want to expand their social media services to other applications.

3.6.1.6. Case Study 6: Company F Profile:

Company F is a catering company based in the busy spot of Rawalpindi. They are located in the middle of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. It's a family run business, established in 2004. They have 22 employees, including the managers.

Company F provides the catering service for different events such as birthday parties, weddings, corporate events, funerals, other religious gatherings, etc. Company F can cook catering food from 50 to 10,000 people. They aim to open more branches in other vibrant cities of Pakistan.

In 2017, company F joined the social media pages to target their audience and attract more customers by offering different packages through social media. They joined the most popular social media applications such as Facebook and Instagram. Within a month, they have got 5K likes. The owner of the business revealed that SC technology could boost the business.

They focused on their core business activities and outsourced the technology adoption to the marketing agency. Company E worked hard along with the marketing agency, and it was found that they post the content on their social media pages daily. It helped them to engage their customers and get their trust.

3.6.1.7. Case Study 7: Company G Profile:

Company G operates as a hotel in Islamabad. It has 31 employees thus it meet the definition of SMEs in Pakistan. Company G was established in 2012. They have 48 luxurious rooms of 6 types for the customers. All rooms are equipped with air condition and flat TV screen fitted in the rooms.

They have different services for their customers such as free breakfast, pick and drop service to and from airport, swimming pool etc.

During the skype interview with the Social media managing director, it was noted that company G opted in for the SC technology in 2017. Their initial plan was to introduce themselves on social media and let their customer know about their services. They recruited the skilled people for their organization to carry the adoption process. They provided the fast and reliable internet service, desktop computers, laser printers for the dedicated team.

It was revealed that customer in Pakistan does not trust on online buying. Therefore, they are reluctant to pay online. Different strategies were adopted to overcome this challenge. The more successful strategy was on arrival payment. Also, customer can book online with 100% free cancellation if they already paid online. It assisted the organization to get the customer trust in very less time. Company G gave their staff decision power regarding the ICTs activities and there was always online support for the customers. The key challenge was for them to recruit the skilled people for the organization.

Company G blame to government educational system. As most of the graduates from universities were not updated technology such as social commerce technology. Therefore, company G has to go through by long recruitment process. It was also indicated that shortage of skilled people is biggest impediment for the SMEs in Pakistan.

3.6.2. Reason for choosing Case Study Research:

Ridder (2017) claimed a critical insight that case studies can explore an emerging hypothesis. A well-constructed case study approach may also test an established hypothesis and offer a basis for new questions. Furthermore, case studies offer rich evidence within a given context, which offers a detailed understanding of participants' perspective (Saunders et al., 2016).

There is no exact tool to measure the optimal number of cases to be investigated to allow for accurate analysis (Ridder, 2017). Several researchers indicated that case studies, requiring various degrees of study, can cover single or multiple cases (Harrison et al., 2017). However, generally, the view is that the adequate degree of the interpretation of the relevant results is often fundamentally based on the representativeness of the case(s) examined in detail and on the level of comprehensive data analysis carried out on such cases, rather than on the number of cases reviewed.

Stake (2013), on the other hand, asserts, remarkably, that the purpose of the case study is to be unique. The fundamental rule is that the study's interpretation is to offer distinct concepts to different individuals. Readers of different perspectives may then draw different conclusions from the same scenario. Overall, the fundamental interest of this method is to produce thoughtful information based on the facts of the case study, which can be used as a reference for achieving new data.

This study aims to explore the factors that influence the adoption of e-commerce in SMEs and provide answers to research questions through the conceptual framework for in-depth analysis. This study has demonstrated the need for a research strategy to explore the problem and answer qualitative research questions "How" and "Why". As a result, this research followed a case study strategy after choosing an interpretative paradigm to uncover the hidden factors behind the adoption of e-commerce by SMEs, mainly in the context of a developing economy

The use of the case study strategy supported the importance of this research because case studies are deemed more compelling for SME owner-managers than analytical discussions (Bush, 2016). Studies without a qualitative dimension should not be used as a justification for making recommendations or advising policy maker or owner-managers (Moen and Middelthon, 2015). Ponelis (2015) highlighted that case study also support making a contribution that research on the use of new technologies in small and medium-sized businesses. Yin (2018) further confirmed that when the phenomenon examined fulfil the criteria of weak and highly complex technical expertise, qualitative analysis in the context of a case study should be considered.

Adopting social commerce is the innovation phenomenon in SMEs in developing countries such as Pakistan, the best tool for information and communication technology. Therefore, it is not alarming that most of the previously conducted studies are informative and apply to numerous fields and industries. The case study strategy is the best option to study determinants relevant to social commerce research because the information system is essential to s-commerce. Therefore, the case study as a research strategy is the most ideal for this form of social commerce study.

Nakayama and Wan (2019) argued that cultural differences between economies in the adoption of social commerce are significant because diversity directly affects e-commerce applications. Cultural differences often present a big challenge for emerging economies, such as Pakistan, to follow diverse ideas, models and systems both for developed economies and developing economies. This, in essence, poses more concerns about the subject's phenomenon, which, as part of the analysis approach, should be discussed.

3.6.3. Overview of Singular or Multiple Case Study:

For the phenomenon mentioned above, case studies may be single or many (Yin, 2018). According to Mesec (1998, p. 384), in multiple case studies, every case is analysed as if it were a single trial and then applied to the other cases. The research of each subsequent case is based on the information obtained by the review of prior cases, adding that where a particular case is a critical or severe or special case, it is often used. Conversely, it is possible to pick a single case because it is standard or allows the researcher the chance to look in depth by visiting their website and social media pages and examine a phenomenon that few people have taken into account.

Multiple case studies have been used in this study. Yin (2018) said one case is frequently used to be the critical case or, instead, the extreme case or single case, which in this study was not the case. A technique for case studies may include many cases, i.e. more than one case. The basis for the use of multiple cases depends on whether the outcomes from the first case are presented in other cases and whether related observations are expected (Yin, 2018). He further argues that multiple case studies could be preferable to a single case study, especially when addressing more general outcomes.

By taking all of the above arguments into consideration, seven cases were chosen for this particular research. Based on SMEs in the hospitality and tourism industry in Pakistan, the selected number was deemed appropriate for the inquiry (detailed descriptions of the sample and the criteria for selecting the cases are provided in the next section). This enhanced external legitimacy provided compelling evidence and allowed comparisons of cases. Multiple case studies also help to improve research positions (Saunders et al., 2016). Yin (2018) further supported this statement and illustrated that evidence from multiple case study is always more valid. It was also expected that the investigation would include an analysis, by in-depth interrogation, of the actual context of the subject area. Therefore, a comprehensive explanation and summary will be produced as an exploratory study. There is also a common opinion that the multiple case analysis is more rigorous.

3.6.4. Selection of Participants:

A small participant sample needs solid qualitative analysis to understand each situation better, investigate and examine the topic studied by concentrating on defining various meanings about the problems studied, and collect data on unspecified areas; rather than being generalised with larger populations (Kumar, 2014). As this research is a qualitative one, the sample size chosen is small and not representative or suited to the research objective. The sample includes 7 SMEs in Pakistan in both the Hospitality and Tourism industry.

In addition, the current data processing process continued until the data became saturated. Cypress (2017) stated that the data could be saturated as data is completed and repeated by participants. The gathered data can provide a full explanation and an interpretation of the phenomena under analysis. In addition, the counting of answers determines how many participants discussed the same point "misses the point of qualitative analysis" (p.1174). The consistency and outcomes of the participants' answers are essential in the qualitative study rather than the number of participants (Kumar, 2014).

In quantitative research, there are multiple sampling strategies, and they can be categorised as follows:

- Random/probability sampling design,
- Non-random/non-probability sampling design, and
- Mixed sampling design.

However, by introducing non-probability sampling plans, qualitative analysis sampling can be done:

- Purposive/judgmental sampling,
- Expert sampling,
- Accidental sampling, and
- Snowball sampling.

The sample size – which can be adjusted before gathering information or not – depends on the resources and time available and the research objectives. It is also calculated based on theoretical saturation (the point in the data collection when the new data no longer provides additional information

to the research questions). Purposive sampling can also be beneficial, and it has been used in all the elements of this study's data collection and data analysis.

Erika et al. (2016) have endorsed purposive sampling; they argue that purposive sampling or decision is one of the most common techniques of the qualitative sample to locate and pick case-rich information to use limited resources more efficiently. Yin (2018) also clarified the principle of purposive sampling, which states that the researchers' criteria are critical in researching who can provide information to accomplish its objectives. Therefore, the researcher used a purposive sampling approach to invite owners and other related SME employees to participate in the study. The participants were chosen based on their expertise in social commerce and the deployment and use of ICT infrastructure units.

This research was not meant to generalise the findings but rather to clarify the natural growth and adoption of social commerce in SMEs. In particular: how and why SMEs evolve technology and SC. A total of seven cases have therefore been chosen for this review.

At the initial stage, SMEDA provided a list of SMEs (with contact details). Telephone calls were made to 24 SMEs listed as fulfilling requirements for this analysis to verify the presence of the organisations and gain permission to participate in the study using the contact information. In this regard, A membership request was eventually requested by a telephone call to the owners to the degree to which authorisations were requested. The objectives of the study and the reasons for the requested participation were briefly mentioned. It also included obtaining authorisation to speak to other related staff members as needed.

This request produced a response rate of almost 29% and contributed to the final sample of seven organisations. In Pakistani cities such as Islamabad, Rawalpindi, Peshawar, Lahore and Karachi, the offices of the established SMEs were located.

The researchers made a telephone appointment with owners, managers and other staff familiar with Social Commerce and ICT-related technologies for Skype/telephone interviews. The researcher has looked for additional tools such as website, social media page, social media presence, online reports of the organisations to understand better. An additional condition in the selection process included that organisations must have social media presence to give the researcher an insight into the site's contents, an essential tool in SC interactions for this analysis.

Although the permission for the interview was granted over the telephone, consent forms were also signed via email to include a paper record before the interviews. Participants also collected reports on the interview length, the interview notes and specifics that were manually recorded in a journal and written transcription notes. It's interesting to remember that many owners-leaders did not want to engage due to their busy lives, which was the key reason for not participating. The interview lasted overall from 30 to 65 minutes. It was agreed that telephone interviews could be carried out to collect further information if more information was necessary. Finally, all participants were told that they could withdraw from the study during the data collection process at any time. Both participants were further clarified that the interview results would not be released to any other third party and would only be used for the analysis.

3.7. Data Collection Procedure:

The research center focuses on methods for data processing and analysis. This section includes information on methods for data collection and the analysis tools for collecting information to address research questions to achieve the aim and objective of this study.

3.7.1. Interview Procedure:

An interview as a research method to collect data was used during this research process, while an interview form was selected as a semi-structured interview. The first part of this segment addresses the interview as an approach to data collection and describes its significance for this study process. Details of the selection of semi-structured interviews as the instrument type used are given in the second half of this section.

One of the most important sources of evidence for gathering data is the interview in the case study research. In particular, interviews could benefit by offering interpretations (i.e. "how" and "why") of significant events and concepts that represent participants' relativistic viewpoints (Yin, 2018). An interview is a traditional tool used to obtain knowledge from individuals. There are several different meanings of interviews, but interactions between two or more individuals with a specific goal necessarily include a person, whether face-to-face or not (Kumar, 2014). Research interviews are planned conversations between two or more people (Saunders et al., 2016, p. 388), which demand an interviewer to develop an excellent relationship to open questions that the interviewee wants to respond to care and address accordingly. Since this study aims to obtain a good deal of information on the factors affecting the adoption of social commerce, interviews are thought to be the best research

method to collect data from research topics in SMEs in Pakistan. Since evaluating the interview as a guide for analysis, the next step was to determine how the interview approach should be taken. Although there are numerous methods for performing interviews, the segment will now address the particular form of interview used during this analysis stage.

Interviews can be organised, structured, semi-structured or unstructured, as mentioned next. Semi-structured and unstructured interviews are commonly used in qualitative analysis, as the structured approach often provides quantitative data (Wethington et al., 2015). Semi-structured interviews are probably the most commonly used in the two qualitative interview approaches (Kallio et al., 2016). Based on his future benefits, the study's data collection methodology was selected as the semi-structured interview method.

3.7.2. Reason for choosing Semi-Structured Interview:

This decision is justified for several reasons. Firstly, the researchers can defuse the problem of analysis better and obtain rich knowledge about the adoption of social commerce by SMEs. This approach provides researchers with an ability to build their thoughts on the phenomenon of research, according to (Saunders et al., 2016). It helps researchers analyse the participants' perspectives (Kallio et al., 2016) and investigate both personal and social problems in depth (Wethington et al., 2015). The semi-structured methodology also encourages the researcher to use a guide to interview with a predetermined list of open-ended questions (Wethington et al., 2015). Therefore, it provides a high degree of flexibility and is helpful for the researcher in exploring the views of participants about the main issues relevant to the adoption of social commerce.

Secondly, a predetermined list of open-ended questions helps the researcher identify new possible problems relating to the study phenomenon through semi-structured interviews (Kallio et al., 2016). For instance, Galletta (2013) commented that the researchers could use questions from the experiments to ask additional questions to explain specific concerns presented during the interview. As a result, semi-structured interviews allow the space for improvisation rather than the minimal script queries, as in structured interviews (Wethington et al., 2015).

3.7.3. Semi Structure interview:

A semi-structured interview is a flexible meeting at which the interviewer does not strictly follow a formal list of questions. Still, rather he understands the opinions of respondents in depth. The order of

questions can also rely on the discussion flow to explore research questions, and the aims of the phenomenon studied (Saunders et al., 2016). Semi-structured interviews provide more open questions and encourage open conversations with the respondent rather than simplistic questions and answers (Doyle, 2017). The researchers may refocus their questions or ask for more specific details in such interviews as something exciting or new occurs. Although the interviews result in differences, they have a list of subjects or divisions and may have several main problems. Therefore, semi-structured interviews are recorded individually (Saunders et al., 2016).

In semi-structured and in-depth interviews, the qualitative researcher focuses more on face-to-face interactions. This thesis is focused on an exploratory study of interpretative epistemology with an exploratory aspect. The qualitative research design of the study has been based on semi-structured interviews. This design was seen as recognising the importance of the different SME participants to the different factors involved with social commerce adoption.

In particular, the primary purpose of this strategy is to gain detailed information from the participants, which can be used as a guide to achieving new outcomes. In the light of all the arguments for this analysis, separate groups of participants were chosen for each SME because they felt that this should be effective for the investigation. The participants were chosen according to the corresponding parameters provided by SMEs in the Hospitality and Tourism sector that used or started to implement/adopt social commerce in their companies. For interview purposes, the participants were classified at three levels of management: the director, the manager and the person with SM/SC adoption experience in the business (SM Manager).

3.7.3.1 The Participating SMEs:

In the first phase of this research, a qualitative study, the characteristics of the participating SMEs are covered in this section. The below-mentioned table gives an overview of the organisations that participated in this round of the study.

No	Job Role	Organization's Size	Educational Background	No of years in the Job role
SME01	Owner	47	BA Hons	21
	Social Media Manager	47	Bachelors in Networking and security	3
SME02	Owner	29	Bachelor of Computer Science	3
SME03	Social Media Manager	27	Network Engineer	1.5
	General Manager	27	Graduation in Law	5
SME04	ICT Managing Director	5	B.Com	5
	Owner	5	MBA	5
SME05	Manager	15	MBA	7
	Owner	15	MSc	11
SME06	Owner	22	FSc	10
	Social Media Manager	22	B.com	07
SME07	Social Media Managing Director	31	MBA	09

Table No. 3.3: List of the Participating SMEs

3.7.4. Number of Interviews:

The number of essential interviews is based on the organisation's size, the phenomena investigated, the degree, and the time available (Pan & Jang, 2008). However, less than 15 interviews (Baškarada, 2014) are not considered enough. Similarly, Creswell and Creswell (2016) have reported that 16 participants are estimated to have complete, accurate details. However, some researchers accepted that in-depth interviews between 10 and 15 are enough (Baker & Edwards, 2012; Guest et al., 2006).

The researchers directly or telephone interviews with the subjects in qualitative research or take part in a focus group. Thus, 12 in-depth semi-structured telephone interviews (both in pilot studies and then telephony interviews) were performed in seven SMEs for information from owners, managers and other personnel. This qualitative case study was conducted in seven SMEs. Further details are given below:

S. No	SMEs	Total Interviews	Participants
1	SME001	2	Owner, Social Media Manager
2	SME002	1	Owner

Table No. 3.4: Pilot Study Information

In the first phase, the pilot study included semi-structured interviews through telephones. A total of 3 non-formal (two SMEs) telephone interviews took place, and general information was gathered about the current status of social commerce in their organisation, their information technology structure and other problems relevant to their ICT infrastructure units. The researcher manually wrote all the interview material for pilot analysis.

Following the pilot telephone interviews, an open questionnaire was used to perform a total of 12 semi-structured, in-depth telephonic interviews were taken. Two or three participants of each of the seven SMEs, such as Owners, managers and other workers familiar with technology concerns, participated. Galvin (2015) recommends that it be a beneficial tool to interview different people for different points of view. The opinions of senior officers should not be given greater weight than those at lower levels in all the related parts of the company where necessary (Ridder, 2017).

S.No	SMEs	Total Interviews	Participants
1	SME001	2	Owner, Social Media Manager
2	SME002	1	Technical Project Manager
3	SME003	2	General Manager, Social Media Manager
4	SME004	2	Owner, ICT Managing Director
5	SME005	2	Owner, Social Media Analyst
6	SME006	2	Owner, Social media Manager
7	SME007	1	Social Media Managing Director
Total Interviews		12	12 Contributors

Table No. 3.5: Participants Information List

3.7.5. Other Tools:

Another critical approach to the collection of data in a qualitative case study is observation. It is a purposeful, systemic and selective way of looking at an interaction or phenomenon and listening to it (Kumar, 2014). Because a case study is most likely in the natural environment of the case, qualitative investigators create the opportunity for direct observations (Yin, 2018). Galvin (2015) explained the qualitative direct observation method and how it differs in several ways from participant observation.

First, a direct observer does not try to participate in the context and tries to be as discreet as possible not to restrict observations. Second, direct observation suggests a more detached perspective where the researcher attempts to find the phenomena under study via observation more than participation. Technology can be a valuable part of direct observation. For example, the observer can record the phenomenon in a movie or observe behind unidirectional mirrors. Third, direct observation tends to be more focused than participant observation. The researcher observes sampled situations or people instead of trying to delve into the context as a whole. Finally, direct observation tends not to take as long as participant observation. As in the case of semi-structured Skype interviews; online visits to website and social media pages were made on this occasion for better understanding. Still, the

interviews were used as the primary source of data collection. Nevertheless, as noted by Mayer (2001), the researcher has to make many choices by making observations, especially on the type of observation, the capture time, the number of observations to be made and observations to observe.

The motivational degree was also considered for selecting particular guidance in using technology and recognising the social commerce environment within the organisation. In the economic systems of different SMEs, the lack of social commerce activities is further noted. Any primary informants, including workers at a lower level and other team members, did not know much about social commerce or its developments. Many of those workers required information and expertise about the use and contents of the new ICT infrastructure devices.

Documentary information is a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating printed and electronic documents (computerised and transmitted over the internet). Like other analytical methods of qualitative research, documentary information requires data that can be examined and interpreted for meaning, understanding and empirical knowledge (Rapley, 2007; Strauss & Corbin, 2008). The documents contain text (words) and images that have been recorded without the intervention of a researcher. In this study, Yin (2018), and earlier Mayer (2001), were used to gather in-depth information from various organisations.

In this study, relevant documents were available on specific issues, but it was impossible to gain access to all the documents requested. In some cases, documents were lost or shredded, but in this study, several data sources were considered:

- Organisation memoranda concerning the terms of the commercial contract and other legal details were analysed.
- Future implementation agendas and technology announcements discussed in Reports on upcoming technology events, such as conference publications and technology adoption seminars, were also assessed.
- Organisational hierarchy, administrative documents, business proposals, technology improvement plans, and internal progress reports.

- Case studies on formal technology adoption, including ICT infrastructure units and other technology-related implementation and development reports evaluated in the organisations' business environment.

These and other types of documentation were all increasingly available through internet searches and organisational websites such as company information, mission, goals and future development plans, and statistical reports on organisational development provided by SMEDA and other local institutes, including the (RCCs and the SBP). The researcher in this study was authorised (by the organisation's management) only to use the documents in the premises of the case study organisations due to the confidentiality of the documents.

3.8. Research Instrument:

This study is interpretative by nature, using 7 case studies in a qualitative research format. As a qualitative researcher, evidence was obtained by reviewing records, analysing behaviours, and interviewing participants using an open questionnaire as a research tool. Data recording was performed using a case study technique (Yin, 2018). A transparent questionnaire – led by the interview – was used to ensure that the main discussion points of the dialogue were not omitted. In the case of an interview, the interviewer reported the responses, either in whole or in the form of a detailed description. As noted above, the interview lasted from 30 and 65 minutes. The timescale was contingent on the environment and the respondent's capacity and desire to include knowledge on social-commerce phenomena within their organisation. This included influences and obstacles as this was the primary knowledge to be collected to meet the research goals of this report.

3.8.1. Pilot Study:

After the survey tool was developed, a small group of volunteers had to perform the survey before publication for the final target respondents. In any research (Creswell & Creswell 2017), the pilot study is considered a critical factor, along with a helpful exercise to recognise possible problems.

The piloting and refinement of the test tool based on the findings achieved some unique advantages. Firstly, the survey instrument efficiency improved (Kumar, 2014), calculating errors reduced and design problems were resolved (Merolli et al., 2014). It was also helpful to assess the sample's reliability and gain input on whether the problems relating to the study phenomenon were sufficiently answered. Furthermore, since this method has been designed and disseminated via an online tool, it is critical to monitor the online survey reliability when viewed through various browsers and devices.

The piloting was also key to refining questions to improve the accuracy of the terminology used and minimise questions' uncertainty before circulating it to the complete sample (Jahanmir and Lages, 2016). Similarly, pre-testing questions made it possible to understand better the study, which is a matter of relevance to the chances that a successful response rate will be achieved.

Three participants were chosen out of two SEMs for the Skype pre-test. An open-ended questionnaire was sent to these participants (Company A and Company B as presented in Table No. 3.6). This was meant to qualitatively examine participants' viewpoints on s-commerce adoption in their organisations. Participants were urged to identify multiple s-commerce challenges and problems in their SMEs and externally assess the relevance of the questionnaire. On top of it, all the business managers' prior Social commerce experience has been chosen, with a cumulative interview time varying between 30 to 45 minutes. Handwritten notes documented the interviews were taken. The final questionnaire was prepared and conducted by their responses.

The first interview was held with the hotel's owner and social media manager (Company A), based in Pakistan, Islamabad. It has 47 employees that follow the definition of SMEs.

Both of the participants have a considerable working expertise in small to medium-sized businesses. During the pilot interviews, the researcher could assess the significance of the questions asked. Following the interview, the researcher checked the responses to ensure that the questions were asked correctly and that adequate detail was gathered during the pilot test. The critical barriers to SC adoption in the company were identified as

- SC familiarity
- Role of leadership
- Financial capabilities
- Lack of ICT knowledge
- Government role

The second Skype interview took place in the famous city of Pakistan, Rawalpindi, an organisation called Company B. This organisation has 29 employees. The skype interview was conducted with the restaurant owner to get the information about the SC adoption. After the pilot interview, it was revealed that barriers affecting SC adoption in SMEs are following;

- Role of Consultant (Vendor)

- Energy crises

NO	Organisation Name	No. of participants	Total Employees	Role of interviewee	Educational background
1	Company A	2	43	Owner & Social Media Manager	BA Hons & Bachelors in Networking and security
3	Company B	1	29	Owner	Bachelor of computer science (BCS)

Table No. 3.6: Pilot Study

The researcher obtained outstanding input on the research questions from the pilot project, and as a result of the comprehensive responses, the validity of the interview questions was improved. Relationships were developed during skype pilot interviews with the different participants, allowing the researcher to become acquainted with each organisation, making it easier to join the organisation for final interviews.

3.9. Data Analysis:

Data were obtained from 7 SMEs from the Hospitality and Tourism Industry in Pakistan's two largest cities (Islamabad and Rawalpindi) using semi-structured interviews. This section aims to summaries and analyses the responses of the participants who were interviewed. The interviews were exploratory in nature to get a better understanding of the challenges that SMEs face in Pakistan to adopt social commerce.

Furthermore, the exploratory stage was designed to show the key factors that influence SMEs' intention to adopt SC, based on the experiences and perspectives of SMEs' owner-managers. This chapter is split into three major parts for easy comprehension.

- Section 3.9.1 provides a summary of the thematic analysis (TA) as a method for analyzing data.
- The following section, 3.9.1.1, gives a more comprehensive explanation of the method used to create categories and themes from the interview results.
- Table 3.3 presents an overview of the profiles of the SMEs and their owner-managers who took part in the interview process.

3.9.1. Data Analysis Procedure and Thematic Analysis Technique:

Since the qualitative researcher in this analysis had to consider the abstract and socially constructed interpretations conveyed by the participants in this research on social commerce as a phenomenon under study, it was combined with an interpretative theory. The most complex and least codified aspect of the case study method has been qualitative research (Sundler et al., 2019). The qualitative researcher seeks to explain and analyse phenomena relating to the context of the participant's position by analyzing the results (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018).

Via semi-structured interviews with SME owner-managers, the first phase of this research aimed to identify the different steps of Pakistani SMEs must go through during the Social Commerce adoption process.

The qualitative data in this analysis were analyzed using the NVivo 9 program by the researcher. However, it was later decided to use personal data processing to assign emails, written messages, and photographs more meaning (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). To compare the problems posed by an integrated study, which showed the significance of the data considered by (Colorafi and Evans; 2016). Since the NVivo 9 program did not analyses the various stories collected during the interviews iteratively, this analysis used thematic analysis (TA). As a result, each case was examined independently, and the conclusions contrasted. Before explaining the data analysis process, this is necessary first to summarise the TA methodology, describe the benefits, and discuss how it was applied at this stage of the study.

It's "not an easy or fast job" to analyse qualitative analysis results (Terry et al., 2017). In reality, unlike quantitative research, the qualitative research method generates a vast and overwhelming quantity of raw data (transcripts and notes) (Vaismoradi et al., 2016), making the best of it nuanced, enigmatic, time-consuming, and the labour-intensive component of the qualitative research phase (Cresswell, 2016; Vaismoradi et al., 2016). It is a comprehensive and iterative process that should begin as early as possible in the data collection process (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). As a result, the data must be 'organised logically' to achieve a deeper interpretation (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017).

Narrative analysis, discourse analysis, semiotic analysis, material analysis, and TA are only a few of the data analysis approaches used to analyse qualitative studies (Braun et al., 2014; Liamputtong, 2009). Content analysis (CA) and text analysis (TA) are two of the most often used qualitative evaluation techniques in various fields. There are some parallels and distinctions between the two methods (Braun et al., 2014; Vaismoradi et al., 2016). One of the significant distinctions is that Content Analysis outcomes are more quantitative, while TA outcomes are more concerned with defining and expressing both overt and implicit concepts (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). CA is partly quantitative because it requires categorising data and then calculating the frequency of occurrences within the acquired data (Krippendorff, 2018). TA is being used to analyse the qualitative data obtained using a semi-structured interview instrument in step one of the current analysis.

TA is a tool for finding, analysing, and documenting trends (themes) within records (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Boyatzis (1998) defines it as a method for encoding qualitative data that helps researchers organise, process, and analyse the content. It enables researchers to perceive and make sense of seemingly unconnected facts and information (Vaismoradi et al., 2016). The researcher may also use TA to sense the data's themes, create codes, and view the data and themes in the light of the theory (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). It offers a rich collection of observations by concentrating on observable themes in fragments of texts (e.g. interview scripts) (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). It assists the researcher in gaining deep insights into dynamic analysis phenomena and uncovering important trends in the results (Herzog et al., 2019).

TA is a commonly used qualitative data analysis tool in qualitative research by researchers in a variety of disciplines, as well as the IS sector (Braun et al., 2014; Braun and Clarke, 2006; Grbich, 2012; Vaismoradi et al., 2013; Vaismoradi et al., 2016). Recently many researchers (Chen et al., 2020; Perannagari and Chakrabarti, 2019; Radzi et al., 2019) used the TA method to analyse qualitative interview data collected to explore the factors affecting technology adoption different sectors. In addition, Johnston et al. 2013 used the TA approach to investigate factors influencing open source software adoption in South Africa. Alsanea (2015) used the TA approach to investigate factors impacting cloud computing adoption in Saudi Arabia.

For several factors, the TA method was selected to support the data analysis in this research, mainly because of the advantages found by several researchers when using TA to analyse qualitative data when opposed to other possible methods (Boyatzis, 1998; Braun et al., 2014; Guest et al., 2011). Therefore, this is, first and foremost, a versatile strategy. It could be applied to various empirical problems, analytical structures, and data sets of various types, small and large. According to Braun et

al. 2014, TA allows the researcher to address various types of research questions, including those relevant to identifying influencing factors, as in this research.

Secondly, unlike other approaches to data processing, TA is not limited to a particular category of qualitative data and can therefore be applied to a wide range of data collection instruments (e.g. interviews, focus groups, qualitative surveys). As previously stated, the semi-structured interview is used as a data collection tool in this study process, resulting in textual data for which TA has been defined as an appropriate data processing technique (Guest et al., 2011). Thirdly, unlike other methods, TA does not require much effort to learn because it is convenient and straightforward. Fourth, for inexperienced scholars, TA is a simple methodological technique. Last but not least, it allows for simple data sorting, displays data themes/patterns, and detects repetitive information across instances (Alhojailan, 2012).

As a result, it is expected that TA will allow the researcher to identify, classify, and analyse what the research subjects (SME's owner-managers) believe influences social commerce adoption in Pakistani SMEs in Hospitality and Tourism industry. In general, TA is a valuable method for identifying and reducing data related to previously determined patterns/themes (Abdullah et al., 2012) and making sense of the interview data (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). After deciding to use TA to analyse the interview data gathered in phase one of this report, the next move is to figure out what kind of TA to use.

In terms of types of TA, there are three types: inductive, deductive, and hybrid (Alhojailan, 2012). Simply placed, the forms are described as the theme's source (s). Two fundamental origins of themes were established by Braun and Clarke (2006) and Ryan and Bernard (2003): (i) evidence and (ii) the investigator's previous theoretical knowledge of the phenomena under investigation. Inductive analysis generates categories and themes from the data, while deductive analysis categorises the study data using a logically derived/pre-defined collection of themes (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). A third approach is a hybrid approach that combines inductive and deductive methodologies to analyse research findings. (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

Data were analysed using a two-step method in this study based on inductive reasoning. Initial codes for each organisation were created after reading the transcripts of each organisation. For each case study, this process was replicated, and the coded data were clustered and separated into various themes and sub-themes. The firm study was built to define latent structural reasons for accepting social commerce in each organisation to provide answers to important research questions. These variables were then analysed and categorised using the TOE model (Torntzaky and Fleischer, 1990). The framework was then supplemented with an additional human contextual element to emphasise the importance of owner-managers and management in implementing social commerce.

3.9.1.1. Data Condensation:

In qualitative data analysis, data condensation is the first step. It is a method of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting, and converting evidence found in written field reports, interview transcripts, papers, and other observational materials (Miles et al., 2014) to determine which segment tags better summarise a solid piece of information and which changing narrative to tell from the original data.

The researcher used field notes, paper summaries, diary notes, and scripts to highlight what participants had said about social commerce and its functions in the organisations during the first phase of this analysis, which included interviews with organisations. The notes and transcripts were checked several times to identify any problems or experiences that may be significant. This approach is used to familiarise the researcher with the data gathered and begin organising and structuring the data (Easterby-Smith et al., 1991). It also aids comprehension of the various themes identified by the literature (Saunders et al., 2016).

The next step was to create the principal codes after the data had been condensed. Codes are primarily used to recover and categorise fragments of related details (Miles et al., 2014, p. 72). This allows the researcher to identify, remove quickly, and group segments relevant to an issue or research subject. In the beginning, the researcher carefully and thoroughly read the interview transcripts. This was discovered to be helpful for four purposes: (i) familiarising myself personally with the data and making sense of it; (ii) getting a comprehensive overview and synopsis of what was said in each transcript; (iii) recognizing and deleting extraneous data and identifying material that pertains to concepts or ideas described in the primary themes; and (iv) searching for any patterns in the interview data (Burnard et al., 2008; Creswell, 2013).

In this study, transcripts of the interviews were validated with handwritten notes and codes were generated that were based on literature issues and Tornatzky and Fleischer's (1990) TOE framework. In the data, the selection of codes (nodes) and the configuration and reconfiguration of the code provide appropriate responses to research questions (Bazeley & Jackson, 2013).

The next step was to come up with a list of potential subjects (themes). Braun and Clarke (2006) illustrate that there are no hard and fast rules for themes. The value of a motif defines it. The codes were examined in this situation, and some of them were grouped into one theme. There were multiple codes related to scale, place, age, and industry. For example, they were grouped under the initial theme of Overall Characteristics and Situation.

Handwritten notes and audio transcripts were closely analysed in semi-structured interviews to find parallels and variations in SME participants' responses to interpret the field data better. These findings revealed a variety of distinct and overlapping trends relating to literature topics and diverse technical, organisational, environmental, and individual influences. As previously said, a thematic research approach was used in this study to identify relevant themes since it is considered the most appropriate qualitative approach.

Themes are structures in data sets (Please see Table No. 3.7) that were significant for explaining the phenomenon studied (storyline) and were linked to the study's research questions. As a result, after the interviews were transcribed, themes were categorised according to the TOE framework and the literature review conceptual categories: Main steps to adopt SC, Critical success factors, Driver and challenges to adopting SC, Impact of SC adoption on SMEs. The four main themes were updated to match current emerging themes, sub-themes, and patterns using these categories and the TOE structure to generate an overview of the research issue and the goals that are the subject of this study.

Themes	Sub-Themes	Manual Coding
Adoption of SC	Social Presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Presence • Action Plan • Daily Post on Social Media Page • Vendor's Role • Self-Learning • Personal Development • Facilities and Services • Consultation • Following Trends or Other leaders in the market • Influence of Celebrities
Critical Success Factors	Role of Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owner or Manager Knowledge • Importance of Leadership • Recruitment Process • Resource Optimization

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bold and wise leadership decision • Innovative Owner or Manager
	Highly Skilled Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shortage of Skilled Staff • Empowering Staff • Employee's Decision Power
	IT Vendor Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vendor's support • Vendor's Decision Power • Working along with Vendor
	Role of Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political Instability • Incompetent Government Staff • Corruption • Provide better IT Infrastructure issue within Country • Lengthy Government Processes to get information • Government Dedicated Department for SMEs (SMEDA and PTA) • Less Support from Government as compare to western countries • Government Unfair Policies • Government Policies and legislations

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education System in Pakistan
	Customer Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Customer Trust on Technology • Brand Awareness • Customer Trust on Brand • Payment issues
	Social WOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online customer Feedback • Customer Purchase Decision • Sharing SM Page
Driver and Challenges to adopt SC	Technological Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadband availability and speed • Communication with Customer • IT Infrastructure • Choice of Hardware tools • Choice of Social media platforms • Website attributes • User Interaction • Payment Options • Wrong Product Listing
	Organisational Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact of Organisational Culture • Communication with Vendor • In-house Training System • Financial issues • Cost Control • Customer Service

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Development • Company’s SOP • Social Media Marketing Campaigns • Team Collaboration • Interaction with customers • Social Support
	Environmental Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Customer Knowledge • Impact of COVID-19 • Multi-Tasking Employees • Personal Development • Self-Learning • Friend and Family Support • Traditional Business to Digitised Business Techniques • Staff Knowledge • Self-Evaluation • Lack of professionalism in vendors
Impact of SC Adoption on SMEs	Market Penetration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rise in Sale • Worldwide customer approach • Timely response to customer • Customer retention • Attracting New Customer

Table No. 3.7: Identified Themes and Sub-themes

3.9.1.2. Data Display:

The display of data is the second major step of any research. Data display is organised and compressed data from which results and behaviour can be drawn (Miles et al., 2014). Data display/visualisation is seen as an essential tool to facilitate clarity in the analysis phase, in addition to being a valuable medium to interact, summarise, and analyse qualitative data (Alhojailan, 2012). Put it another way, this move enables a clearly understandable and visually stimulating description of the analysed data from which conclusions about the study can be drawn (Alhojailan, 2012). This step takes many forms, including tables, maps, decision-making bodies and other geological formats (Miles et al., 2014).

3.9.1.3. Conclusion Drawing and Verification:

The third stage of the qualitative data proposed data processing. The researcher tries to attach significance to the findings to make sense of the data about the nature of the problem under examination during this process. This phase based on two major activities: drawing conclusions and verifying the procedure (Miles et al., 2014).

This method entails analysing the meaning of the analysed data and assessing the consequences for the problems at hand. Verification, which is inextricably related to drawing conclusions, entails checking the evidence as many times as possible to cross-check or validate these emerging results. This also assists the researcher in correctly ranking the results, which leads to clear conclusions. The hypothesis and evaluation processes are critical in providing and generating relevant and reliable data based on the study's findings; ongoing investigations can only accomplish this to produce new information. As a result, valuable data on the themes' contextual variables were identified, and emotional substance can be seen in the findings. A researcher then derives the context and develops hypotheses for these data using their information and experience. Using this method, the researcher in this study identified the issues and drivers of social commerce adoption in different SMEs in Pakistan. The researcher involved in this study generated and produced narrative perspectives from skype and telephonic interviews with owner, managers and other employees about social commerce within the participating SMEs. As previously mentioned, a thematic analysis technique was used in this research to provide precise interpretative results based on the textual data – and their simplified version contained in the matrices.

In this research, after transcription and reviewing the data several times, the research "in this case" was done on a case-by-case basis. Themes were then prioritised, and transcripts and annotations were created as concise, manageable, and rich explanations for each scenario. Furthermore, they were organised under the descriptive system to allow for a further case study.

The fundamental goal of the "within the case" study was to find generalisable structures and patterns for each case, regardless of the research questions. After reorganising the related case data into codes, the data were clustered and organised by themes. The specific factors that hampered or encouraged social commerce adoption for each organisation were established through the "inside the case" study. Participants were also sent copies of the interview narratives and asked if they contained any inaccuracies or misunderstandings. They were instructed to contact the researcher within two weeks if they were dissatisfied with the narratives.

The data from a multiple case study was then compiled using a "cross-case" analysis, which involved first analysing the findings for each particular case study and then studying the identical pattern of the results in the case studies to create matrices. Case studies that combine internal and cross-case analysis are more successful in producing analytical models and systematic recommendations than studies that focus only on case-by-case or cross-case analysis (Barratt et al., 2011). A cross-case analysis was used in this study to reinforce the hypothesis by repeating the accounts of the interview subjects and the things heard during the interviews, as well by using physical examination to derive correlations and commonalities from what the researcher saw on the field. Finally, each case study was designed so that all of the data was categorised into essential categories.

The themes and trends were then explored in the light of current literature, a method (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007) refers to as the restricting literature, with the understanding of the findings as to the end product of this stage of the study. Miles et al. (2014) model and a comparison classification system were used to create matrices in a cross-case study. Industry associations, trusted third parties, and local and government institutes analysed the cases in pairs, then looked for correlations and variations in the results. Following that, any new observations or elements/trends discovered during the study were documented compared to sector data collected from stakeholders.

Then, based on the discussion of each case study and a methodological comparison of the findings in response to the research questions, conclusions were drawn. The discussion of Chapter # 4 introduces some of the critical themes and trends within each organisation. Finally, the researcher's insight and imagination were used to make sense of the text, photographs, and handwritten material gathered during the field interviews.

3.10. Research Reliability and Validity:

In any study, whether qualitative or quantitative, reliability and validity are two essential aspects of data quality. However, in quantitative analysis, each word denotes a critical component to the rigour and robustness (Heale and Twycross, 2015), including the data quality. As a result, it was essential to understand these principles while performing the second phase of this research review to express the instrument's rigour and improve its precision (Yin, 2018). While the two definitions are distinct, it is essential to note that reliability and validity checks are related (Tavakol and Dennick 2011). However, as the literature indicates, a test with a high-reliability score but no validity, or vice versa, is likely (Jackson, 2014).

Validity and reliability, which can be interpreted as internal and external, are fundamental in qualitative research (Yin, 2018). Qualitative quality, according to implies that the researcher verifies the consistency of the findings using specific methods. In contrast, qualitative reliability means that the researcher's data collection process is compatible with other legitimate studies (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). According to Saunders et al. (2016), validity and efficiency minimise the risk of lousy test outcomes. In this study, owner-managers were interviewed as organisational decision-makers about s-commerce project adoption and implementation. Other administrative personnel from different branches of the seven organisations were also interviewed to allow for qualitative analysis, which helps improve the quality and reliability of the data gathered during the interview processes.

3.10.1. Research Validity:

Validity is one of the strengths of qualitative research. It is based on determining whether the findings are accurate from the researcher's standpoint, the participant or the readers of an account, and adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007). Yin (2018) identified two types of validity in the investigation of the case study; internal validity and external validity.

The rigorous method of handling interview test questions assisted the internal feasibility of this analysis using the interview questionnaire. The questionnaire was reviewed during the pilot research process after it was designed. According to the participant and the researcher's monitoring team, the interview questions were thoroughly prepared, reviewed, and refined. The questionnaire was also

developed, analysed, and updated using the literature scan during the pilot process. The researcher used the literature review to fill in the gaps and concentrate on the challenges and factors of social-commerce adoption in developed and emerging economies. As a consequence, the interview questions reflected this.

According to Yin (2018), external validity is the degree to which the results of a case study can be applied analytically to cases that were not part of the initial study. Instead of using only one case study, the researcher in this study used several case studies to establish solid proof. According to Yin (2018), external authenticity is the most significant stumbling block in the study of qualitative analysis events. The researcher in this analysis selected the purposive sampling approach as a suitable method for evaluating generalisation to address this challenge. Participants in the purposive sampling process better portray the research subject or have the most experience of the sample. As a result, with the whole company as the unit of study, having access to the owner-manager as a participant was a critical factor in choosing the various cases from other workers with e-commerce expertise. Finally, seven organisations from the Hospitality and Tourism industry were chosen for final data collection in three Pakistani financial cities.

Furthermore, during the semi-structured and skype interviews, the researcher asked open-ended questions as part of the data collection phase, allowing participants to openly express their thoughts and perspectives about the study priorities necessary for the conversation. Furthermore, before the direct personal interviews, the interviewer made himself known to the participants and developed a professional partnership, which gave them more interest in providing relevant answers to the study questions. The interviewer started the interviews by giving a general overview of the research subject, the importance of the study before moving on to the research questions.

As a result, the findings of this study apply to other SMEs in Pakistan, as Pakistani SMEs are homogeneous and share many characteristics. As a consequence, the results of the seven SMEs may be seen elsewhere. However, Yin (2018) stated that it was possible to generalise by including other organisations and nations, but researchers should be careful.

3.10.2. Research Reliability:

Yin (2018) illustrates that reliability aims to reduce errors and biases in a sample. He advised qualitative researchers to chart their case study protocols and take as many methodological measures as possible. Furthermore, Yin (2009) assumes that reliability can be achieved by maintaining accuracy in the analysis and reducing the probability of error and bias. For example, after the interview

recording, review the transcripts to ensure there are no visible mistakes. It was also suggested that a case study protocol and a comprehensive archive be developed to follow the same procedures. Throughout the research, all of these criteria were met.

Through standardising the survey, the case study protocol contributes to its reliability. A basic overview of the project, key testing questions to be answered during the interview process, field interview protocols, and field data recording techniques are relevant documentation. In addition, to reduce inferences, the researcher reported and transcribed all interviews. As a result, the researcher created a case study protocol in this study and a model framework for the case study and a guide on designing experiments to increase reliability. The researcher can conveniently view and restore data for re-analysis using the case study protocol and database registration.

Furthermore, the researcher contacted the study participants during the data collection and interpretation periods to provide additional assistance if requested during the study's testing phase. Furthermore, during the investigation of this study's theory and methods, the researcher explored his research approach with many doctoral research associates and community participants and a supervisor to resolve research issues that occurred during the investigation, For instance, research onion layers, research methods and techniques, data analysis, theme recognition, and research conclusions.

3.11. Consideration of Ethics:

For researchers, ethical policies are a huge point of concern. From the beginning to the end, it is an essential component of the study. It has also been identified as the "heart" of high-quality research by Ritchie et al. (2013, p.78). As such, the ethical quality of the study must be maintained.

It isn't easy to classify the essence of ethical questions in the qualitative study and varies from quantitative research topics. Ethical problems exist, for example, as to how a researcher approaches a collective group and the consequences of researchers on participants (Cresswell and Poth, 2013). Qualitative researchers concentrate on investigating, analysing and describing individuals and their natural settings. They are thereby introduced into qualitative studies in the principles of interactions and influence between researchers and participants. The willingness to participate depends on a participant's willingness to share his/her experience.

Social scientists ought to reconcile the research values with the customer's interest, says Patterson (2013). In addition, Ritchie et al. (2013) and Blandford (2013) argued that critical ethical concerns such as privacy, secrecy and informed consent should be addressed when undertaking quality research. Consequently, researchers must obtain ethical consent before undertaking a field study under the UWS

ethics policy. A comprehensive request with all the details and procedures needed was sent to the Committee of Ethics, and the committee endorsed the request.

The application for ethics contained some documentation: the researcher application form, reports on studies and secrecy matters (indicating that no personal information about the participants and the organisations' name would be revealed at any stage of the research and should remain confidential). Code names can be produced and used throughout the analysis. There was also a consent form to allow participants openly to join and withdraw from their research at any moment. During the application for ethics, more cover letters were also submitted to the university.

3.12. Summary:

The philosophies and qualitative methods of analysis followed in this thesis were discussed in the chapter based on the description of the research onions, according to Saunders et al. (2016, p.124). A review also focused on interpretive study trends in epistemological and methodological ideologies and how they form the foundation of research design. Then it addressed quality analysis types, techniques, case study plan and the time for the longitudinal.

The study described how numerous data sources, such as interviews, observations, documentation, and online sources (to gather data from participants; mainstream findings of e-commerce adoption by the small and medium-sized businesses) had been adopted instead of relying on a single data source. The approach for analysing the qualitative data was then explored based on the work of Bazeley and Jackson (2013) to analyse data systematically.

This was conducted to produce clear interpretative findings based on textual details. A thematic analysis approach to define issues arising in the data was explored to help draw an inference based TOE structure model. The analysis was carried out based on textual data. There were debates on SME selection, ethical issues and data collection tools.

The following chapter discusses findings and discussions.

4. Findings and Discussions

4.1. Introduction:

Through cross-case analysis and comparison with the literature research findings, this chapter aims to present and evaluate the seven case studies' data analysis results under examination. This chapter takes the approach of explaining any new insights or understandings that come from this research and attempting to relate the findings of this research to those of earlier research. The first part outlines the significant steps of implementing social commerce in each SME and provides up-to-date information on the evolution of social commerce within each organisation. In the second section, the critical success factors to adopt social commerce in developing countries are examined to support and improve the SC initiative. This section also looks at the different parts of the TOE model, including technological, organisational, and environmental factors influencing SC adoption in SMEs. The third section examines the influence of leadership and behaviour in promoting and adopting SC adoption. The fourth part looks at the numerous driving and challenging factors that each SME must overcome to adopt SC. Then in the fifth section analyses the role of leadership and behaviour towards the adoption of SC. The final section of this chapter discusses the impact of SC adoption on SMEs. A summary and conclusion are presented in the last part of the chapter.

4.2. Adoption of SC:

The qualitative data of this study show that SMEs adopt different strategies to adopt SC. Some organisations have followed the other leaders in the market, while some organisations have their plans. In Pakistan, some environmental issues were found during the skype interview and discussed below in this chapter. Therefore, most organisations do not follow or invest money in professionals. They intend to focus on self-learning or personal development. To adopt SC successfully, most of the organisation focus on their social presence among the community. Although, it was revealed that most of the SMEs have their social media page on Facebook or Instagram (Two popular social media applications in Pakistan). Making a business page on these applications require just basic information and knowledge. The qualitative data of this study found that owner or business managers have knowledge of this technology and want to run this project professionally. Their self-learning or personal development skills assist them to see the outcome of the project before they hand it over to the third party or hire professionals. Therefore, they focus on social presence to get customer and assurance. For instance, the owner and Social Media Manager of Company F stated in the skype interview;

Our business was very traditional at the start, and we used traditional techniques to approach the customer. In 2017, with the rise of technological advancement in the country and looking at the different features of popular social media platforms (Facebook and Instagram), we had an idea to be more social in the community. We signed up on Facebook and Instagram, where we reached about 5k people within few weeks and following us on social media.

The owner of Company E indicated that;

To get customer trust, we started with our social presence on Facebook and Instagram. We offered them different packages. All this process started with planning; we have team members who consider different aspects to bring change within the organisation. To adopt social commerce more successfully, we just started with our social presence on social media. The reason for this process to get customer trust in our brand and customer awareness about us.

The social media manager of company C told in the skype interview that;

To adopt social commerce, we have gone through different phases. We felt that customer service techniques are switching from traditional to digital customer service. Our organisation already had a social presence on social media. Those pages were very basic. There was no information other than our company logo, address, and few posts on the wall. I took the responsibility to shape them more professionally. We did our market research by filling up the customer response card. So market scanning/research was our first stage.

While the social media manager highlighted that they have gone through the decision-making process;

To adopt SC for the first time in our business, we had to undergo a decision-making process where the management team decided whether or not to go through with the decision. Then we conducted market research (market scanning) and third-party consultations to ensure we were knowledgeable about the initiative.

4.3. Social Presence:

The qualitative data of this research show us that SMEs in Pakistan take the first step to adopt SC is social presence.

Within virtual settings containing social participants, social presence has been deemed particularly important. It is because the social company has a positive effect on social influence. According to research, social presence has been linked to several good communication outcomes, including persuasion and attractiveness (e.g., Fogg and Tseng, 1999; Lee et al., 2006a). Hassanein and Head (2007) concluded that social presence was positively associated with Trust, enjoyment, and perceived utility of an online shopping website, resulting in increased purchase intentions.

Company A provides hotel services, and they adopted social commerce by creating a page on Facebook and Twitter to attract their customers. For example, the owner explained:

"The most important stage we had to go through was to establish ourselves on social media. We decided to focus mainly on Facebook and Twitter to gain attraction. On top of self-advertisement, we had to find a way to make sales online, which we did by offering nightly stays on the Facebook marketplace" (Owner, Company A).

To adopt SC professionally, they had gone through the planning and consultation with team members after conducting market research argued by SM Manager

"To adopt SC for the first time in our business, we had to undergo a decision-making process where the management team decided whether or not to go through with the decision; then we conducted market research (market scanning) and third-party consultations to ensure we were knowledgeable about the initiative. Then, we carried on with the planning and preparations for the implementation of SC in our business strategy. Our last steps were to implement and review the decision to assess the results of incorporating SC in our business" (SM Manager, Company A).

The owner further argued that there was no strategic plan to adopt the SC. Their main intention was to attract sales and increase revenue by offering online deals and promotions. He further added that they asked their customers to give them online feedback that helped them a lot.

"Our goal is to reach many people of different kinds to build popularity and open more locations. We focus on offering online deals through social media platforms. Those

booking which we get through social media advertisement, we can ask the customer to leave us feedback on our social media page. It is an easy way to share customer feedback on our social media page; it promotes our sale" (Owner, Company A).

Company A got direct help from a third party (vendor) to adopt SC and implement it. The other local brands also inspired them. They also used their expertise through self-learning and personal development. They encouraged their customers to give them feedback about the product and service on their social media page.

"Which resulted in the final decision to use peer-reviewed websites and group deals to generate sales. Social media is an important part of SC in our company as we make sure to have customer representation through customer-generated content displayed on there" (Owner, Company A).

In an interview with company C, their SMM argued that they used almost the same techniques as Company A to adopt SC. They made their social presence too on available social media platforms to gain popularity. After conducting the market research, they opted in for the SC.

"Our organisation already had a social presence on social media. Those pages were fundamental. There was no information other than our company logo, address, and few posts on the wall. I took the responsibility to shape them more professionally. We did our market research by filling up the customer response card. So market scanning/research was our first stage" (SMM, Company C).

In an interview with Company E owner, it was found that they used the same steps to adopt social commerce.

"To get customer trust, we started with our social presence on Facebook and Instagram. We offered them different packages. All this process started with planning, and we have a team who consider different aspect to bring change within the organisation. To adopt social commerce more successfully, we must start with our social presence on social media. The reason for this process to get customer trust on our brand and customer awareness about us" (Owner, Company C).

In an interview with the Owner and SMM with company F, they brought to attention that they created and ran social media pages on different platforms such as Facebook and Instagram to get the customer trust. They found them very beneficial and got followers and customers within a month. They browsed the features of social media platforms and adopted Social commerce.

"In 2017, with the rise of technological advancement in the country and by looking at the different feature of popular social media platform (Facebook and Instagram), we had an idea to be more social in the community. We signed up on Facebook and Instagram, where we reached about 5k people within few weeks and following us on social media and liking our daily posts. We discussed it with our managers and decided to adopt SC and use its features professionally" (Owner & SMM, Company F).

The social media managing director of company G asserted that they did the market search first and adopted the social media pages to introduce their brand in the market.

"In 2017, we have noticed that market is emerging and customer trend is changing to digital services. Our top management decided to adopt SC after market research. Our initial plan was to introduce our business on social media and make the customer aware of us. We planned to adopt social commerce technology through experienced staff. We recruited the people and started working on it."

In brief, during the interview and several visits to the company's social media pages and websites, it was identified that there was no formal planning or consultation took place to adopt SC within SMEs in Pakistan. SMEs in Pakistan joins social media for their social presence and get the Trust of the customers or for information purposes only. With social network features, they opt-in for social commerce to increase their sales and customers. In general, we can say that the social presence is a crucial driver to adopt SC in SMEs' in Pakistan.

4.4. Critical Success Factors:

This section discusses the findings related to the critical success factors theme. Based on the results associated with this theme, four sub-themes were identified that influenced the adoption of SC. The below-mentioned paragraphs present the findings related to each sub-theme in details.

4.4.1. Role of Leadership:

The owner of company A argued that leadership is a critical part of any project. It is not possible to complete any task without leadership.

"I believe leadership is the most important aspect of any task that may need to be completed. With that being said, we used our leadership to develop our idea of establishing social commerce in the first place" (Owner, Company A).

Furthermore, the SM Manager argued that:

"The role of leadership and top management was essential in the SC adoption process because, as in any change initiative, support for a change is communicated top-down. Without top management support, this initiative would not be successful" (SM Manager, Company A).

In brief, leadership plays a critical role to motivate their team to adopt new technology. Clear guidelines and company's policies defined by innovative leaders can enhance the adoption process.

The social media managing director of Company F shares the same thoughts:

"I feel that without the support of leadership, it was not possible to bring in house change. Leadership made bold decisions to adopt SC. They defined the team's business goals and pushed their subordinates to achieve them" (Social Media Managing Director, Company F).

An interview with the SMM of Company C identified that:

"I think the role of leadership or top management is very crucial and important during this SC adoption process because the leadership of any organisation is directly linked to decision making and they are also policymaker" (SMM, Company C).

Respondents from Company D, F and G argued that their leadership is fully responsible for conducting training sessions, food hygiene, quality control, customer-related chores, and maintaining their ongoing sales. The data shows that executives provide a clear path to their associates to bring change to the organisation. Their enthusiasm and motivation are higher than other staff.

The Manager of company E asserted that:

"Leader plays a key role in the adoption process of SC. The leadership of our company initiated the shift from traditional to social commerce, and they led from the front by keeping a close eye on all the aspects of change along with keeping the team motivated."

The role of leadership is another critical factor that plays an essential part to adopt SC. The qualitative data shows that the owner's, Manager's and leader's innovativeness is another vital factor affecting the organisational SC adoption process. This element offers an organisation's acceptance of the new ideas and especially to new ICTs tools. Owner and managers are the primary decision-maker in the organisation, specifically in SMEs (Isma'ili et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 2015). Although, this has been considered as an essential factor in many previous studies (Alghamdi et al., 2018; Boukamcha, 2019; Ngibe, M. and Lekhanya, 2019). SMEs are more likely to embrace IT if their leaders are more innovative and have a positive attitude toward IT adoption (Henry et al., 2017; Orser and Riding, 2019).

4.4.2. Highly Skilled Staff:

In the interview process, It was revealed that highly skilled staff is another critical success. Company F got services from the vendor to train themselves and to train their staff. The owner and SMM of company A argued that they could not teach their staff despite all the hard work. In Pakistan, sometimes it isn't easy to find the right person for the right job.

The owner of company F said in a Skype interview that:

As we live in the era of technology, the IT skills of managers and employees would help any business. As I have faced these challenges to adopting SC.

The General Manager of company c shared that:

"Poor IT skills of managers and operational employees may also add fuel to the fire."

The owner of company C further argued that:

"I had to get some IT help from a consultant. It helped me a lot; without it, I would never have been able to take this process off."

The SMM of company C said in the interview that:

"We have got a team after a long process of recruitment, there are different technical institutes in Pakistan, but they hardly teach them about upcoming or ongoing technology. In short, you can skilled staff was another challenge."

The ICT Managing director of company D argued that the shortage of skilled staff was the most significant impediment. In developing countries, you have to work hard to find a professional. Many institutes are teaching about social media things, but organisations are struggling to find the right person. He further blames the education system of Pakistan.

"ICT knowledge and not set of clear guidelines was a big impediment for us. We worked hard to adopt and implement SC most effectively, but as I already mentioned that this adoption was not ideal for us in the beginning."

The owner of company E further illustrates that their adoption was not ideal due to a lack of technical skills. He relates this to the shortage of skilled employees. There were no clear guidelines for them to adopt SC most effectively. This process would be easier for them if they had qualified people in their organisation.

"ICT knowledge and not set of clear guidelines was a big impediment for us. We worked hard to adopt and implement SC most effectively, but as I already mentioned that this adoption was not ideal for us in the beginning."

The SMM of company C argued that it would be helpful for the organisations to recruit highly skilled employees and organise training sessions if they have enough financial resources.

As a result, SMEs have challenges developing a commercial website for SC transactions and finding experienced IT workers for webpage development, IT unit maintenance, and daily SM activity execution. Aside from the scarcity of IT specialists in Pakistan, highly trained individuals are employed by major firms, and SMEs cannot afford to hire and pay for their costly services.

4.4.3. Role of Vendor:

In the interview phase, it was found that IT vendors play a critical role in adopting SC. The owner of company A shared his thoughts about the vendor's role that:

"It's one of the most important aspects! Without vendor support, there'd be no business in the first place. They also play a direct role in social commerce adoption. The responsibility of a vendor supporter is to promote our business."

The SM Manager of the same company argued that:

"The consultant's role was also one that held great significance in the SC adoption process because the consultant was responsible for the education and the guidance of the SC management team. It gave the consultant great power; if it was violated could result in high costs for the company."

The almost same type of thoughts was shared by the General Manager of the company C:

"Vendor support/consultant's role has a huge impact to the SC because these people know techniques, expertise and mechanism to implement SC in business."

In developing countries, especially in Pakistan, technology is growing. Still, the adoption process relies on the experts as the small organisations can't afford to recruit highly skilled people for full time. Most of the organisations get the services from third parties to get an overview of the project.

SMM has slightly different thought from his general managers; he argued that:

"Vendor does the same things as we are doing by our self in our company. The only difference I can say that their business model is different. They work for you and take the care of everything on your behalf."

SMM of company C further explained that they could do the same job as the vendor is doing for them. Due to a lack of financial resources, the firm's owner or general Manager was not interested in investing much in the setup.

The owner of Company E explained that:

"Social media advertising agency is responsible for all our social media-related issues. For successful SC adoption in our organisation, the vendor has played a critical role."

Furthermore, it was revealed in the interview that company E rely on their IT Vendor. IT vendor is responsible for technical issues, running SM page, publish a daily post on SM platforms, and creating

any offer or deals on social media. In this way, the owner explained that he has less hassle and have extra time to look at other issues personally.

The Manager of Company E illustrates that:

"Vendor support is one of the key aspects of the social commerce adoption. Vendor support enables the successful adoption and running the business successfully post-adoption."

Company E struggled to find highly skilled people for their IT department. Hence, they decided to get the services from a professional IT vendor. After a long journey with different IT consultants and marketing agencies, they found the right team. They claimed that they had hired other IT vendors, but there was a lack of professionalism.

The owner of the company D shared his view about the vendor's role as:

"In our case, it is not as relevant, but in general, I believe the support from vendors can make the adoption process less difficult."

Company D has used their resources as it got help from friends and family. They also focused on personal development and self-learning. The Skype interview revealed that their adoption was not very effective, but they managed somehow according to their needs.

4.4.4. Role of Government:

Many scholars (Awiagah et al., 2016; Nazir & Zhu, 2018) feel that government efforts play a significant role in e-commerce adoption since they can either help or hinder the growth of social commerce. The government plays an essential role in developing SMEs in many developed and developing countries, assisting firms in the usage and adoption of new forms of technical equipment for SC adoption. The government is also helping numerous SMEs obtain better IT resources to boost technical activities and revenue, which may help the country's economy grow and flourish.

All participants from SMEs in Pakistan agreed that the government plays a significant role in creating social commerce capacity in any economy when interviewed. They also say that, although the GoP plays a vital role in formulating numerous SME policies that benefit multiple enterprises in the country, many SMEs continue to lag. The primary issues raised in this study under GoP support for social commerce adoption include the lack of legislative rules on the s-commerce framework, uncertain political and governmental conditions, and, most importantly, corruption in the GoP.

In the Skype interview with the owner of Company A shared his thought about this factor as:

"It does play a bigger role than we can casually assume. The popularity of high government officials can take a toll on social media and social commerce, as we've seen with former US President Donald Trump. During his presidency, he was able to draw many republican officials off of Twitter, along with their supporters, and on to different platforms."

The SMM of the same company said that:

"The government plays a minor role in terms of technological development. Some laws and regulations guide technological development in Pakistan, but enforcement of those laws is not as strong."

The General Manager of company C said that:

"Without any doubt, we can say that government can play a vital and key role in the technological development of SMEs under proper continuation and implementation of policies."

He also argued that there is a lack of cooperation from the government to adopt the new technology.

"We were facing like no cooperation from the governmental organisation, their lazy and inactive working on the issues they have to deal with."

In the same line, the owner of company B said that there is no support for SMEs from the government of Pakistan. He further linked this limitation to all other challenges.

"In Pakistan, We have ministries and national departments to support small business. I never got any kind of support from them. First, it is difficult to approach them. Secondly, they do not have full information in one place. You might have to go through different people to obtain any information; to me, it's time-consuming. You can get better information from any consultant with less effort and time. Third and more important, I would say that government should focus on and encourage youngsters to adopt the new technologies. We will have more skilled people at affordable cost."

The SMM of company C has mentioned in the Skype interview that:

"It does play a bigger role than we can casually assume. The popularity of high government officials can take a toll on social media and social commerce, as we've seen with former US President Donald Trump. During his presidency, he was able to draw many republican officials off of Twitter, along with their supporters, and on to different platforms."

The Manager of the company E shared his thought about this factor as:

"Previous governments have worked to bring the technology in the country. Also, they made some policies for small businesses, but there is not much support for the businesses in Pakistan compared to the businesses that support Western countries."

The SMM of the company F said that usually, the government set the rule and regulations of any project. Also, government aim to provide the IT infrastructure in any country.

"I don't think there is a Government role in terms of SC adoption in any organisation. They just set the regulation, policies to follow or bring the technology in the country."

The social media managing director argued that:

"Government plays the role of backbone in the developing of economies. SMEs directly contribute to the healthy economy of the country. In terms of support to adopt technology, there was not much support from the government side."

According to the findings of this study, there is a negative correlation between the government of Pakistan's support and SC adoption by SMEs in the country. According to data collected from participating SMEs, the GoP had a role in supporting e-commerce to some level, as it would aid economic development. The GoP, for example, took the initiative to create Ministries to Support Small Businesses. The primary goal of these ministries was to give SMEs the most up-to-date information and skills and development training. However, the participants, including the owners-managers of all seven SMEs, pointed out that the government needed to focus on several elements to enhance SC's overall structure in the state. The main problems for SMEs include corruption, incompetent government employees, discriminatory treatment, legislations to adopt new technology and a lack of financial support. Furthermore, when supporting innovative technology in the country, it was thought they should also provide subsidies for SMEs.

Furthermore, there was no legal framework to allow the country to exploit SC technology to stay competitive worldwide. Many economies' governments are responsible for teaching and promoting awareness about SC among SMEs. The GoP, on the other hand, does not pay enough attention to or take efforts in the IT sector (including SC) for the benefit of investors, as demonstrated by this study's various internal and external impediments. Because SMEs experience a lack of access to financial resources, the government should give financial help by granting subsidies and encouraging banks to provide financial support to SMEs.

These findings are consistent with those of Rahayu and Rita (2015), who investigated the variables that influence SMEs' adoption of e-commerce in developing countries, notably Indonesia. When compared to SMEs in industrialised nations, they found that Indonesian SMEs had a long way to go regarding technology adoption. This circumstance calls on the government to support effective programs and initiatives to assist Indonesian SMEs in using the new technologies.

4.5. Driver and Challenges of SC Adoption:

This part contains information on many aspects influencing the effective adoption of SCs in various SMEs based on the TOE model and the previous themes and sub-subjects. The following table shows similar elements within the seven SMEs. Three more factors based on the TOE model (technological, organisational and environmental factors) were separated into many sub-themes and codes. These are further examined, starting with the technical aspect.

Themes	Sub-Themes	Codes
Technological Factors	E-readiness in society and knowledge management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wrong Product Listing • IT Infrastructure • User Interaction • Communication with Customer • Choice of Hardware tools • Website attributes

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choice of Social media platforms • Payment Options • Broadband availability and speed • Data security and privacy
Organisational Factors	Poor HR Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-house Training System • Customer Service • Research and Development • Company's SOP • Social Media Marketing Campaigns • Impact of Organisational Culture
	Importance of Financial Resources and Management support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial issues • Cost Control • Communication with Vendor • Interaction with customers • Social Support
Environmental Factors	Traditional Business	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Customer Knowledge • Traditional Business to Digitised Business Techniques

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-Tasking Employees • Impact of COVID-19 • Personal Development • Self-Learning • Friend and Family Support • Staff Knowledge • Self-Evaluation • Lack of professionalism in vendors
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Table No. 4.1: Themes and sub-themes based on TOE model

4.5.1. Technological Factors:

Although it is crucial to embrace numerous technologies in SMEs, as discussed in chapter 2, the number of codes has been identified in this context. Further, two sub-themes were created under the technological factor theme.

4.5.1.1. E-readiness in society and Knowledge Management:

The significance of this theme has been highlighted in the qualitative data from the interviews and is an ongoing issue among different SMEs included in this study. Participants said mainly that improving information and knowledge management in the organisation is one of the biggest obstacles to the effective adoption of SC as a business strategy for their business operations. Although they have the essential information and understanding, the participants further noted that it undoubtedly influences the effective integration of SC services.

The overall status and preparation of country infrastructure for adopting the newest technology, including SC, and excellent quality hardware and software, was another criteria noted by all SME participants. Interviewees stated that the general quality of the country's infrastructure is one of the critical barriers to their companies' growth. All sources pointed out that inadequate infrastructure quality is a barrier to adopting state-of-the-art technology such as SC in Pakistan.

The SMM of company A said:

"Two main things have contributed to hindering the success of SC in our business. As mentioned above, consumers in Pakistan are not exposed to the concept of mixing social media with shopping at a vast level, so we had meagre traffic in the start."

The ICT managing director of company D argued that:

"Quality of hardware tools are not available in the market. We spent a lot of money on these tools. Local companies make the software we use to keep customer records (Epos system), and we lose our customer record anytime. In terms of branded product and service, they are not affordable as there is no subsidiary government on these products."

The owner of Company E stated that:

"There is no IT infrastructure available in the rural area; mostly our customers belong from rural areas who travel every day to the city for their job and business. We cannot approach them in time, as there is no internet service available."

The social media managing director of company G illustrated that their community is not well aware of the features of social media apps. Most social media users use social media to consume their free time or for purposes. He also blamed the government educational system, as GoP does not take the initiative to digested the country.

"In Pakistan, most people use social media for pleasure and fun purposes. They are not well aware of the features of these social media apps. I would blame this to our government as their educational system is not updated."

Furthermore, the owner of the company F stated that:

"My village is about 50km away from Pakistan's capital, but there are no internet services. PTA is a governmental organisation to provide the information and communication system in the country, but still, I could not understand their system. In

brief, I would say that all the previous governments were failed to provide the information and communication system in the country."

The owner of the company E asserted that:

"I found that to promote your page or product on social media, and you have to choose the right keywords for your product listing. It is another technical issue. We were not getting enough response on social media while we were offering the packages to our customers. It was because we were not using the right search keywords. Thanks to our current vendor."

4.5.2. Organisational Factors:

4.5.2.1 Poor HR Planning:

Every firm has a different definition of "success" and "failure," but surveys in the business sector suggest that more organisations have failed in their projects. A probable explanation for such a tremendous failure rate of any project is that organisations (set by managers, decision-makers and other stakeholders) are not taking the necessary action to analyse the risks and manage them (Kumar, 2020). Human resource management methods are one of the most effective ways to maximise internal resources and increase revenues by enhancing employee performance (Rahman et al., 2020). Human resource management systems have a substantial influence on both individual and organisational performance. Human resource (HR) measures that promote job satisfaction can help people work longer, although the extent of this benefit is unknown (Barslund et al., 2019).

Mainly, the qualitative data of this study shows that poor HR planning of Pakistani SMEs is one of the main challenges to adopt SC. In the case of Company C, participants have indicated that due to their poor HR management and planning, their SC adoption was not effective by any means.

"As we all know, practice makes a man perfect. We had some flaws in our work, not properly trained staff, poor decision making and planning."

The respondent from company G stated that they have gone through a long process to recruit people for their organisation. HR skills would make this processes easier and cost-effective.

"The second biggest challenge was to find experienced and talented staff. When we advertise in the newspaper about the ongoing positions, we have got 1000 applications. It was a very challenging process to find the few right people out of one thousand applications."

The owner of Company B shared the same kind of arguments:

"As I mentioned earlier that adopting social commerce was not like we thought about it. Therefore, we had to get a third party service. They set up the page again on social media and managed it fully."

The owner and SMM of company B gave their briefed views about it. Company A is trying to train themselves by self-learning processes and getting services from third parties to train their staff.

"Yes. My family employees and I used self-exploration to build our skills on social media. Instead of researching, we decided to use hands-on strategies to develop ourselves better."

"We opted for third party consulting and educational services; therefore, despite all our expertise being from within the company, they were not trained in-house."

Another insight into why HR components are highly significant to the success of SMEs in Pakistan was provided by exploring interview data. Some of the participants in the company G emphasised these:

"We ensure that our staff is 100% trained and can solve any issue by themselves. We gave our staff decision power and will be confident to make any decision in the interest of the organisation."

4.5.2.2 Importance of Financial Resources and Top Management Support:

A recent survey carried out in Rahayu and Day (2017) also found that the heavy dependency on email services, lack of government role, the absence of ICT experts, poor management, and financial resources hinder Indonesian SMEs' poor use of technology services – a developing economy. Studies by Fawcett et al. (2008) and White et al. (2014) have demonstrated that small and medium-sized enterprises are neither uniformly or standardised. They are, in reality, highly heterogeneous in size,

sector, age, design and location and vary substantially. These features can impact the ICT adoption by an organisation directly (Apulu et al., 2011).

The owner and manager self-initiative also helped SC adoption and has had a favourable effect on the organisation's effective SC adoption. Building a social page on social media platforms is wholly built and implemented and has contributed significantly. The ICT department established the website for online consumers with the financial backing and the owner and managers in social commerce.

In the same organisation, both respondents agreed:

"Financial capabilities are another aspect to adopt SC. Without financial resource, we would not be able to adopt and implement SC more effectively."

The SMM of the same company F argued:

"We wanted the things done in our way. I worked along with the vendor and was providing them guideline throughout the process. I have worked with different vendors. The problem I face or any organisation face is that vendor does not recruit expert people. They have the people who did short computing courses and don't know about other things, i.e., marketing, branding, social presence, social support, etc. When they create any post, they do not consider all these aspects."

The owner of company B revealed that he is some knowledge and experience in customer management services. He has utilised all his resources to retain and engage his customer.

"After setting it up. The process of letting customers know the deals were a lot easier. We had to send a text and update our Facebook page by putting up a post. The end goal here to make sure customers come back. It can't be a one-time deal. You cannot grow a business on one time customers; you have to keep bringing customers and keep engage your existing customers constantly. You have to make sure that you are giving them the best price and service compared to other businesses around you."

The SMM has shared his views about financial resources and management role as:

"Financial capabilities play a most important role to bring change in the organisation. It is because you have to recruit the talented staff, new equipment, organise training sessions etc."

"To adopt social commerce, we have gone through different phases. We felt that customer service techniques are switching from traditional to digital customer service. Our organisation already had a social presence on social media. Those pages were fundamental. There was no information other than our company logo, address, and few posts on the wall. I took the responsibility to shape them more professionally."

While the owner of company A mentioned that there is no role of financial capabilities to adopt SC. Still, during the interview, he stated that their extensive and silent challenge was bankruptcy.

"I don't think it's as important as some would say. Sure, it helps to have it, but we don't have many financial resources or capabilities. We have a screen and people, and it gets the job done."

"From my perspective, it was everything we overcame before we were able to consider social commerce. We faced bankruptcy many times and had very many vacancies at a time."

The qualitative data shows that financial resources are vital for any organisation to run their daily operations and change. It also indirectly impacts managerial-related activities, such as HR department, operational Manager, employee and customer retention, etc.

4.5.2.3 Traditional Business:

Due to a lack of training in SMEs, most staff prefer to work manually and are not excited about using technology. The ICT managing director of company D asserted that:

"Customer tries to get more information through social media pages or via email. We aim to respond to them ASAP, but since we are busy with many other things. We ensure that we write them back with five working days. As our employees are not fully aware of these applications' features, they prefer to do their work traditionally. Also, there is no system in place to train our staff, so the top management or owner has to do technology-related activities."

These findings support the study done by Pagani and Pardo (2017). This study shows the overall behaviour of Pakistani small and medium-sized enterprises in the context of a conventional manner of conducting business. They also looked at the fundamental problem for SMEs to fully develop e-commerce and use online communication platforms to market different products and services.

The SMM of company F argued that:

To acquire a banking system at our workplace is a lengthy process and needs a box of documents. Also, the Pakistani community does not believe in social commerce and online payments due to fraudulent activities. Therefore, we prefer and give cash payment option to our customers. Although the online payment system is less hectic and beneficial for SMEs, our country's IT infrastructure is different from that of European countries.

"In Pakistan, we don't have an IT system and infrastructure in place, so people are still not believing that these things exist. The main issue we face with payment methods, the people who want to pay online, but the banking system does not support it. For a small organisation, legal documents production is a big hassle. To set up a payment terminal, we have to go through the long process, so we prefer a cash payment system."

Self-learning and getting support from friends and family is another success factor for personal development. Most SMEs go through this process to reduce their cost. Still, in Pakistan, SMEs does not have the professional services available such as support or training program from government, professionalism in vendors, and professionalism in employees. Therefore, the qualitative data of this study shows that most of the SMEs owner or Manager does not trust IT Vendors. Hence, they focus on personal development.

The owner of company B asserted that:

"First and most important challenge was for us that we had no professionals at our workplace to provide us guidelines. It was a self-motivated approach to adopt new technology that did not work initially due to less knowledge. Secondly, when we tried to hire a professional person for our workplace, it was not cost-effective. You are never sure about the outcome of any project. Therefore, it was more worthy for us to get services from any consultant. We are still improving our information and communication process once we feel that we are on top. We can recruit people and can provide facilities (Hardware, broadband, office, technical equipment etc.) to them."

In the same context, the owner of the company D asserted that:

"I had bad experiences in the past. The vendor that I hired for my company did not fulfil the commitment he made. I lost my time and business just because of his incompetency and fake promises. I knew the basics and learned more from friends and family, and got online help too. I am still learning about new and innovative ways to boost the SC in our company."

The owner of company A argued that:

Due to COVID-19, all their plans were failed. They worked day and night on this project, but Coronavirus was a silent challenge for them.

"One of our biggest silent challengers was the effect the Coronavirus took against us. The 13 of us live in the hotel together, so you can imagine we can get crowded together at times, and we, unfortunately, had a casualty along the way."

4.5.2.4 Customer Trust:

In the qualitative data, it was found that customer trust was another challenge for SMEs in Pakistan. A lack of customer trust to make online transactions in Pakistan has been the common challenge of all SMEs. In Pakistan, shopping is an outdoor experience, and urban Pakistanis tend to combine shopping with family dinners at restaurants. The instances reported in this study illustrate that, in contrast to Western consumer culture, which has limited time to go to commercial marketplaces to visit physical businesses and buy, Pakistani customers enjoy shopping by making it a regular thing. As a result, customers prefer to shop in person rather than make transactions online (Nasimi et al., 2018). In this research, however, participants identified specific grounds for not shopping and usage of social commerce; the lack of Trust in social commerce and its services was one of the most critical factors. The qualitative data analysis gave some other important insights into cultural obstacles that can influence an organisation's choice to adopt social commerce. The SMM of company D indicated that:

"Consumer trust is one of our main external challenge for us, the customer from urban areas have the power and knowledge to purchase online things, but due to lack of Trust, they are reluctant to do online shopping. In case our business, the customer would never make online payment before having their product and service. Therefore, we offer them cash payment or bank account transfer for their assurance."

Another SMM from company C shared the same types of thoughts:

"As the poverty level in Pakistan is very high as compared to developed countries. Therefore customer does not want to provide their bank details due to fraudulent activities. These understandable things as most customers have limited income, so they do not want to be victims. I would say that government ministries can play their role in this scenario by introducing the best legislation to protect our community and SMEs."

There is no doubt that the inflation rate in Pakistan is very high, and the people of Pakistan have limited income. Therefore, they cannot afford to lose their money.

The SM managing director of company G asserted that:

"From a customer point of view, we were struggling to get the Trust of customers. I worked hard along with my team. I have arranged the training session for them about social commerce and its components features. I have made sure that there is always online support for our customers. This strategy helped us a lot."

The consumer does not trust SMEs instantly. Hence they have to go through with techniques to be competitive in the market. Regarding SC adoption and consumer trust, the ICT managing director of company D stated that:

"Owner of this organisation has invested in ICT hardware tools such desktop computers, laptops, scanner, etc. First of all, we decided to give Trust to our customers, and it was not possible without the availability of speedy Internet. We aim to instant reply to any customer query or comment on our page. It helped us to make our social presence in the marketplace."

The owner of company B asserted that:

"People do not trust you, and they need assurance about you and your product. As I mentioned at the beginning of the interview, it was difficult to get page likes and followers. We are constantly updating our social media pages to assure people and get their confidence in our ICT service."

Qualitative data gives insight that customer trust in business and IoT is a challenge for SMEs in Pakistan. As we can see from the data, most SMEs face this as a critical driver for the successful adoption of SC. Therefore, some organisation tries to get the customer trust strategically. Their social presence helped their customers and grew the business.

For instance, the owner of company E argued that:

"To get customer trust, we started with our social presence on Facebook and Instagram. We offered them different packages. All this process started with planning, and we have a team who consider different aspect to bring change within the organisation. To adopt social commerce more successfully, we must start with our social presence on social media. The reason for this process to get customer trust in our brand and customer awareness about us."

4.5.2.5 Social WOM:

People worldwide are utilising social media in real-time for various communication purposes in today's borderless world, with the majority spending over a quarter of their daily time surfing social networks (Hussain et al., 2017). Service and product firms are eager to attract customers' attention and rethink marketing methods and policies for those firms. One component of the transformation, which reflects its products, services and brands to the outside world, is incorporating social media into its marketing regime.

Kazmi (2021) elaborated that consumer in Pakistan like to post a review about the product and service they use. Furthermore, a study on social platforms also assists the organisations in attracting new customers and leaving a solid product value in the customer's mind. In this regard, a respondent from company F argued that:

"Online reviews on our social media platforms gave confidence to other customers, and we are using them as a tool to attract new customer. Apart from that, these reviews are also assisting us in making our company's profile more strong."

Some managers and owner believe that customer feedback is an essential part of SC. The SMM of company C has shared his thought about it as:

"Customer feedback is one of the main factors we consider. We always push our customer to leave us feedback, either positive or negative. As it's a core component of SC."

Social commerce features allow their users to share the business pages, content transmitted by others and viral the things in the second. In contrast, e-commerce has minimal features, the customer leaves the feedback, but the seller has no chance to justify themselves. The General Manager of company C argued that:

"Since the SC allows customers to leave feedback and share the content with other customers, we are cautious about it. It works on both sides, as compared to the E-commerce system, sellers do not have the right to control the things (customers)."

SMM of company F shared that:

The customer's feedback was beneficial. We overcame those issues which we never thought. For example, due to technical reason, our website was down—a customer posted on our page that our website is not working. We fix the issue on a priority basis.

We have to be on top of everything; social wom empowered the customers worldwide. SMEs gets the different innovative ideas and queries from o

Mellinas and Reino (2019) illustrated that eWOM is a valuable resource for travellers to purchase decisions. Also, a Positive business reputation improves consumers' purchasing intentions, attitude toward the firm and its products, and brand loyalty (Jung et al., 2016). The owner of the company D asserted that:

"We send our customers a review link on their mobile phones, provided link takes them directly to the review section. Their reviews help us to look improve our service. Also, we use them for marketing purposes too. We share some of the reviews on our social media pages to give the assurance to new customers about us."

The Manager of company E argued that:

"Customer feedback is critical to us as that is the reflection of our service. Along with the positive, we had some negative feedback and rectified those issues urgently. We ask our customer to give us recommendation about our services, by doing this way we can have more business ideas."

The qualitative data of this study shows that social wom has a direct impact and positively affect sales through customer engagement. Customer engagement is described as a customer's reaction, response, or relationship to a company, commonly measured by how they respond to marketing campaigns (Bijmolt et al., 2010). Cvijikj and Michahelles (2013) elaborated that In social commerce, Customers' engagement with a firm has been assessed through their liking, sharing, and entering comments on the social media platforms.

The ICT managing director of company D further asserted that:

"There is always positive and negative feedback of any change. In terms of SC in our organisation, I would say we have got a mostly positive response from our customer. We have got different types of suggestions from our customers, for instance, customers are asking for chatbot service for quick customer query, and we are working on it."

4.6. Impact of SC adoption on SMEs:

An organisation can only expect to survive and grow if it is constantly adopting change and renewing itself. (Baker, 2007). Technology innovation is defined as a strategy that gives a company a competitive advantage by expanding its market and creating new economic prospects (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2018). The information technology revolution has created many opportunities and challenges for many organisations. As a result, managers must learn to adapt and maximise the benefits of ICT while avoiding the hazards that come with it. Information technology has brought customers and sellers together (Me, 2018), and a world without computers, mobile phones, or the Internet is unimaginable (AlBar and Hoque, 2019). Information technology was supposed to aid market penetration efforts by providing insight into prospective consumers' demands, including product quality, expected services, complaints about items and services offered, and even rival activity.

4.6.1 Market Penetration:

Market penetration is another sub-theme identified during the data TA procedure. The qualitative data of this study shows that SC helps SMEs increase their daily revenue, more efficient communication with customers, assist the customer in making a decision, business and product promotion locally and internationally.

The owner of company B asserted that:

"We have got a new customer, and our sale has been gone up. We are getting new customers daily. It's a lot easier for us to promote our business locally and worldwide. Happy customer recommends us online to their friend and families and shares our pages with their peers. After that, I would say that we are a local legend now."

The owner of company A stated that:

"We're able to better connect with our customers in many ways. It feels like nothing is impossible with social commerce. However, it is a blessing and a curse. We are out in the public eye more with negative aspects given to us by unhappy customers."

The SMM of the same company argued:

"Success is measured through marketing metrics such as the traffic brought in by our social media accounts, the conversion for online registrations, booking and so on. These are provided from each social media company, and we have our records which are used to track progress."

In the same context SMM of company C has stated:

"Social commerce technology is very beneficial for small businesses. With SC features, you can launch your business and promote your product in an effective way. I can say that after adopting SC, we are more popular now, and the customer does inquire us daily through social media platforms. Since it helps to decide the customers about the purchase, there is no need for the direct contact of person to person, as technology plays a medium role. The last thing I would like to say is that the adoption process is a bit expensive in Pakistan compared to developed countries."

Qualitative data illustrates to us that social commerce is benefiting small and medium enterprises in different manners. Although, the adoption process is not cost-effective in Pakistan in contrast to developed countries.

A two-way working system of social media platforms is another feature of social commerce. Information disbursement, increasing in the sale, targeting new customers, and effective advertising strategies attract SMEs. The owner of company D said that:

"Increased in the sale, reaching to potential customers within the country as well as in foreign countries, efficient way to promote our business and a more interactive platform working in both ways for consumers and sellers are beneficial for SMEs."

The General Manager of company C shared the same kind of thoughts:

"The one main advantage of using SC in business is to get the business flourish in a short period, and disadvantage is that you need a huge finance and have to face the technicalities while adopting SC in business."

5. Conclusions:

5.1. Introduction:

The goal of this last chapter is to provide an overview of the research effort. The significance of this chapter rests entirely in presenting the research's contributions and discussing their implications, identifying their limitations, and suggesting future study directions.

This section concludes the overview of the cases and how each research question can be answered, based on the findings and discussion in the previous chapter (4).

5.2. RQ 1: What are the different steps to adopt SC in Pakistan?

The findings show that SMEs in Pakistan are well aware of the importance of social commerce. Regarding SC adoption, it was concluded that adoption is an innovation in the organisation. In general, SMEs engaged in the case studies adopted it in the following steps: prior knowledge of SC, decision-making, self-learning and social presence.

To investigate and deploy SC as a viable project, SMEs needed appropriate and sufficient ICT infrastructure across all disciplines (Bouwman et al., 2019). In contrast, the study found that Pakistan's IT infrastructure does not completely support or adopt SC characteristics (Qalati et al., 2021). Furthermore, this study concludes that SMEs do not have the formal organisational structure and IT department to run SC project. This study also suggests that SMEs use SC mainly for promotions and marketing purposes of creating brand awareness and social assurance (Trust) among customers. Therefore, this study concludes that the first step SMEs take to adopt SC is to create social media pages; this supports them in spreading information, communicating with customers, and offering them to advertise their deals. Easy to use, market search, follow market leaders, support from friends and family, personal knowledge assist the owners or managers in adopting SC by themselves. According to the findings of this study, most of the SMEs in Pakistan adopt SC naturally based on their prior awareness and understanding of SC. The company's awareness of SC popularity and internal interest in SC from senior management or staff influenced the decision to adopt SM usage.

Furthermore, Ikumoro, A.O. and Jawad (2019) illustrated that the choice to employ SC for commercial purposes was often made by the owner/top management, with no apparent planning or engagement of

skilled staff. Many SMEs' SC adoption processes lacked proper understanding and strategic planning. In most situations, once a company opted to adopt SC, and the decision was finalized and did not require any further reassessment or confirmation. Persuasion and confirmation phases were not supported as part of the SMEs' experience of SC adoption phases. Once the choice to utilise SC was made, several SMEs tended to deploy it in a hurried, uneducated manner, frequently beginning with the usage of numerous SM platforms and functionalities, primarily for marketing activities.

It was found in the finding and discussion chapter that the only number of SMEs handover the whole adoption process to the IT vendors and improve their SC adoption process accordingly. Due to the lack of financial resources and shortage of highly skilled people, most SMEs follow their SM pages and assess their performance by looking at the followers or likes on the business page. If the situation was improved and further developing, they invest more in the hardware, put more effort, money and time accordingly.

5.3. RQ 2. What are the drivers and challenges of SC adoption amongst SMEs in Pakistan?

The TOE model was used to identify the technological, organisational and environmental factors to answer this question. The finding of this chapter shows that several factors are influencing the adoption of SC in Pakistan. As previously stated, this study aimed to investigate the influencing factors related to SC adoption by SMEs in Pakistan. Therefore, it was essential to identify the driver and challenges that prevent the adoption of SC.

In terms of technological factor, this study has identified several factors impacting the successful adoption of technology in SMEs in Pakistan. All participants stated that the availability and quality of IT infrastructure are the most critical factors for integrating successful SC adoption in SMEs in Pakistan. On the other hand, it was concluded that Pakistan's flawed banking and IT system (Naqvi, 2018), quality of hardware tools (Jahan et al., 2019), fewer choices of software and speed of the broadband (Tanveer and Hassan, 2020), and availability of skilled workforce are significant impediments to the SC adoption (Iqbal and Ahmed, 2021). The finding of case studies illustrates that E-readiness in society and IT knowledge are the additional main challenge for SMEs to adopt SC. Ease of use, cost-effectiveness entry, the popularity of SM platforms among the customers, ease of marketing, promotion of brands and deals are the main drivers to adopt SC among SMEs in Pakistan.

From an organisational perspective, many factors were identified as influential factors on the adoption of SC in Pakistan. Such as organisational structure, lack of financial resource, lack of HR support, no

managerial support, no clear strategy of Research and Development and social support. Two more sub-themes, (i) Poor HR Planning (ii) Importance of Financial Resources and Management support, were identified under organisational factors. It was also revealed that all these factors are interlinked to each other. The adoption of SC is more challenging to those SMEs who do not have the proper structure of the organisation (Cimini et al., 2020). Most SMEs are family-run business, and the controlling bodies are just the Owner or manager. Therefore, the investment in people and adoption of change need to be decided by one person.

In term of environmental context, Technological and organisational factors are interrelated to the environmental factors. Lack of customer knowledge, Pakistan's education system, friend and family support, staff knowledge are known as traditional business practices. As mentioned in the previous chapter, consumers are unaware of the technology features and those who know about it but do not trust local brands' lack of IT system and infrastructure (Dinulescu et al., 2021). The leaders of the SMEs are also reluctant to get IT services from third parties (Salam et al., 2021). As the outcome of the SC adoption is not measured. Therefore, most managers and owners focus on their learning and get help from friend & family members. This practice makes an impact on in-house training sessions to train their internal staff. Lack of IT knowledge of employees pushes them to follow everyday business practices.

5.4. RQ 3. What are the critical success factors influencing SC adoption?

The SC adoption of SMEs in Pakistan also had to be assessed thoroughly to identify these influential factors. To determine the critical success factor, the questions of semi-structured interviews were based on the TOE model. The research finding revealed that the following factors are influenced and positively impact SC adoption in SMEs in Pakistan. Role of Leadership, shortage of skilled staff, IT vendor role, Role of GoP, Customer Trust and Social WOM were identified as critical success factors to adopt SC.

Innovation of the SMEs leadership found as the critical success factor to adopt the SC. The finding of this research found that those SMEs whose leaders are more innovative adopt SC. The leadership are the people who have significant control to bring change within organisations. This study shows the substantial relationship between SC adoption and the characteristic of leadership. It was recommended that the chances of adopting new technology for SMEs are increased by decentralised decision-making and imaginative leadership (Giotopoulos et al., 2017).

The finding of this study illustrates that small-medium enterprises have no formal structure and IT departments. These issues directly impact the organisational recruitment process to find suitable and highly skilled people for their organisations (Noshad et al., 2019). During the semi-structured interview, it was found that the education system of Pakistan is not fully developed. Higher education providers are not teaching and introducing the latest technologies in the context. Therefore, it is difficult for SMEs in Pakistan to find skilled staff.

The role of the IT vendor is another critical success factor. Due to the shortage of highly skilled people in the market, IT vendors can play a significant role for the SME to adopt SC. The finding of this study illustrates that IT vendors must understand their market segment and address their objectives more efficiently. It was also concluded that careful selection of IT vendors is essential for effective SC adoption,

The case studies have shown that government could play a critical role in adopting SC in Pakistan. It was also noted that there is a lack of coordination between the Government and small businesses. Better IT infrastructure, coordination between governmental departments, banking legislation, educational system, and technology awareness among citizens could support SMEs in adopting SC. For instance, it was revealed that corruption in the country, incompetent staff, lengthy information process and government policies are making reluctant to SMEs approach the local government for support. It recommended that government could play a critical role to enhance SMEs capability to adopt SC.

Customer trust was found another critical factor to adopt SC in SMEs. The finding of this study tells us that customers are not very inclined towards the adoption of the latest technology. Pierre and Peters (2020), illustrated that Lack of government support to bring awareness to society is another fundamental issue. Therefore, some organisations see it as not a very successful technology. Subramanian (2017), identified that from an organisational perspective, Customer trust is directly linked to many problems such as lack of IT infrastructure, payment mechanism etc. For instance, the consumer in Pakistan less likely to order anything online due to privacy and security issues and lack of Trust on social media pages. Therefore, small organisations using social media platforms just for marketing purposes.

On the other hand, the Pakistani population uses these platforms just for fun and to consumes their extra time (Naqvi et al., 2020). It was suggested that government institutions and other stakeholders must work together to solve this issue (Naqvi et al., 2020).. It was noticed that the Pakistani population

is much familiar with Facebook and Instagram. Therefore, customers' Trust in businesses and online payments could boost SMEs' performance and encourage more SMEs to adopt SC.

The result of this research indicated that SMEs might considerably benefit from social WOM. Social media allows SMEs to get seen merely by following particular influencers in hundreds or even millions. The literature has revealed a link between Trust and social-wom. Erkan and Evans (2016) recognised that confidence in social-WOM is vital to customers, especially if it is anonymous, not face-to-face, and responsible for their purchase decisions. It is essential to fight against well-known companies with critical customers and renowned brands, as SMEs cannot generally spend a great deal on communications (Beverage, 2015). Customers' attitude towards social commerce is dependent on confidence and the advantages it would obtain (Yeon et al., 2019). The decision-making process was facilitated after the influencer won the spirit of the participants.

5.5. Theoretical Contribution:

By examining and using the TOE structure, this research offers a significant theoretical contribution to implementing innovative new social trade technologies by SMEs. This research draws on emerging literature on IT innovation adoption by SMEs, which has concluded that various factors influenced the adoption of technology. Moreover, this study is based on the technology-Organisation-environment (TOE) framework to investigate the factors affecting social commerce adoption in the organisational context by SMEs.

This study helps to understand better how the decisions to adopt new technologies and social commerce in small and medium-sized businesses are influenced. This study has thus offered an enhanced knowledge of the factors influencing social commerce adoption in SMEs in Pakistan. Also, this study provides three contributions related to identifying several phases for adopting the SC and the drivers and obstacles of adopting the SC in Pakistan. In addition, this study presents recommendations for a more successful SC adoption based on the TOE model.

The TOE framework has been investigated to study the factors that influence SC adoption in SMEs in Pakistan. The findings presented additional critical elements for the TOE framework, including technological, organisational, and environmental aspects, which gave new insights into factors that might influence the adoption of SC in Pakistan. Drivers and challenges were suggested, facilitating and speeding up the adoption process and contributing to favourable results. In addition, the results of this study revealed some of the primary practices that might either improve adoption in SMEs, clarify best practice, or advise on an effective method for SC adoption, as well as the mismanagements that should be avoided while adopting SC in Pakistani SMEs. It is the first study to investigate the adoption

process of SC in SMEs in Pakistan, as most studies focus on consumers' adoption of social commerce (Abed, 2016; Akman & Mishra, 2017; Hajli, 2015).

Also, it is one of the few research that has identified leadership (owners and other departmental managers) in adopting SC as new technology in SMEs in Pakistan. The role of government, customer trust, highly skilled staff, and social ewom highlighted as critical success factors to adopt SC in SMEs. These factors have also directly affected the performance of SMEs in Pakistan.

Above all, this research gave an exhaustive suggested method for SC by SMEs to improve many company performance elements. The framework underlined the need in determining new technologies in developing countries to include technological, organisational and environmental factors. It provided insights into the relevance of perceived technical advantages and possible positive outcomes for SMEs to speed up the decision-making process on SC adoption.

Furthermore, the current research contributed to the academic literature on ICT systems and innovation in business adoption, implementation and the aspects discussed in the literature review. This study also provided more information on SC as emerging technology, including features, technology, and general advantages for SMEs. It is particularly relevant to the situation in Pakistan, in which no research on this issue has been undertaken, primarily about the knowledge of the present SC adoption process among SMEs. The current commercial use of prominent SC platforms in Pakistan and together with some essential issues surrounding them. In addition, in the literature study, concepts and methodologies were discovered that were likely to interest both SMEs and academics and maybe further examined in the future. The present study also provides recommendations to SMEs to improve and sustain their enterprises.

Without the help of government and corporate institutions, mainly contracting agencies and regulators, various challenges of technology adoption cannot be solved (Nazir & Zhu, 2018). Therefore, this study emphasizes the role of the government and provides recommendations to the Government of Pakistan to enhance their services to support SMEs within the country. Its theoretical contribution is, therefore, further research that might lead to the theory being adopted.

This research's last and most important contribution is how the SMEs can benefit from social commerce components such as social-wom and Trust. Previously none of the studies identified the role of these critical factors to adopt the SC, especially in Pakistan. These results showed that the scope of challenges and obstacles related to the growth of SC was more broadly viewed.

5.6. Research Implications:

The present study results have significant implications for several groups of stakeholders, including business owners and managers and government agencies responsible for the general growth of SMEs, specifically for fostering new technology adoption at these critical business segments.

5.6.1. Practical Implications:

The main general implication of some of the interviews in this study is that small and medium-sized enterprises should adopt social commerce on the initial stage rather than the 'wait and watch' policies. Early adoption was encouraged in any IS breakthrough since small and medium-sized companies can reach clients and increase their capital.

The most clear evaluated model that SMEs in Pakistan may use to assess the technical, organisational and environmental circumstances under which technology is employed for social commerce. The TOE model established in this study might be used by SME owner-managers: (i) to evaluate circumstances for social commerce to be used and (ii) to raise knowledge of the numerous aspects impacting the choice for these technologies. The model may also be a reference point for other SMEs interested in exploring the adoption of social commerce in the future by raising awareness of the influential factors to adopt SC technology in SMEs.

In terms of social commerce adoption, Trust is an ongoing issue (Hajli, 2017). In practice, the consequences of the results do not imply that Trust among business partners throughout the Pakistani environment should be avoided. Instead, potential adopters should establish a balanced relationship and structure to explore new chances effectively, ensuring a positive aspect of Trust that should also be sufficiently flexible for them to explore and seek a wider variety of options. The outcomes of this research also have a significant impact on social-wom. Companies want customers to trust and believe them (Ioanas, 2020). Therefore, they use trusted advertising to accept them. These kinds of acts have caused people to wonder about the substance of social media platforms.

5.6.2. Implication for the Policy Makers:

The SMEDA and PTA are two leading government bodies and are responsible for the growth of Pakistani SMEs and national policymakers. These two institutes may benefit from the results of this study to develop and strengthen the social commerce of SMEs in Pakistan because of the implications of the findings of this study. Below you may see the implications for policymakers. SMEDA and PTA

can coordinate and build collaborations with developing social commerce consultants or IT vendors to speed up the adoption of social commerce by SMEs and establish strategies to implement best practice in SC adoption to solve the identified challenge of shortages of highly skilled people.

The study suggests public officials that sets SC rules and regulations for SMEs need to be developed for developing countries. In Pakistan, there is no permanent policy for the growth and development of SMEs. This research also offers information to the government to enable SC adoption for SMEs and provides comprehensive data and networking system to improve and expand the SME knowledge base. In addition, it also offers to the government that how to improve the information system. To ensure that SMEs can comprehend and benefit from SC phenomena following international standards, governments and institutions such as SMEDA and other private institutions should organise international conferences, seminars, and workshops on the use of ICT and SC.

The Government of Pakistan might also create and maintain the SC infrastructure necessary to allow online payments in the local business environment and other organisations, including banks. To create a safe online transaction platform and protect online companies and customers from card theft and hacking, the government can also play a significant role in regulating different cybercrime laws.

5.6.3. Implications for the Managers:

A well-defined SC adoption strategy aligned with its IT plans and policies should also be prepared for its management. With the defined plan, organisations may improve competition and assist business partners in applying this technology in their local business environment (Horváth and Szabó, 2019). Owners and managers in developing nations may also benefit from various scenarios by comparing their attempts to enhance SC adoption with advanced countries. Owners and managers are also urged to attend seminars and forums on technology. Through this contact, they will learn from industry experts and other technology consultants and communicate with them to increase their SC environment and technical status (Horváth and Szabó, 2019).

Small business managers have less influence over what the customers say about their company. They need to work carefully to gain control of their reputation with their online followers. So if an eminent post on social media advertises a product for small and medium-sized enterprises, the audience is aware of the brand, leading to greater awareness and purchasing intention (Tan et al., 2018). This result will also help to increase the revenue. SMEs are therefore more equipped and more likely to overcome

any communication challenges and rebound with the deployment of more persuasive promotions (Horváth and Szabó, 2019).

Finally, SMEs that include social WOM in the social media marketing mix will have a more significant chance to become more competitive versus bigger businesses, as they may influence customers' purchasing behaviour directly, as social media users are more inclined to act. Thus, marketing managers of small businesses should carefully handle favourable reviews as they are less effective if they do not include information and facts (Ramanathan et al., 2017).

5.7. Limitation of the Research and Future Research Opportunities:

The findings of this research have exposed the primary technological, organisational and environmental factors that influence the successful adoption of SC in SMEs in Pakistan. However, there are several limitations to this study that will be discussed further below.

The availability of information was the first limitation of this study. A lengthy interview questionnaire was sent out to 15 small and medium enterprises with a cover letter stating that the study researcher was gathering data from outside the country. As a result, respondents expressed reservations about disclosing information regarding the governments and related institutes roles in SC adoption.

Another limitation at the organisational level is the accesses to obtain the relevant information regarding the phenomena under investigation. The majority of managers were reluctant and cautious about disclosing information about their Owner or senior managers within organisations because they feared that if this information reached them, they would be fired. To address this issue, the researcher affirmed (through consent forms) that the material gathered during the interviews would be used solely for research purposes. Only the researcher and supervisors would have access to it.

It would also be valuable to interview and analyse a broader range of cases with high success rates regarding their SM adoption to determine the shared best practices for the successful implementation of SM in SMEs empirically. It would also be helpful to conduct more case studies of a similar type in different sectors in the Saudi market, to test the broader generalizability of the theories proposed, and to determine whether the factors identified by this study influence SM adoption in the same manner in business sectors other than the retail and service sectors, and the various subsectors, assessed by the current project

Secondly, only seven SMEs from two main cities (Islamabad and Rawalpindi) participated in this research and one industry: hospitality and tourism. As a result, future studies should include additional SMEs and sectors from other Pakistan cities to understand better the role of their local government institutes and their desire to assist other SMEs in their environment. In addition, comparing the results to those of other emerging economies and generalising them to other industries would be intriguing.

In addition, this research expanded the area of the TOE framework (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990) to uncover critical success factors to adopt SC in SMEs in Pakistan. To better understand the responsibilities of leadership and management while adopting SC as a new technology in their SMEs, more study is needed to extend the TOE framework in different situations, particularly emerging economies, by using the mix-method methodology.

This research investigated and identified the initial main steps while adopting SC in SMEs in Pakistan. Future research could be done to identify the main adoption stages in the context of SMEs in Pakistan.

5.8. Recommendations to SMEs to make effective Strategy to adopt SC:

5.8.1. RQ 4. What is the impact of SC adoption on SMEs, and what recommendations can be made to adopt SC more effectively?

This section provides information on RQ 4 and proposed recommendations to improve SC adoption in Pakistan. The strategies can be described in two ways: (i) the role of leadership and consideration of social commerce components (ii) the role of government (iii) the role of IT vendors

The findings of this study helped to identify the most critical determinants affecting SMEs in adopting SC as a new online technology in the country. As discussed in previous sections of this chapter, the leadership innovativeness and self-knowledge of Owners and managers can play a significant role in adopting SC in SMEs. The study indicates that the leadership must be visionary in terms of adopting SC as new technology. Their core knowledge could be beneficial for the organisation. It was also concluded that those organisation whose leaders are optimistic and have basic knowledge about the latest technology adopted the SC effectively. The utilisation of available resource in the organisation with the assistance of leaders combined with social commerce components can provide a better path towards the successful adoption of SC in SMEs. Social Presence, Trust and social-wom were found most effective social commerce components. Also, interlinking between these components could

devised sales growth and lead to more social commerce adoption in SMEs. However, the other social commerce components such as website attributions, social support were also defined as adequate.

Government social commerce rules are lacking, as there was less support from governmental institutions and public and commercial banks. The findings also show that the government's current role in the country is insignificant in promoting SC. Its efforts to support SMEs at various stages have been slow and insufficient. As a result, the government and local business organisations must establish a permanent and efficient SC policy that can enhance and expedite SC laws and regulations to help SMEs in all industries. Individual clients will also gain from this since they will be able to fully engage in the options available.

In addition, the government also needs to organise a training session for the SMEs to promote social commerce technology and provide assistance to adopt these technologies. To ensure that SMEs in Pakistan are up to date and fully developed according to international standards. Government training programs for SC and ICT can only be implemented with the collaboration of public and private bodies and other stakeholders such as telecommunication service providers, IT consultants, higher education institutes etc.

SMEs who do not have adequate resources to adopt the SC can benefit from IT services from IT vendors. Knowledge of leadership is also directly linked to this factor. Their knowledge can assist them in selecting a suitable IT consultant for their organization. The Owner or manager's experience in embracing the SC technology could support the IT vendor in the limited budget. As noted in the finding of this research, the shortage of skilled people is another critical factor to adopt SC. Therefore, those organization that cannot recruit highly professional staff due to their higher financial demand can promote the SC by opting in the service from IT vendors.

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Appendices:

Appendix 1:

Participant Information Sheet

Research Title: Influencing Factors of Social Commerce Adoption on SMEs in Pakistan:
 Implications for SMEs in Hospitality and Tourism Industry based on case

Researcher: Muhammad Bilal

Course: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

Department: Business and Enterprise

About the Study

Technological development has changed the ways of conducting business. One of these changes is the provision of various services on traditional and non-traditional channels, i.e., in-store, online, click and collect, multi-channel, etc. These changes in service providers require the assessment of the service quality. This research study is aimed to determine the impact of social commerce adoption of SMEs in Pakistan in the hospitality and tourism sector.

The social relationships of consumers, enhanced by the emergence of Web 2.0 technologies, enable them to support each other and take an active role working on the internet. This advancement has emerged through social commerce and is primarily because of Web 2.0. Web 2.0 has increased communication between consumers by introducing new channels such as blogs, social networks, social media and communities. There are also new channels for businesses to get in touch with customers. This research discusses the role of social commerce and uses the TOE theory to propose a recommendation for social commerce adoption.

The adoption of s-commerce is a critical issue, particularly for the SME sector. Small businesses are one of the most significant changing divisions of e-commerce. Hence, the purpose of the study is to provide recommendations to developing countries. This model needs to be investigated through an examination into current barriers to s-commerce adoption in those countries.

This study will aim to understand better the challenges, barriers, and influencing factors on social commerce adoption that can help SMEs in Pakistan enhance the implementation of social commerce.

Who is responsible for the study?

I am the sole researcher working on this topic, and I will be collecting all the primary data in person, which will be in the form of semi-structured interview recordings in the first phase

Risk Involved

The participants of the study will remain anonymous throughout the study. The information obtained from the participants will be kept confidential from the public and will be used for this study only. The

participants will be free to withdraw themselves from the study at any stage without providing any reason.

Participation and Monetary Benefits

Participation in the study is voluntary, and there will be no monetary rewards for the participants. The data collected will not be used for any commercial purposes.

Contact

If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Name: Muhammad Bilal

Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 2:

Research Consent Form

Research Title: Influencing Factors of Social Commerce Adoption on SMEs in Pakistan:
Implications for SMEs in Hospitality and Tourism Industry based on case studies

Researcher: Muhammad Bilal
Course: Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)
Department: Business and Enterprise

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information about the study as provided in the participant information sheet.
- I confirm that I was given the opportunity to ask questions, and I am satisfied by the answers provided by the researcher.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study at any time.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential, and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to the use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving for future research.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant's Name

Designation / Title

Participant's Signature

Date

Researcher's Name
Muhammad Bilal

Appendix 3:

Semi-Structured Interview Questions

Name:

Age:

Education:

institute:

Job Role/ Designation:

No of years in job role:

Organisation's Background and Structure:

1. Could you please give us a detailed history of your organisation? Including the number of employees, a year since incorporated and main service industry?

Section A

Objective 1: To understand different stages SMEs in Pakistan go through during the Social Commerce adoption process

2. What were the main stages you had to go through in order to adopt SC for the first time? (For example, decision making, preparation, planning, consulting, market scanning, and implementation).
3. Do you have a specific strategic plan for employing SC in your business?
4. Can you tell us some details regarding the adoption process, setting up, and if you used any outside help and support to start using SC?
5. If you use your own expertise then, did you train it in-house?
6. What changes have you had to make when you first start using SNs for business purposes internally and externally?

Section B

Objective 2: To understand the critical success factors influencing the SC adoption among SMEs in Pakistan

6. How important do you think the role of leadership or top management during this SC adoption process?
7. How important do you think vendor support/ consultant`s role impacts the SC adoption?
8. How important do you think organisational financial capabilities and resources are for the success of the SC adoption?
9. How does organisational culture impacts SC adoption?
10. Does government play any role in the technological development of SMEs?
11. What limitations did you face during the SC adoption stage?

Section C

Objective 3: To investigate challenges that SMEs in Pakistan face during the SC adoption

12. What (in your perspective) has been the biggest impediment to adopt the SC technology so far?
 - a. In terms of User interaction? Managerial Issue? Technical Issues? Organisational issues? Environmental Issue?
13. What other challenges did you experience during the SC adoption process?

Such as:

- IT skills of managers and operational employees
 - ICT knowledge and Experience of employees
 - Not having a clear set of guidelines to follow SC adoption to implementation
 - Inadequate resources like financial and human capital with infrastructure.
14. How did you overcome those challenges?

Section D

Objective 4: To make recommendations to SMEs in Pakistan for a successful SC adoption.

15. Have you received feedback from the users after the implementation?

- a. Are they positive or negative feedback?
16. What are the main advantages and disadvantages of using SC in your business?
17. How do you measure your success in utilizing SC?
18. Do you think the adoption was carried out most effectively?
19. Can you suggest any changes to improve the effectiveness of the adoption process for future projects?

Appendix 4:

Transcript Sample

Organization's Background and Structure:

1. Could you please give us a detailed history of your organization? Including the number of employees, a year since incorporated and main service industry?

Our organization, company A, is a hotel service established in 2001. We are a family business, with only 47 people hired at our service. We operate and maintain two hotels now, but we are looking to further expand within the next two years. Our contemporary hotel offers 33 different rooms to choose from, an indoor pool included, and complimentary breakfast.

Section A

Objective 1: To understand different stages SMEs in Pakistan go through during the Social Commerce adoption process

2. What were the main stages you had to go through in order to adopt SC for the first time? (For example, decision making, preparation, planning, consulting, market scanning, and implementation).

The most crucial stage we had to go through was to establish ourselves on social media. We decided to focus mainly on Facebook and Twitter to gain attraction. On top of self-advertisement, we had to find a way to make sales online, which we did by offering nightly stays on the Facebook marketplace.

3. Do you have a specific strategic plan for employing SC in your business?

We planned to advertise ourselves on Twitter by combining our advertisements with popular culture, including memes, jokes, etc. Our goal is to reach many people of different kinds to build popularity and open more locations. We focused on offering online deals through social

media platforms. Those booking which we get through social media advertisement, we can ask the customer to leave us feedback on our social media page. This is an easy way to share customer feedback on our social media page, promoting our sale.

4. Can you tell us some details regarding the adoption process, setting up, and if you used any outside help and support to start using SC?

We didn't use any direct outside help, but we did look at the success of social commerce and humour by looking at other companies in the market. They were our main inspiration in combining humour with social media.

5. If you use your own expertise then, did you train it in-house?

Yes. My family employees and I used self-exploration to build our skills on social media. Instead of researching, we decided to use hands-on strategies to develop ourselves better.

6. What changes have you had to make when you first start using SNs for business purposes internally and externally?

We made a mutual decision to focus our posts on computers instead of using mobile devices. That way, we were able to make more posts faster and still had plenty of time to publish our vacancies on Facebook Marketplace.

Section B

Objective 2: To understand the critical success factors influencing the SC adoption among SMEs in Pakistan

6. How important do you think the role of leadership or top management during this SC adoption process?

I believe leadership is the most critical aspect of any task that may need to be completed. With that being said, we used our leadership to develop our idea of establishing social commerce in the first place.

7. How important do you think vendor support/ consultant`s role impacts the SC adoption?

It's one of the most important aspects! Without vendor support, there'd be no business in the first place. They also play a direct role in social commerce adoption. The responsibility of a vendor supporter is to promote our business.

8. How important do you think organizational financial capabilities and resources are for the success of the SC adoption?

I don't think it's as important as some would say. Sure, it helps to have it, but we don't have many financial resources or capabilities. We have a screen and people, and it gets the job done.

9. How does organizational culture impacts SC adoption?

It's essential to develop the organizational culture to develop a social commerce adoption. Our organisation is very pressed on building chemistry and relationships, as a family business should, and it helps us connect with our audience more than most companies would.

10. Does government play any role in the technological development of SMEs?

It does play a more significant role than we can casually assume. The popularity of high government officials can take a toll on social media and social commerce, as we've seen with former US President Donald Trump. During his presidency, he drew many republican officials off of Twitter, along with their supporters, and onto different platforms.

11. What limitations did you face during the SC adoption stage?

It's easy to say money was a definite limitation, as we have little amounts of it. However, it did not wholly hinder our adoption, and we could still get our job done. I would say our biggest hindrance was our popularity from the start, as it is very low.

Section C

Objective 3: To investigate challenges that SMEs in Pakistan face during the SC adoption

12. What (in your perspective) has been the biggest impediment to adopt the SC technology so far?

From my perspective, it was everything we overcame before we were able to consider social commerce. We faced bankruptcy many times and had very many vacancies at a time.

a. In terms of User interaction? Managerial Issue? Technical Issues? Organizational issues? Environmental Issue?

13. What other challenges did you experience during the SC adoption process?

Such as:

- IT skills of managers and operational employees
- ICT knowledge and Experience of employees
- Not having a clear set of guidelines to follow SC adoption to implementation
- Inadequate resources like financial and human capital with infrastructure.

One of our biggest silent challengers was the effect the Coronavirus took against us. The 13 of us live in the hotel together, so you can imagine we can get crowded together at times, and we, unfortunately, had a casualty along the way.

14. How did you overcome those challenges?

It was important for us to remain a family. Though tensions were high and relationships would be difficult to maintain for a while, we were still family at the end of the day and realized we would not rather have it differently.

Section D

Objective 4: To make recommendations to SMEs in Pakistan for a successful SC adoption.

15. Have you received feedback from the users after the implementation?

a. Are they positive or negative feedback?

We've had an equal amount of both, I'd say. We're lucky to have not lost business, but we haven't really gained business yet because of our negative feedback.

16. What are the main advantages and disadvantages of using SC in your business?

As an advantage, we're able to better connect with our customers in many ways. It feels like nothing is impossible with social commerce. However, it is a blessing and a curse. We are out in the public eye more with negative aspects given to us by unhappy customers.

17. How do you measure your success in utilizing SC?

I wouldn't call it much yet, but establishing it gives me a good feeling that things will be better.

18. Do you think the adoption was carried out most effectively?

No, I don't. However, what's done is done, and we have everything to look forward.

19. Can you suggest any changes to improve effectiveness of the adoption process for a future projects?

I would say that we should utilize our resources more. It is important to use what we have to our advantage instead of ignoring it for faster and easier success, as it will usually generate less success in the long run.

Appendix 5:

26/02/2021

Dear Muhammad Bilal,

Your application 16077: Social Commerce Adoption in Pakistan: Implication for SMEs, submission 13351, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner